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Contributors	Pauline O'Donohoe, Joanne Casserly, Catherine Waters – MI Luis Poersch, Alessandro Cardozo – FURG Brett Macey, John Bolton, Marissa Brink-Hull, Mark Cyrus, Bas de Vos, Nick Loubser – UCT, DFFE, VIK Kati Michalek, Adrian Macleod – SAMS
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1 Summary

This manual was created as part of the WP2 'New IMTA value chains and production methods' of the H2020 All Atlantic Ocean Sustainable, Profitable and Resilient Aquaculture (ASTRAL) project. It provides detailed instructions of the cultivation technique for each of the species trialled at the ASTRAL IMTA labs. Three types of IMTA systems are included in this report, including an open-water IMTA system, a land-based pump ashore system and a RAS Biofloc system. The ASTRAL species included fed and extractive species of fish, seaweeds, molluscs, echinoderms and crustaceans.

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3 Introduction

3.1 ASTRAL

The H2020 project ASTRAL developed new, sustainable, profitable and resilient value chains for integrated multi-trophic aquaculture (IMTA) production in the marine environment, within the framework of existing, emerging and potential Atlantic markets. This project gathered four IMTA labs including open-water (Ireland and Scotland), land-based pump-ashore with partial (50 %) recirculation (South Africa) and recirculation 'biofloc' land-based (Brazil) systems and one prospective IMTA lab (Argentina), focusing on a regional challenge-based perspective, including fish, mollusc, echinoderm, crustacean and algae species. ASTRAL assessed how to increase circularity using IMTA methods of cultivation by 50-60 % compared to monoculture aquaculture and provided a circular business model, boosting revenue diversification for aquaculture producers increasing profitability by at least 30 %. New and improved innovative technology has been developed, including biosensors, sensors, Internet of Things (IoT) and an Artificial Intelligence (AI) data analytics platform has been validated at the IMTA labs. Potential environmental and climatic risks for Northern and Southern Atlantic regions were addressed, delivering a monitoring programme and recommendations for Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs), pathogens and microplastics. ASTRAL has delivered an ambitious and gender-sensitive human capital development plan (HUCAP) which seeks to improve professional skills and create a highly trained workforce. This project gathered a collaborative ecosystem within the project framework bringing together and connecting industrial partners, SMEs, scientists, policy makers, social representatives and other relevant stakeholders, promoting data exchange, knowledge sharing and business opportunities.

3.2 IMTA

IMTA is defined as the farming of aquaculture species from different trophic levels, and with complementary ecosystem functions in the same area or at the same site. This type of integrated culturing allows one species' uneaten feed, waste, and nutrients to be recaptured and converted into fertilizer and feed for the other aquaculture species. This approach takes advantage of synergistic interactions between species. The combination of fed aquaculture species (e.g., finfish or shrimp) with extractive aquaculture species, which utilizes the inorganic nutrients (e.g. seaweeds) and organic nutrients (e.g. suspension and deposit-feeders such as bivalves, urchins, sea cucumber) enhance growth in this type of system. IMTA aims to aid ecological balanced systems to improve environmental sustainability, enhance ecosystem services, boost economic stability by increasing biomass, lowering

costs, providing product diversification, reducing risk, and creating jobs in rural communities while advancing societal acceptability¹.

3.3 ASTRAL IMTA Laboratories

The IMTA labs form the heart of the ASTRAL project, providing the context for developing cost-effective, profitable and sustainable IMTA production. The term 'IMTA labs' refers to the locations of the IMTA production sites and is not to be confused with a typical laboratory set up. The ASTRAL IMTA labs consist of Recirculating Aquaculture system (RAS) Biofloc, open-water and land-based pump ashore production systems. The locations of the ASTRAL IMTA labs are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Locations of IMTA labs around the Atlantic Ocean

¹ Chopin, T. (2013). Aquaculture, Integrated Multi-trophic (IMTA). In: Christou, P., Savin, R., Costa-Pierce, B.A., Misztal, I., Whitelaw, C.B.A. (eds) Sustainable Food Production. Springer, New York, NY. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-5797-8_173

3.4 ASTRAL Production Manual

This manual contains detailed descriptions of the methods employed to produce all 23 of the ASTRAL species trialled in this research project. This manual will give guidance on how to grow the species and the parameters needed for their successful production, including welfare, health and biosecurity.

3.5 Sources of information on IMTA production and IMTA research projects

- ASTRAL H2020 project <https://www.astral-project.eu/>
- IMPAQT H2020 project <https://impaqtproject.eu/about-impagt/>
- IMPAQT massive open online course (MOOC) in Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture and Precision Aquaculture <https://www.open.edu/openlearncreate/course/view.php?id=7116>
- AquaVitae H2020 project <https://aquavitaeproject.eu/>
- AquaVitae MOOC - Sustainable Aquaculture for Low Trophic Species <https://open.uit.no/courses/course-v1:UiT+SALTS101+AquaVitae/about>
- INTEGRATE project (INTERREG Atlantic Area 2014-2020 Programme) – Transition towards IMTA in the Atlantic Area <https://integrate-imta.eu/>
- IDREEM EU FP7 project – Increasing Industrial Resource Efficiency in European Mariculture <https://www.bmrs.ie/bmrs-projects/past/idreem>

4 Open Water IMTA

IMTA production can be carried out in several differing aquaculture systems. Open water IMTA, as carried out in the ASTRAL project in IMTA lab Ireland and IMTA lab Scotland, refers to species production at sea with mooring structures in place to anchor the growing structures to the seabed. This type of system is continuously exposed to the environmental conditions including wind and wave action. Figure 2 shows a potential IMTA set up in open-water.

Figure 2. Schematic of potential open-water IMTA scenario. ©Marine Institute

Temperate Climate

The open-water IMTA production described in this manual has taken place in temperate climatic conditions in Ireland and Scotland. Temperate climates are defined as having an average temperature above 0 °C but below 18 °C in their coldest month. Temperate maritime climates are characterised by the absence of extreme climatic conditions. This generally refers to mild winter temperatures and warm summers. Rainfall is frequent but not extreme and the climate generally is free from hazardous atmospheric systems².

² <http://thebritishgeographer.weebly.com/the-climate-of-the-british-isles.html>

Climate change effects often remain difficult to discern from natural variations in environmental conditions. However, marine aquaculture relies on coastal habitats known to be threatened by climate change impacts such as sea-level rise, warming coastal waters, changes in rainfall and storm patterns; to name a few. Expected impacts are strongly related to the industry's dependence on the marine environment for suitable biophysical conditions and may also create new niches and market opportunities for aquaculture species of the future.³

³ Callaway, R., Shinn, A.P., Grenfell, S.E. et al. (2012). Review of climate change impacts on marine aquaculture in the UK and Ireland. *Aquat. Conserv. Mar. Freshw. Ecosyst.* 22, 389–421. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aqc.2247>

4.1 Open Water IMTA Labs

4.1.1 IMTA Lab Ireland – Open Water IMTA System

Figure 3. Location of Irish IMTA lab Lehanagh Pool.

Lehanagh Pool Research site is a coastal aquaculture installation located 0.25 km from the shore in Bertraghboy Bay, on the West Coast of Ireland (53°24'03.3"N, 9°49'09.4"W) (Figure 3). The site is a licensed 23.3-hectare multi-species research site. It is a fully experimental, non-commercial cultivation site operated by the Marine Institute. The site is within a sheltered enclosed area to the east of Bertraghboy Bay that is predominantly shallow (Figure 3). The location is relatively sheltered with no significant fetch or swell and waves are produced by local wind conditions. It is located approximately 1 km from the nearest pier used for site access. There are two sources of freshwater input, Cashel Bay and the Gowla River. The location of the site in the Connemara area of Ireland, is subjected to runoff from rainfall, reducing salinity and increasing turbidity with high particulate loading. Due to runoff, surface salinity ranges from 24 to 35 psu but is typically > 32 psu. Tidal range is approximately 5 m and water temperature ranges from 5 to 18 °C. The depth of the production site ranges from 15 m to 20 m. The mean current speeds are 0.040 and 0.028 m/s for mid-water and seabed, respectively, and residual currents and directions are 0.028 m/s at 171° and 0.015 m/s at 180° for mid-water and seabed, respectively. These low current flow rates indicate little dispersive capacity for fish cage waste. Any discharge from the cages at this site is likely to be dispersed initially to the south and any particulate wastes would be deposited to the seabed close to the cages. Infrastructure on site consists of a traditional 5 x 50 m circumference pen grid for fish culture (Figure 4). This scaled down approach is approximately a quarter of the size of a commercial Irish salmon farm as the site operates for research

purposes only. To the south-east of the pen grid, there is an attached Low Trophic Grid (LTG) consisting of a submerged rectangular grid with capacity for ca. 780 m suspended longlines (Figure 5).

Figure 4. Image of Lehanagh Pool research site looking north-east to south-west in direction of prevailing current. ©Marine Institute

Figure 5. Engineer drawings of low trophic grid, moored as an annex to the salmon pen grid.

The Lehanagh Pool mooring grid is made up of the following components:

- 14 x 500 kg Assembled HSS mooring anchors.
- Rope Danline 57 mm 3 strand.
- 10 tonnes of 38 mm open link chain.
- 12 x Warm galvanised mooring plates with 16 holes of minimum 37 mm diameter.
- 6 x 1100 L grid buoys.
- 6 x 1600 L grid buoys.

A 14-day simulation of the Marine Institute Bertraghboy model with particle tracking for upper, mid and bottom simulations was completed to assess nutrient dispersion sourced from fish waste at the pens. Based on the results of this model, the new infrastructure is orientated south-east of the pen grid (indicated in red in Figure 6). The location was chosen downstream of the modelled nutrient plume to maximize the potential for the uptake of nutrients from the fed species at the site. This new LTG is moored as an annex to the grid structure (Figure 7).

Figure 6. Heat map of particle tracking modelled of nutrients released from salmon pen indicated by the red dot. Black line indicates site boundary. ©Marine Institute

Figure 7. Surface image of low trophic grid on site fully stocked with all species. Colour floats used to indicate stocks. ©Marine Institute

The bespoke low trophic grid was designed to complement the current monoculture facilities to ‘add’ productivity (Figure 8). The grid model aims to maximize the use of available space and materials, while also minimizing environmental impacts. The design allows the operator to adjust orientation, depths, and spacing of culture lines using multiple attachment points to facilitate a range of low trophic species. As the grid structure is submerged there is less visual impact, suspended culture limits interaction with the benthic environment and by utilising the main grid for fish culture, the co-location maximises uptake of nutrients released from fish rearing activities and reduces the number of anchor points by 50 % when compared to traditional longlines.

Figure 8. Lehanagh Pool low trophic grid, showing the location of low trophic species adjacent to the salmon pens.

By creating this new structure there is increased habitat and biodiversity at the site for low trophic species, and a reduction in the environmental nutrient load, delivering a healthier production system.

This novel set-up maximises the use of space at this site and adds to the development of circularity within the production system. Careful consideration is given to the materials used to balance longevity of components, with appropriate end of life disposal such as recycling and renewables. The design also allows multiple uses for single pieces of infrastructure, future proofing, and planning for continued sustainable research at the site.

Table 1 contains the materials and components used to construct the LTG.

Table 1. Equipment and materials used to create and install the LTG.

Equipment description	Material
Damper buoys 1100 L	Rotomolded PE and filled with Polystyrene foam. Density Foam 25kg/m ³ i.e. 580 L =21.25 kg of Foam and remaining material is LLPE (51.755 kg)
Grid rings - round steel ring - masterlink 6" x 4"	Heavy duty galvanised steel
Ultraflex Aqua Plus 40 mm mooring rope with hard eyes 50 m	Polypropylene
Ultraflex polysteel 14 mm heel rope	Polysteel
OCEANFLEX unleaded 24 mm polypropylene riser rope	Polypropylene
Galvanised steel anchors	Heavy duty galvanised steel
Galvanised steel chain 19 mm 3 m	Heavy duty galvanised steel
Heavy duty galvanised steel chain 5 m	Heavy duty galvanised steel
Bow shackle 6.5 T	Heavy duty galvanised steel
Bow shackle 9.5 T	Heavy duty galvanised steel
32 mm grid rope with dyneema soft splice locks	Dyneema

A full catalogue of species trialled at the IMTA lab Ireland can be seen in the Table 2 below.

Table 2. Species cultivated at the Irish IMTA lab.

<u>Common name</u>	<u>Latin name</u>	<u>Role in IMTA</u>
Lumpfish	<i>Cyclopterus lumpus</i>	Fed species
Ballan wrasse	<i>Labrus bergylta</i>	Fed species
Atlantic salmon	<i>Salmo salar</i>	Fed species
Atlantic wakame	<i>Alaria esculenta</i>	Extractive Species
Sugar kelp	<i>Saccharina latissima</i>	Extractive Species
Black or Variegated scallop/Cluisín	<i>Mimachlamys varia</i>	Extractive Species
European lobster	<i>Homarus gammarus</i>	Novel species
King scallop	<i>Pecten maximus</i>	Extractive Species
Native oyster/European flat oyster	<i>Ostrea edulis</i>	Extractive Species
Purple sea urchin	<i>Paracentrotus lividus</i>	Extractive Species
Sea cucumber	<i>Holothuria forskali</i>	Extractive Species

The species at the IMTA lab Ireland (Figure 8) are categorized as: fed, extractive, benthic scavengers or novel species.

1. Fed species: Feed is inputted to the system for Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*), lumpfish (*Cyclopterus lumpus*) and Ballan wrasse (*Labrus bergylta*) when stocked. As a result, the fish release waste/nutrients into the surrounding water.
2. Extractive species: There are two types of extractive species. The filter feeders; Great scallop (*Pecten maximus*), Cluisín (*Mimchlamys varia*) and Native oyster (*Ostrea edulis*), filter out particulate waste (uneaten food and faeces) from the water as food, reusing the waste released from the fed species. Dissolved 'waste' is extracted by seaweeds *Saccharina latissima* and *Alaria esculenta* by absorbing dissolved minerals and carbon, reusing the 'waste' from the fish and shellfish entering the environment.
3. Benthic scavengers: Purple sea cucumber (*Holothuria forskali*) removes particulates from the upper surface of benthic sediments on the seafloor. This particulate 'waste' contains uneaten food and particulate waste from the fish.
4. Novel species: European lobster (*Homarus gammarus*) utilise fish waste prevalent in the water column but also graze on the community structure established in the holding baskets.

However, they are not grown to market size; instead, they are released as juveniles as a stock enhancement initiative linking coastal industries. Purple sea urchins (*Paracentrotus lividus*) are fed with the seaweeds grown in the IMTA process. They are incorporated into the food web by manual feeding, enhancing the circularity of this IMTA production system.

4.1.2 IMTA Lab Scotland – Open Water IMTA System

The IMTA lab Scotland, Port-a-Bhuiltein (PaB), is an open coastal aquaculture site located 200 m off the mainland shore in the Firth of Lorn-Loch Linnhe estuarine system, West coast of Scotland (56° 29.176 N, 5° 28.315 W) (Figure 9). The site has been operated as an experimental seaweed cultivation site by the Scottish Association for Marine Science (SAMS) since 2014.

The site is moderately exposed to south-westerly winds with the main current flow in NE-SW direction at average surface current speeds of 11 cm/s (range = 0.1 – 500 cm/s at 1.5 m depth). The tide is semi-diurnal (range = 0.15 – 4.51 m) with sea surface temperatures ranging from 6 – 15 °C and salinity from 24 – 34 psu (typically > 32 psu). The mean water depth is 30 m with muddy sand and mixed sediments beneath the farm.

Figure 9. Location of the IMTA lab Scotland Port-a-Bhuiltein (PaB), a low-trophic coastal aquaculture research site on the West coast of Scotland.

The site is licensed by Marine Scotland for the cultivation of seaweeds and, following an amendment in 2020, also for the integration of selected shellfish species for experimental non-commercial use. Thus, PaB has transitioned from a seaweed monoculture site to a low-trophic aquaculture (LTA) site for the integration of extractive species.

The total lease area is 30 hectares and currently consists of one tensioned 100 x 100 m (= 1 hectare) grid submerged 3 m below the surface. The grid can support up to 48 seaweed growing lines of 50 m length, spaced 4 m apart, which are suspended horizontally and parallel to the main current flow at a depth of 1.5 m below the water surface. The system is modifiable and offers capacity for additional deployment infrastructure for seaweed and shellfish production as well as environmental monitoring equipment (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Left: Site layout showing the positioning of seaweed and shellfish cultivation infrastructure and stationary monitoring equipment (selected). Right: Aerial view of the seaweed harvest operation (June 2020).

Cultivation species and production scales have focussed on European kelp species (*Alaria esculenta* and *Saccharina latissima*) and European flat oysters (*Ostrea edulis*). Under ASTRAL, additional LTA species are trialled (Table 3) including brown (*Laminaria digitata* and *Sacchoriza polyschides*) and red (*Palmaria palmata*) seaweeds as well as king scallops (*Pecten maximus*).

Table 3. Species cultivated at the IMTA lab Scotland.

<u>Common name</u>	<u>Latin name</u>	<u>Role in IMTA</u>
Atlantic wakame	<i>Alaria esculenta</i>	Inorganic extractive species
Sugar kelp	<i>Saccharina latissima</i>	Inorganic extractive species
King scallop	<i>Pecten maximus</i>	Organic extractive species
European flat oyster	<i>Ostrea edulis</i>	Organic extractive species
Oarweed	<i>Laminaria digitata</i>	Inorganic extractive species
Furbelows	<i>Sacchoriza polyschides</i>	Inorganic extractive species

The species at the IMTA lab Scotland are categorized as inorganic and organic extractive species:

1. **Inorganic extractive species:** Seaweeds absorb dissolved inorganic nutrients from the surrounding water in their tissue. During photosynthesis, carbon dioxide dissolved in seawater

is taken up by the seaweed and oxygen released as a co-product. Added oxygen and algal debris are beneficial to shellfish and other marine organism in proximity.

2. **Organic extractive species:** Shellfish are effective filter-feeders taking up dissolved and particulate organic matter suspended in the water column. They release nutrients back into the water column as part of their metabolic activity, thus adding to the nutrient pool available to other marine organisms, including seaweeds.

4.2 Species Production

4.2.1 Farm Management

All farm practices are subject to current legislation and license requirements. The management of an open water production site includes a number of checks that are carried out routinely and regularly on a site-wide basis; these observations are common to all the production species.

4.2.1.1 *Routine Operations (daily/weekly)*

- Surface visual inspection of the production site to include licensed structures, nets, moorings, navigation buoys and feeders.
- Recording of environmental parameters on site.
- Repair and maintenance of operational structures.
- Mortality removal as required.

4.2.1.2 *Recordkeeping*

- Stocking and feeding records to be updated as required.
- Record of environmental parameters.
- Record of health checks/visits carried out.
- Record the storage and use of chemicals and medicines.
- Site visitors log updated as required.

4.2.2 Seaweed (Kelp: *Alaria esculenta*, *Saccharina latissima*, *Laminaria digitata*, *Sacchoriza polyschides*)

In Europe, brown seaweeds or kelps can be found along most Atlantic coastlines, often forming dense forests. Kelp species are harvested from the wild and cultivated commercially, being a highly productive and fast-growing crop used mainly for food and feed products as well as for the extraction of high-value compounds (e.g. alginate and mannitol). On a global scale, Europe's contribution to seaweed production in general remains small compared to Asia, but interest and available market opportunities have expanded in recent years and will require the continued upscaling of local production to meet growing demands.

Seaweeds are on-grown from hatchery cultures which are seeded onto grow-out structures before being deployed at sea and left to grow until harvest; commonly 7 – 9 months from deployment to harvest, depending on the species and intended application (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Life cycle of seaweed species. ©Marine Institute & SAMS

4.2.2.1 Seed Supply & Transport

The seeding material, young seaweed sporophytes, can be sourced from designated hatcheries (e.g. commercial seaweed nursery operated by SAMS Enterprise). These offer various choices of cultured species, seeding substrate and equipment, and seeding strategy employed (direct and indirect seeding; the latter still dominating). Detailed rearing protocols have been established for the culture of main kelp species⁴ including biosecurity control to prevent contamination across species and with the environment. In general, best practice designates the culturing of endemic and locally sourced seaweeds and grow-out locally to its source.

Figure 12. Left: *Saccharina latissima* sporophyte culture; Middle: seeded twine reels in nursery tank cultivation ©SAMS. Right: Kuralon twine under x10 magnification with well-developed *Saccharina latissima* sporophytes ©Marine Institute.

For indirect seeding, better known as twine-seeding, up-scaled seaweed cultures are seeded onto reels holding fine polyester twine of 1 mm in diameter. The reels are then transferred into nursery cultivation tanks supplied with filtered UV-treated seawater and held under controlled temperature, light and nutrient conditions until juvenile sporophytes have developed sufficiently and evenly across the twine surface (Figure 12, nursery stage 4 – 6 weeks depending on species) and are ready to be transported for grow-out at sea.

⁴ <https://bim.ie/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/BIM-Technical-Report.pdf>

Figure 13. Transport of seeded twine. © Marine Institute.

Reels should be kept moist and dark during transport using soaked clothes and a lidded box (polystyrene or cool box) (Figure 13). For longer journeys, ice packs and a temperature logger should be supplied to monitor temperature conditions during transport. Upon deployment, reels should be handled very carefully, avoiding touching of the twine and thus abrasion of the culture material.

4.2.2.2 Kelp Deployment

Site selection for cultivation is crucial. Physicochemical conditions must be suitable for the sessile kelp to grow and survive, being of adequate temperature, salinity, water movement (to deliver nutrients and carbon dioxide for growth) and light availability (low seawater turbidity to allow for light penetration and photosynthesis)⁵ (Table 4).

Table 4. Optimum environmental parameter range for kelp growth.

|
Wave Height |
|--|---|--|---|--|--|
| 8 – 15 °C | 24 – 35 psu
>30 psu ideal | 10 mmol TON* m ⁻³ | 50 – 250
μmol photons m ⁻² s ⁻¹ | Moderate – High > 1 m s ⁻¹
Low < 1 m s ⁻¹ (<i>S. latissima</i>) | 0 – 4 m |

*TON = total oxidised nitrogen (nitrate NO₃ and nitrite NO₂)

For European kelp species, deployment generally occurs in the early Autumn. At this time of year, seawater temperatures and light levels are still sufficient for the young sporophytes to further develop their holdfasts and properly attach to the growing line before the onset of more severe weather conditions in later Autumn to early Winter. Surface seawater temperatures of ≤ 14 °C and salinities of

⁵ Kerrison, P.D., Stanley, M.S., Edwards, M.D., Black, K.D., Hughes, A.D., 2015. The cultivation of European kelp for bioenergy: Site and species selection. *Biomass and Bioenergy* 80, 229–242.

≥ 30 psu are recommended for kelp deployment. Optimal deployment conditions may vary slightly across kelp species; *Alaria esculenta* being more sensitive to sudden changes in salinity than *Saccharina latissimi*, but more resilient in strong current and wave regimes. Ideal deployment conditions include overcast weather, little to no wind, and no rain. Strong winds and direct sunlight can cause desiccation and physiological stress, affecting the condition of the fragile sporophytes and thus chances for growth and survival. Wind direction and tidal state should also be considered to allow for the work boat to drift downwind from the starting point (Figure 14). In general, deployment should be performed carefully and efficiently, keeping environmental exposure and manual handling to a minimum.

Twine deployment can be performed manually or semi-automated (Figure 14) depending on the scale of the operation and equipment available, by applying the following procedure: (1) one end of the growing line (three-strand twisted high-tenacity polysteel 'seasteel') is passed through the reel; (2) the twine is untied from the reel on one end, unwound a few turns, and spliced into the growing line for secure attachment; (3) this start of the growing line is tied to a mooring point preferably at the far side (upwind) of the farm; (4) slowly and controlled, the boat is allowed to drift downwind whereby the seeded twine is wrapping helically around the growing line; (5) once completed, the end of the growing line is secured to the opposing mooring point. All personnel involved (skipper, person(s) handling line and twine) should communicate throughout the entire operation to ensure that tensions are maintained for the twine to deploy into the lay of the growing line and to avoid sagging.

Figure 14. Deployment at IMTA labs Ireland (top panel; ©Marine Institute) and Scotland (bottom panel; ©SAMS). Ireland: Manual deployment onto 28 mm growing line; Scotland: semi-automated onto 12 mm growing line using a seeding tool manufactured in-house.

Another important consideration is the spacing between growing lines. Environmental and practical considerations include allowing for an average swell in both directions to avoid line interaction and unobstructed navigation of the work boat. In addition, lines should be far enough apart to avoid shading effects whereby kelp fronds overlay one another which limits light exposure and photosynthetic capacity. Both open water IMTA labs commonly use line spacings of 4 – 5 m with narrower intervals and potential effects on seaweed yield and composition being trialled in ASTRAL.

Once seeded, growing lines should be tensioned and buoyed up according to the desired cultivation depth; for IMTA labs Ireland and Scotland this is approximately 1.5 m below the water surface. Buoyancy can be maintained using 8" trawl floats or polyform pencil buoys (e.g. LD20 buoys); the latter being preferred in medium-high current environments as less tensile force is acting on the growing

line. A neutral colour should be used where possible to minimise the visual impact of the longlines as per licence conditions. Floats should be deployed approximately every 15 m along the growing line, using 6 mm Nylon cord cut to the required length (Figure 15). Since growing lines are positively buoyant and kelp biomass is not yet established, a 0.5 – 1 kg weight should be attached to each float connection to maintain the growing line at the required depth.

Figure 15. Deployment at IMTA lab Scotland, Oct 2023. Attachment of weighted polyform buoys along the seeded growing line. ©SAMS

4.2.2.3 Maintenance

As the seaweed grows, lines will rapidly become heavier and be pulled down. Therefore, line position, tension and depth should be checked regularly and adjusted as required by adding floats and tensioning up lines. Site visits for maintenance and monitoring (see below) should be performed at a minimum monthly as well as following storm events or extended periods of heavy weather. Some common issues encountered, and their cause may include:

- Line drag or crossing → heavy weather; recognized by altered float location and buoyancy.
- Line abrasion → floats/weights can wrap around the line and strip off on-growing biomass. Float connector ropes may be embedded in slim PVC tubes to increase rigidity.
- Detached floats and/or mooring buoys → heavy weather; require immediate attention.
- Biofouling → competition with crop for space, light and nutrients. Infrastructure should be cleared from heavy fouling and kelp harvested prior to onset of heavy fouling from May.

4.2.2.4 Stock Monitoring

Kelp grows comparatively slowly during the colder months but quickly enters their exponential growth phase in late February until late April, when biomass yields can double every 12 – 17 days, depending on the species (Figure 16). After this, growth slows down and yields stagnate or even decrease as older parts of the frond are shed and biofouling pressure (especially grazing organisms) increases (Figure 16).

Figure 16. *S. latissima* after 3, 5 and 7 months (from left to right) at sea. ©SAMS & Marine Institute.

Depending on the site's operational scale and interests, stock growth and performance should be assessed regularly (monthly – bimonthly sampling) in addition to routine environmental monitoring for key physicochemical parameters such as temperature, salinity, and nutrient levels.

Kelp is sampled destructively for monitoring biomass yield, morphology/performance and biochemical composition (% moisture, ash, protein, carbohydrates, lipids). At sampling, the work boat is aligned and secured alongside a growing line. Using a tape measure a line area of 0.5 m is marked (Figure 17, left) and all on-growing biomass removed and placed carefully in a labelled net or bag and stored cool and dark for transport. This procedure can be repeated twice more along the line for a representative cover. Back on land and for each collected sample, the biomass is removed from the bag onto a clean work surface. For recording biomass yield, holdfasts are cut off and discarded and excess seawater removed from the biomass (= fronds with stipes) using a spinner; small salad spinner or industrial range depending on sample volume i.e. time of year. The spun-down biomass is weighed, and the value multiplied by a factor of two for biomass yields in kg per meter growing line [multiplication factor depends on the line area samples; e.g. factor of 5 if only 20 cm line are sampled]. If frond morphology is to be assessed, select 2 – 3 longest individuals from the sample before spinning, lay them out flat

and measure frond length and maximum width; after which these join the remaining biomass for spinning and recording of yield (Figure 17, middle and right).

Figure 17. Seaweed sampling and processing at IMTA lab Scotland. Left: *Alaria esculenta* sampling Jan 2021; middle & right: *Laminaria digitata* frond length and biomass yield in May 2021. ©SAMS.

Subsamples can be stored in labelled zip-lock bags and frozen at -20 °C for analysis of biochemical composition or high value compounds of interest (e.g. mannitol or alginate). For analysis of trace metals such as cadmium, arsenic, iodine to name a few, required for seaweed entering the food and feed market, samples should be rinsed in deionised water before storage to remove excess salts.

4.2.2.5 Kelp Harvest

Kelp harvest is performed in Spring with the exact timing largely determined by the crops' quantity, quality and intended end use. Harvesting early in the season will yield lower quantities but ensures pristine fronds of high quality without biofouling damage; requirement when used for food and feed applications. A later harvest will yield much more biomass but of lower quality as damaged by fouling organisms and UV stress; for use as e.g. fertiliser rather than sold as a food/feed product. Heavy fouling can also impact processing activities such as fermentation or anaerobic digestion used for e.g. biofuel production as calcareous fouling organisms may offset the pH buffering capacity.

Harvest types include (i) partial harvest: fronds are cut below the meristem in late Winter and left to re-grow for a second harvest in late Spring, and (ii) full harvest: the whole individual is removed either by pulling or scraping it off the line or by cutting the stipe. Harvest can be performed manually, semi-automated or fully automated using harvesting machines, and can take multiple days depending on the type of harvest and scale of the site's operation. IMTA labs Ireland and Scotland perform manual and semi-automated harvests, respectively (Figure 18).

Figure 18. Manual and semi-automated seaweed harvest. Left: *A. esculenta* line pulled into work boat and crop cut off by hand, ©Marine Institute. Right: *S. latissima* line is pulled mechanically (winch) through a shackle and the crop collected in tonne bags beneath. ©SAMS.

Ideal weather conditions are similar to deployment: little to no wind, no rain, no direct sun exposure (overcast ideal), and preferably low or outgoing tide to reduce pressure on the growing lines. Multiple work boats may be in operation to assist with the removal of lines, the storage in tonne bags or large fish bins, and efficient transport to land for further processing and/or hand-over to customers e.g. wholesaler, organic farmers, etc. Where possible, use a mechanical motor or winch to lift the growing lines out of the water – a 50 m line with e.g. 10 kg m⁻¹ biomass yield can easily weigh a tonne when wet.

The harvest season finishes with transporting all growing lines and ancillary material (floats, weights) to shore, where they are left to air-dry before power-washing and removing any remaining twine. Once clean and dry, growing lines are coiled and stored dry and dark for use in the following cultivation cycle (re-used for 2 – 3 cultivation cycles before reaching the end of life is). Any damaged ropes and floats should be cleaned and disposed of correctly in line with EU Directive⁶ on the reduction of the impact of certain plastic products on the environment, also referred to as the Single Use Plastics Directive, and its relevance to aquaculture gear suppliers.

4.2.2.6 Sources of information

A complete guide to seaweed hatchery and at sea grow-out design can be found at this link:

<https://bim.ie/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/BIM-Technical-Report.pdf>

A complete guide to the cultivation of *Laminaria digitata* can be found at the link below:

⁶ Directive (EU) 2019/904 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 June 2019 on the reduction of the impact of certain plastic products on the environment.

<https://bim.ie/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/BIM,Aquaculture,Explained,Issue,26,-,Cultivating,Laminaria,digitata.pdf>

4.2.3 Oyster (*Ostrea edulis*)

The European flat oyster or native oyster (*Ostrea edulis*) is a bivalve mollusc species found along the western European coast and the Mediterranean Basin, as well as North America, where it had been intentionally introduced. Commercial production peaked in the 1960s and has since declined dramatically due to the impact of diseases (mainly Bonamiosis) and the consequential shift to the cultivation of more resilient Pacific cupped oysters (*Crassostrea gigas* or *Magallana gigas*). Production remained low throughout the decades with Spain, France, the United Kingdom and Ireland being the main producers. As availability decreased wholesale prices have increased, with *O. edulis* occupying an economic niche and being considered a luxury seafood item in many regions.

4.2.3.1 Seed Supply & Deployment

Seed oysters can be derived naturally (i.e. natural spat fall) using settlement substrates deployed at site. Where natural spat fall is sparse or unreliable, seed oysters should be sourced from disease free, reliable seed producers i.e. certified oyster hatchery. All regulatory requirements should be met in the procurement and transport of seed to the production site. The duration of the production cycle to harvest can vary depending on the size of oyster required by the markets (Figure 19).

Figure 19. Production cycle of *Ostrea edulis*. ©Marine Institute

In general, there is a wide variety of grow-out methods employed to cultivate oysters: on-bottom, off-bottom, longline and raft-based culture; often relying on natural spat settlement. This manual will focus on the method employed by both ASTRAL open water IMTA labs – floating oyster cultivation on longlines. The floating culture uses longlines deployed horizontally in the water column and serving as carrier ropes for shellfish baskets deployed in regular intervals. These baskets are equipped with their own flotation to maintain the system at the sea surface (Figure 20). The built-in flotation further makes the use of added buoyancy in the form of trawl floats or buoys redundant.

Figure 20. AP6 oyster baskets (3 holding baskets of 70 x 16 x 25 cm L x H x W [V = 72 l], mesh size: 2 cm²) deployed at both IMTA labs. ©SAMS

The oysters should be deployed within the nutrient stream from the fed species in adequate distance (approx. 2 m) (depending on the site’s location and hydrography). With the oysters being held in baskets, the operator should ensure suitable environmental conditions are met for growth and survival (Table 5).

Table 5. Optimal environmental conditions for *O. edulis* growth and survival⁷.

Temperature	Salinity	Dissolved Oxygen	Current speed	Chlorophyll
8 – 18 °C	> 30 psu	> 8 mg L ⁻¹	Low-moderate < 0.5 m s ⁻¹	> 8 µg L ⁻¹

O. edulis is sensitive to overcrowding and thus care should be taken to not overstock the holding baskets. For IMTA labs Ireland and Scotland, baskets were stocked with 100 – 200 juvenile oysters (≤ 3 cm shell length) spread out over the individual compartments, respectively. Basket lids were additionally secured with cable ties either side to avoid stock loss during severe weather.

4.2.3.2 Maintenance

Oyster stock and infrastructure should be inspected regularly as well as immediately following storms and extended periods of harsh weather. Maintenance should be performed monthly and include the following actions:

⁷ Laing, I., Walker, P., Areal, F., 2005. A feasibility study of native oyster (*Ostrea edulis*) stock regeneration in the United Kingdom. CARD Project FC1016. Native Oyster Stock Regeneration - A Review of Biological, Technical and Economic Feasibility.

1. **Basket Damage:** each basket and ancillary material such as connector ropes should be checked for their structural integrity and wear and tear. Damaged components should be replaced immediately to avoid stock damage or loss (Figure 21).
2. **Fouling Control:** the smooth basket surface attracts settlement of both soft- (filamentous algae; Figure 21) and hard-fouling organisms (barnacles, tubeworms, mussel spat, etc.). These compete with the oyster stock for food and space, obstruct the water flow through the mesh if not controlled, and can alter oyster growth and survival. Depending on the extent and type of fouling, baskets may be cleaned at site using wire brushes, or exchanged with clean baskets. Removed baskets are let to air-dry for the hard-fouling to dry out before being power-washed and re-used.
3. **Grading:** as the oysters grow more space is taken up in each holding basket. Oysters will grow at varying speeds, and small and large individuals should be separated to increase space and allow for even growth. For each basket, oysters are removed and roughly graded by size into batches of equal volume before being returned into the holding baskets. Grading should be carried out annually in the winter months to avoid unnecessary stress to the animals.
4. **Mortality:** during the grading process, any mortalities should be recorded and removed. These need to be disposed of following instructions given in the site's biosecurity management plan (BMP).

Figure 21. Oyster basket damage and biofouling cover. ©SAMS

4.2.3.3 Stock Monitoring

The oysters should be monitored continuously for shell growth and meat yield. Assessments should be carried out every 2 – 3 months or more or less frequently depending on the site's scale and objectives. For this, 3 – 6 individuals are randomly chosen from each basket and transported cool and in the dark to shore. Either still on site or back on land, shell growth can be estimated by measuring shell height

(SH) from the umbo to the highest part of the shell (Figure 22). For meat yield (MY), the oysters are opened and all soft-tissue separated from the shell pair. The soft-tissue is blotted dry, transferred into pre-weighed weighing boats and the total soft-tissue weight recorded. Shell pairs are also blotted dry and their weight recorded. Meat yield is an indicator for the 'fatness' of the oyster and is the percentage ratio of tissue to total weight (here tissue + shell weight to exclude trapped seawater; see Eq. below). The value can be corrected for size by dividing it by shell height (% MY/cm).

$$\text{Meat Yield (MY, \%)} = \frac{\text{tissue wet weight (g)}}{(\text{tissue wet weight (g)} + \text{shell wet weight(g)})} \times 100 \%$$

Figure 22. *O. edulis* monitoring. Left: Shell height ©Marine Institute. Right: Tissue and shell weighing for assessment of meat yield ©SAMS.

Figure 23. *O. edulis* at IMTA labs Ireland (left) and Scotland (right). ©Marine Institute & SAMS

Shellfish Safety

In 2006 the European Parliament prescribed legislation pertaining to the quality standards for shellfish waters and requires that Member States designate the waters to which it will apply and set limit values corresponding to certain parameters⁸.

Foodborne illness caused by microorganisms or naturally occurring toxins is the primary food safety risk associated with seafood⁹. Seafood producers have a role to provide and carry out the necessary handling, processing, and inspection procedures to give consumers the safest seafood possible. Government agencies, retailers, processors, restaurants, and scientists also have commitments to ensure that seafood is safe for consumption. All requirements under appropriate legislation and best practice guidelines should be followed when harvesting and placing shellfish on the market (Figure 23).

Legislation and guidelines for aquaculture and aquaculture products in the EU, are categorised as follows¹⁰:

- Requirements for production areas.
- Fish health rules.
- Labelling of aquaculture products.
- Hygiene rules.
- Microbiological criteria.
- Establishments subject to approval.
- Health Standards for Live Bivalve Molluscs.

⁸ [Directive 2006/113/EC](#) (OJ L 376, p14, 27.12.2006)

⁹ Hicks DT. Seafood Safety and Quality: The Consumer's Role. *Foods*. 2016 Oct 28;5(4):71. doi: 10.3390/foods5040071. PMID: 28231165; PMCID: PMC5302431.

¹⁰ <https://www.fsai.ie/enforcement-and-legislation/legislation/food-legislation/aquaculture-and-aquaculture-products>

4.2.4 Salmon (*Salmo salar*)

Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*) is a well-established aquaculture species (Figure 24). Current worldwide production of farmed Atlantic salmon exceeds 3 million tonnes¹¹. There is a wealth of information available about the rearing procedures of this species, please see references below.

Figure 24. *Salmo salar* Atlantic salmon. ©Marine Institute

4.2.4.1 Production

The production of Atlantic salmon at Lehanagh Pool is in keeping with current open water commercial practices (Figure 25).

Figure 25. Production of Atlantic salmon at Lehanagh is carried out in line with commercial practices.

¹¹ <https://www.fao.org/3/cc0461en/cc0461en.pdf>

In an IMTA cultivation situation the rearing of salmon does not differ from that of monoculture methods or production cycle (Figure 26).

Figure 26. Life cycle of farmed Atlantic salmon. ©Marine Institute

The optimal environmental ranges for successful growth of Atlantic salmon are listed in Table 6.

Table 6. Optimal environmental ranges for growth of Atlantic salmon at sea.¹²

 Temperature	 Salinity	 Dissolved Oxygen	 pH	 Nutrients
12 - 15 °C	28 - 33psu	80 – 100 %Sat	6.0 - 8.5	Ammonia < 0.02 mg/L Nitrite < 0.1 mg/L

¹² Marine Institute (2017) The farmed salmonid health handbook. Chapter III The Environment. IFA Aquaculture.

4.2.4.2 Sources of information

The Farmed Salmonid Handbook - [The Farmed Salmonid Handbook | Fish Health Unit](#)

Salmon Farming Industry Handbook 2023 <https://mowi.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/2023-Salmon-Farming-Industry-Handbook-2023.pdf>

4.2.5 Cleaner fish – Lumpfish (*Cyclopterus lumpus*) & Ballan wrasse (*Labrus bergylta*)

Cleaner fish such as Lumpfish *Cyclopterus lumpus* (Figure 27) and Ballan wrasse *Labrus bergylta* (Figure 29) act as biological pest control on salmon farms as they help to combat sea lice infestations on the salmon stocks. The sea lice form part of the cleaner fish diet and have been successfully used on salmon production sites.

4.2.5.1 Lumpfish

Figure 27. *Cyclopterus lumpus* Lumpfish. ©Marine Institute

4.2.5.1.1 Sourcing of stock

Juveniles should be sourced from an appropriate supplier. Disease status of all incoming stock should be established by the producer in order to adhere to the relevant legislation and fish health guidelines. The cleaner fish should be monitored continuously for welfare

4.2.5.1.2 Assessing the effect the cleaner fish has on salmon livestock

Sea lice levels should be monitored frequently, with thorough sea lice counts in all pens.

4.2.5.1.3 Transport

At approximately 6-8 months old lumpfish reach a size of 25-40 g which is the appropriate size to be transferred to the marine salmon pens (Figure 27). Prior to movement the fish should be graded according to size. Fish are to be starved before transport for a minimum of 1-2 days. The transportation tank should be of suitable size for the number of fish being transported. It is important that this tank is dark inside. The tanks are fitted with oxygen supply and aerators. The fish are hand netted into the

transportation tank. Oxygen is checked and adjusted (if necessary) every hour. It should be approximately 100 – 120 % saturation.

Lumpfish are transferred to the salmon pens by hand netting from the transport tanks. Special care must be taken not to forcefully remove lumpfish from a surface if they are stuck to it as this can cause severe damage, tanks are slowly tipped into the pen and held upside down. The lumpfish slowly drop from the surface they are attached to and fall into the pen. It is important that hides are deployed in the sea pen for the welfare of the lumpfish. A large temperature differential between the transport water and the ambient sea temperature should be avoided, efforts should be made to gradually adjust the temperature in the transportation tank to match that of the ambient temperature at sea.

4.2.5.1.4 Special conditions

The characteristic behaviour of lumpfish under stress (crowding or attaching itself to a surface by a suction disc on its belly) makes it difficult to distinguish unstressed fish from stressed fish, as the lumpfish do not display a typical flight response as is the case with salmon. Therefore, stress must be measured physiologically to expose the response. A lumpfish with 'calm' behaviour can be stressed.

Stress and any physical strain (loss of mucus and injuries) in connection with handling (loading and unloading from transport tank) are registered as significant stress factors for lumpfish, particularly with repeated handling in a short space of time, often in connection with secondary transport which requires transshipping of fish. Development of quick, gentler loading and unloading methods should take high priority.

4.2.5.1.5 Habitat enhancement

Lumpfish live the first part of their lives in a kelp forest and are to a large degree pelagic the first years before they leave the strand zone and migrate further out in the sea to search for grazing grounds. Lumpfish have no swim bladders, and in the kelp forest use their in-built suction cups to attach themselves on smooth surfaces, often in a hide in shade, probably for rest and as a natural protection mechanism. Plan for hides (Figure 28) to function as cleaning stations; a place where the salmon go to be relieved of sea lice. Good hides and adequate surface area are vital in reducing stress and ensuring good fish welfare. Kelp forests are serviceable for both large and small lumpfish, but the larger lumpfish (60 g+) often prefer settling on rigid surfaces. One way of creating shade is to have horizontal kelp ribbons the length of the curtained area on the water surface. Tail nipping and aggression may prove a challenge having sufficient hides will reduce this problem. Several types of hide are available on the market, such as ring hides, curtain hides and rigid hides.

Figure 28. Hides for lumpfish in-situ. ©Marine Institute

4.2.5.1.6 Placement of the hides

Hides must be positioned before lumpfish are released into the pen. Consider the direction of the sea current and feeding point for the salmon in relation to the placement of hides and monitor with the camera where lumpfish are most comfortable in order to make appropriate adjustments where necessary. Avoid placing hides alongside the net wall, by salmon feeding stations, resting close to the bottom of the net in a cone-shaped net or in the middle of the net.

4.2.5.1.7 Feed

Execute feeding in the refuge area and from separate feeding automats. Several types of automats are available on the market. Feed manufacturers (Biomar, Skretting, and EWOS) offer small pellets specially designed for lumpfish feed.

Recommended feeding rates:

After release into pen: 2 – 3 % daily feeding of biomass, daily up to 6 weeks.

Summer: 2 – 3 % daily feeding of biomass, 5 days per week.

Winter (<6 °C): 1.5 % daily feeding of biomass, 5 days per week.

Feeding in even doses during the day.

Some producers feed the lumpfish for 2 – 4 hours and finish the meal before the salmon have finished their feeding. It takes time to gather the lumpfish together, and the aim is to have the lumpfish ready in the refuges to go to work cleaning the salmon after the salmon have finished eating their meal.

If feeding is skipped for a day or two, the lumpfish will seek alternative food such as fouling growth, salmon feed or nip at sores and fins. It is recommended to hand feed a small amount during the workday to make observations/assessments of the lumpfish. Healthy fish will quickly react and capture the feed, and other fish that are sick or stressed will be slower to react.

Weight and length should be measured routinely to determine rate of growth and to calculate the right amount of feed to be given to the fish.

4.2.5.1.8 Welfare

Health inspections of lumpfish should be carried out routinely. The fish health service should be contacted if there is an increase in mortalities. Screening prior to transport and release is vital to reducing the potential for cleaner fish becoming a vector for disease. Common symptoms of disease or diminished health are emaciation, sores and wear-and-tear injuries to skin, cataracts or suction cup deformities. Erosion and tail rot are also common, in some instances also seen together with *Tenacibaculum sp.* and *Vibrio sp.* infections.

4.2.5.2 *Ballan Wrasse*

Figure 29. *Labrus bergylta* Ballan wrasse

4.2.5.2.1 Sourcing of stock

Juveniles should be sourced from an appropriate supplier. Disease status of all incoming stock should be established by the producer in order to adhere to the relevant legislation and fish health guidelines. The cleaner fish should be monitored continuously for welfare

4.2.5.2.2 Assessing the effect the cleaner fish has on salmon livestock

Sea lice levels should be monitored frequently, with thorough sea lice counts in all pens.

4.2.5.2.3 Transportation

At approximately 2 – 3 years old Ballan wrasse reach a size of 50 g which is the appropriate size to be transferred to the marine the salmon pens. Prior to movement the fish should be graded according to size. Fish are to be starved before transportation for a minimum of 1-2 days. The fish are hand netted onto the transportation tank of appropriate size. It is important that this tank is dark inside. The tanks are fitted with oxygen supply and aerators. Oxygen is checked and adjusted (if necessary) every hour. It should be approximately 100 – 120 % saturation. Salinity of the water should never be lower than 25 psu, pH shall not be less than 7.0, and should preferably lie between 7.0 – 7.3. Upon arrival at the sea pens the tanks are slowly tipped into the pen. It is important that hides are deployed in the sea pen for the welfare of the Ballan wrasse. A large temperature differential between the transport water and the ambient sea temperature should be avoided, efforts should be made to gradually adjust the temperature in the transportation tank to match that of the ambient temperature at sea. Use a dip net for all handling. A kelp hide should be in place in the transport tank and in pen at the delivery.

4.2.5.2.4 Maintenance

Cleaning of nets, hides and other equipment is essential for successful wrasse biological control of sea lice. Plan and carry out routine cleaning of all equipment that is subject to fouling. If cleaning is sub-standard, the wrasse will prefer to eat the fouling instead of sea lice. Nets and hides should be washed at intervals of maximum 7 – 14 days in the worst periods for fouling. With use of wrasse over winter the hides must be cleaned before temperatures go below 6 – 8 °C. The hides should be cleaned regularly. Use of a mort collector can pose a problem regarding fish welfare. Wrasse often congregate in the dip net, and risk bursting when the net is pulled up to the surface. This is due (in contrast to the salmon) to the fact that wrasse have a closed swim bladder that equalises pressure through a gas gland, which takes a long time. With rapid upward movement from the depths, this escapes via the anus of the fish, and if the pressure is too great the fish bursts. Measures to prevent swim bladder damage include:

- Check via the camera if it is necessary to use a dead fish dip net.
- Avoid taking out dead fish the day after a large delivery of cleaner fish.
- Pull up the dip net slowly; maximum 20 cm/s.
- Jerk the rope to scare off the fish.
- Place hides so they reach all the way down to the dead fish dip net to lead wrasse away from the net. Use the camera to monitor movement.

- Ensure there are escape openings in the dead fish dip net.
- Pull the dead fish dip net up slowly all the way to the surface, so wrasse are able to swim out. If a stop occurs underway there is a risk that dead fish will float out from the net.
- Openings under the dead fish dip net may lead to escapes. These must be checked and repaired.

4.2.5.2.5 Feed

Wrasse must be fed consistently; it is recommended that feeding stations are provided in the hides. With wrasse feeds from Skretting (Clean Soft 12) and Biomar (Symbio Maintenance 12) (Figure 30), it is recommended that fish are fed from a submerged feeding unit. The feed is laid in a soft bait bag or a flexible nylon stocking. The bag must be made of soft material to prevent injury to fish noses. The bait bag/stocking is then placed in the hide, preferably at several feeding points at various depths. Bait bags/stockings should generally be refilled three times a week, less frequently when temperatures are below 6 – 7 °C. The need for refills can vary depending on appetite and number of bait bags in the cage.

Figure 30. Wrasse feeding block. ©Aquafeed.com

4.2.5.2.6 Welfare

Daily observations of the wrasse should take place. Routine health inspections should be carried out using recognised welfare indicators e.g. operculum damage, snout damage, upper jaw deformities, lower jaw deformities, emaciation, vertebral deformities, scale loss and fin damage¹³. The salmon is a

¹³ Kottmann, J. S., Berge, G. M., Kousoulaki, K., Østbye, T.-K. K., Ytteborg, E., Gjerde, B., & Lein, I. (2023). Welfare and performance of ballan wrasse (*Labrus bergylta*) reared at two different temperatures after a preparatory feeding trial with enhanced dietary eicosapentaenoic acid. *Journal of Fish Biology*, 103(5), 906–923. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jfb.15482>

natural predator of wrasse. To prevent this, the salmon should be fed before releasing the wrasse; the wrasse are particularly vulnerable immediately after release into the pen(s). Also having sufficient hides can prevent the problem.

Handling of wrasse before/during delousing:

Pay attention to the wrasse during delousing. The primary concern should be to keep the wrasse away from delousing equipment that is engaged in crowding, pumping and handling of fish. Some producers move hides to the opposite end of the pen from where the delousing equipment is located. Most of the wrasse stay in the hides, away from cast nets and weighted dragnets have passed under the hides. Nonetheless, watch out for wrasse that have become entangled in the cast net and end up in the well boat/delousing equipment. These must be retrieved and handled as gently as possible. Check equipment that is adapted to take care of cleaner fish during delousing operations functions correctly.

4.2.5.2.7 [Habitat enhancement/Hides](#)

Plan for hides to function as cleaning stations; a place where the salmon go to be relieved of lice. Several types of hides are available on the market, including ring hides, garland hides, curtain hides and Cunningham lanterns.

Curtain hides are often used as these offer the salmon plenty of opportunity to come into contact with the cleaner fish. The hide curtains are hung out in parallel lines where experience shows that a distance of 2 – 4 m between each curtain and 1 – 1.5 m between each kelp ribbon provides a spacious area where the salmon and cleaner fish can meet. The distance between the kelp ribbons must be evaluated in terms of how many metres of hide one requires and how many hides are to be utilised in the cage. Producers have reported conditions were improved by increasing the number of kelp ribbons and reducing the distance between the kelp ribbons as one alternative to adding more hides.

Hides must be in position in the pen before the wrasse are released there. Ideally, hides should be placed so that the tops of the hides are 2-3 m below the surface in order to avoid the worst fouling zone. They are also located vertically in the water column to allow the wrasse the freedom to find a suitable depth according to seasonal changes in the seawater environment. Hides should be weighted at the bottom for stability. Place hides at some distance from the net wall to avoid having to move these before net cleaning. Plan for use of delivery hides with releases of wrasse, as these can act as a link to hides placed further out in the pen. Use of delivery pens can play a crucial role in acclimatising the wrasse to a new environment. This may contribute to reducing stress and facilitate wrasse establishing themselves in hides.

If faced with the challenge of cleaner fish seeking cover in the mort collector, you can steer them away from there by attaching a kelp 'climbing rope' (leader hide) from the mort collector up to the hides. This is done by attaching a weight on the middle of a long kelp ribbon and sinking this down to the mort collector.

4.2.6 Lobster (*Homarus gammarus*)

The commercial culture of *Homarus gammarus* is difficult due to the slow growth rate, captive breeding challenges, low survival rates and cannibalistic tendencies (Figure 31). This crustacean species is included in the ASTRAL IMTA open water species production assessments not as a possible commercial aquaculture species but as a restocking candidate to potentially enhance the indigenous stock of lobsters for the local fishery. Juvenile lobsters are reared in a hatchery and grown to stage V or VI, and then transferred to sea for on-growing for a number of years before being released into the wild at suitable locations (Figure 32).

Figure 31. *Homarus gammarus* European lobster. ©Marine Institute

Figure 32. Production cycle of European lobster to adult. ©Marine Institute

The optimal environmental growth parameters are described in Table 7.

Table 7. Optimal environmental parameter range for lobster growth¹⁴.

 Depth 5 – 15 m			
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A guide to hatchery rearing of lobster can be found at the link

¹⁴ Daniels, C. L., Wills, B., Ruiz-Perez, M., Miles, E., Wilson, R. W., & Boothroyd, D. (2015). Development of sea-based container culture for rearing European lobster (*Homarus gammarus*) around South West England. *Aquaculture*, 448, 186-195.

https://bim.ie/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/bimno_23_An_Illustrated_Hatchery_Guide_to_Producing_European_Clawed_lobster_Homarus_Gammarus_2009.pdf

This guide gives the procedures involved in the cultivation from hatchery to grow-out phase.

<https://www.nina.no/archive/nina/PppBasePdf/rapport%5C2006%5C211.pdf>

4.2.6.1 Transport

All individuals should be transported separately to avoid any cannibalistic behaviour by each other (Figure 33). Transport in water from hatchery, monitor temperature of this transportation water and keep cool if necessary. Monitor oxygen levels, add aeration if required.

Figure 33. Transportation of juvenile lobster from hatchery to the sea site. ©Marine Institute

4.2.6.2 Deployment

Lobster are stocked into individual containers as part of a Sea Based Container Culture (SBCC) structure¹⁵ (Figure 34). SBCC units are suspended from longlines in the low trophic grid structure located in the nutrient plume from the fed species. Lobsters reared in SBCC structure are exposed to

¹⁵ Peter Halswell, Carly L. Daniels, Lars Johanning. Framework for evaluating external and internal parameters associated with Sea Based Container Culture (SBCC): Towards understanding rearing success in European lobsters (*Homarus gammarus*). *Aquacultural Engineering*. 83. 2018. 109-119. doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaeng.2018.09.005.

variable ambient biological, chemical and physical parameters which is likely to enhance behavioural enrichment for each lobster¹⁶.

Figure 34. Deployment of SBCC lobster containers. ©Marine Institute

SBCC units are deployed at 3 culture depths, 5, 10 and 15 m. All containment structures should be identifiable (Figure 35), cable ties are used as a numbering system on each structure (Figure 36).

¹⁶ C.L. Daniels, B. Wills, M. Ruiz-Perez, E. Miles, R.W. Wilson, D. Boothroyd. Development of sea based container culture for rearing European lobster (*Homarus gammarus*) around South West England. *Aquaculture*. 448, 2015, 186-19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2015.05.026>

Figure 35. SBCC structures in-situ. ©Marine Institute

Figure 36. Recommended numbering system for individual lobster.

4.2.6.3 Feed

This species grazes independently on the fouling of its containment structure and also gathers nutrient from the wastes for the fed species on site¹⁷. The SBCC allows enough detritus for sustenance as would be available in a rock crevice for a wild lobster.

¹⁷ Baltadakis A, Casserly J, Falconer L, Sprague M, Telfer TC (2020) European lobsters utilise Atlantic salmon wastes in coastal integrated multi-trophic aquaculture systems. *Aquacult Environ Interact* 12:485-494.

4.2.6.4 Maintenance

All unnecessary fouling (Figure 37) should be routinely removed for the containment structures to prevent over burdening of the structure and the longline. Calcareous matter can be left as this is a good source of nutrients for the lobsters.

Figure 37. Fouling of individual lobster container. ©Marine Institute

4.2.6.5 Growth Monitoring

Minimise time spent out of water by leaving remaining SBCC units submerged.

Random sampling of individuals should be carried out quarterly to measure carapace length.

Loxster growth is determined using gridded images and software to measure length.

- Remove the oyster stack from the water.
- Estimate and record the level of fouling (% cover biofouling of the lobster cages). Repeat for each stack. Include any additional observations such as variation in fouling intensity around the stack, alien species, species types.
- Starting from the top, note the number of cable ties to indicate stack number (1 cable tie = stack 1, 2 cable ties = stack 2, etc.).
- Beginning at the top layer, locate the triangular basket marked by a cable tie. This is the first in numerical order for this layer. Work clockwise around the container (Figure 36).
- Mark lobster as present/absent/deceased.
- Remove specimen and place in petri dish over gridded paper.
- Photograph specimen at 90°. Check photograph to ensure clarity, that an accurate carapace length can be obtained. (Figure 38).
- Place specimen back into compartment, replace lid and seal using elastic bands.

- Repeat with the remaining specimens.
- Reassemble stack.
- Reassemble stack. Return it to the water at specified depth.

Figure 38. Measurement of carapace length. ©Marine Institute

4.2.6.6 *Predator Control*

The SBCC structure provides protection from most predators. Regular observation and maintenance are required to ensure that all stacks are intact.

4.2.7 Scallops - King scallop (*Pecten maximus*) and Black scallop or Variegated/Cluisín (*Mimachlamys varia*)

4.2.7.1 King Scallop (*Pecten maximus*)

Scallop production includes both wild capture and commercial cultivation, with aquaculture contributing over four times more to the global total production (2.19 metric tonnes in 2017)¹⁸. Scallop culture is a relatively recent activity compared to other commercial bivalve molluscs (mussels, oysters, clams), originating in Japan in the 1930s in response to overexploited natural scallop beds, and since the 1980s being employed in many other parts of the world. European production is dominated by king scallop *Pecten maximus* (Figure 39) and queen scallop *Aequipecten opercularis*, which often require > 3 years to reach commercial size (≥ 9 cm shell height for *P. maximus*) in European temperate waters. The production cycle will vary with the desired harvest weight (Figure 40).

Figure 39. *Pecten maximus*, King scallop, at IMTA labs Ireland and Scotland. ©Marine Institute &SAMS

¹⁸ FAO (2019) Global Aquaculture Production 1950-2017. Fishery Statistical Collection, Fisheries and Aquaculture Department.

Figure 40. Production cycle of *P. maximus*. ©Marine Institute

4.2.7.1.1 Seed Transport and Deployment

Scallop spat is to be transported in tanks with sufficient aeration and seawater at ambient temperature to avoid stress responses. Seawater salinity should be ≥ 25 psu and pH ≥ 7.0 , preferably between 7.0 – 7.3. As for oysters (see section 4.2.3), scallops are contained in grow-out structures thus environmental conditions at the cultivation site must be within the tolerance range of the species for growth and survival (Table 8).

Table 8. Optimal environmental conditions for *P. maximus* growth and survival¹⁹.

 Chlorophyll				
10 – 17 °C	30 – 35 psu	≤ 100 %Sat	Low-moderate 0.2 - 1 m s ⁻¹	$> 1 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$

¹⁹ Laing, I., 2002. Scallop Cultivation in the UK: a guide to site selection. Lovestoft.

Various grow-out structures exist for suspension culture with the most used being lantern nets but also stacked trays such as nestier trays, also known as SBCC (Figure 41). Suspension lines from which the grow-out structures are deployed should be submerged > 2 m below the water surface to minimise effects of wave action as well as sudden changes in salinity or temperature. Multiple suspension lines may be deployed in parallel whilst allowing for enough space between lines to avoid tangling of the suspension gear during severe weather events (often > 10 m spacing depending on the site's location i.e. exposure and configuration). The suspension line should be supported with floats deployed between rather than above grow-out structures to avoid abrupt tensile forces acting on the structures during storm events. The number of grow-out structures deployed from each suspension line can vary depending on the structure used, the vertical extension of structures (i.e. a 10-layered structure will be longer thus requires more clearance than a 5-layer structure), and the overall site's needs and capabilities. Grow-out structures should be deployed using an anchor or cloth hitch knot, ideally spliced through the suspension line, to avoid sliding.

Whilst lantern nets are negatively buoyant and as such do not require weighing down, adding a light weight can assist in keeping the grow-out structure in a vertical position and reducing lateral movement in moderate to high current environments. Stocking densities vary depending on the scallop size (being reduced with increasing age i.e. size) and grow-out structure and thus surface area in use. IMTA lab Ireland employed lantern nets with 10 – 15 individuals per layer whilst IMTA lab Scotland employed nestier trays with only 4 individuals per layer; worth noting that this was driven by the lower number of juveniles to start with which were also of larger size than the spat deployed at IMTA lab Ireland.

Figure 41. Scallops grow-out in lantern nets (left & middle) ©Marine Institute and nestier trays (right) ©SAMS.

4.2.7.1.2 Stock & Infrastructure Maintenance

Both the grow-out infrastructure and containing scallop stock should be visited regularly in line with the license requirements outlined by the respective authority such as the fish health inspectorate (FHI). At open-water IMTA labs this was performed every 3 months and included the following actions:

- Cleaning or exchange of grow-out structures to remove on-growing biofouling limiting the water flow and thus food supply for the scallops. Removed structures should be transported to land, left to air-dry and power-washed to remove biofouling before being re-used.
- Stock count and removal and recording of any mortalities. Mortality disposal should follow guidelines set out in the site's BMP and excessive mortalities/stock loss reported to the Fish Health Manager.
- Scallop shells may be cleaned from on-growing hard- and soft-fouling (more relevant during the final grow-out to market size).

4.2.7.1.3 Growth Monitoring

Scallops should be monitored for growth throughout their cultivation period. This can be performed alongside the maintenance visits at 3-monthly intervals. Assessments may include the monitoring of shell growth (shell height and width; and total weight). Monitoring should be performed efficiently to minimise the time scallops spent out of the water.

Depending on the stocks' size a representative sample size should be selected. Shell height and width can be measured using calipers or a scaled length board. When following the growth in weight over

time it is advised to clean off any shell fouling before recording total wet weight (Figure 42).

Figure 42. *P. maximus* morphological traits and recording at IMTA lab Ireland. ©Marine Institute

4.2.7.2 Cluisín (*Mimchalmys varia*)

This small scallop (Figure 43) is an indigenous species in the location of Lehanagh Pool. This species creates a natural spatfall and the collection of this spat has led to pilot investigations into the feasibility of this species as a potential aquaculture species.

Figure 43. Cluisín *Mimchalmys varia*. ©Marine Institute

4.2.7.2.1 Deployment

1. Cluisín are stocked in Shellfish baskets (Figure 44).

Figure 44. Deployment of Cluisín baskets. ©Marine Institute

2. Stocking density should not exceed 30 adult Cluisín per quarter.
3. Shellfish basket nets should be suspending from a submerged longline only and not a buoyant structure. If on a longline, do not position floats/buoys directly above them.

4. Shellfish basket nets are positively buoyant and require a weight.
5. Cluisín should be submerged at a depth below 2m to avoid the influence of freshwater in Lehanagh Pool.
6. Shellfish basket units will be suspended from longlines in the low trophic grid structure onsite.
7. Shellfish basket nets should be stacked with a maximum of 8 layers. A stop knot should be used to secure the structure. Fully close the layers using 4mm elastic and potting hooks.
8. All baskets should be checked for holes or damage to prevent stock loss.
9. Cluisín should be checked fortnightly for excess morbidity, stock health and signs of predator damage or after a severe weather event.
10. Any empty shells should be removed to prevent damage to livestock by laceration.
11. A full check of stock occurs every 3 months. This includes:
 - a. Shellfish basket nets should be cleaned by scrubbing the outside with a hard bristled brush. If fouling is excessive, transfer stock to a new clean basket.
 - b. Count total live individuals.
 - c. Cluisín can be cleaned, sponges, for example, should be removed.
 - d. A sub sample of minimum 20 is used for morphology and biomass, then frozen for contingent work. Cluisín growth is monitored by weight and by measuring the length and height of the shell using a length board following growth monitoring procedure.
 - e. Shellfish basket nets should be power-washed, cleaned, and stored indoors out of sunlight, if removed.

4.2.7.2.2 Feed

N/A as they are filter feeders.

4.2.7.2.3 Growth Monitoring

- Biomass accumulation – Quarterly measure and weigh n = 20 individuals.
- Record of morbidity must be kept.
- Minimise time spent out of water.
- Avoid full sampling on very cold days.

Equipment: Length board, data sheet, 250 g scales, camera, digital callipers, PE cord, clean shellfish basket.

Sampling frequency: Quarterly

- Record environmental conditions at location.
- Using a boat hook – remove the shellfish basket from the water.

- Estimate the level of fouling (estimate the % cover biofouling of the holding structure. Record on data sheet. Repeat for each structure. Include any additional observations such as variation in fouling intensity around the shellfish basket, alien species, species types.).
- Check for signs of predator damage.
- Clean outside of basket using a hard bristled brush. If fouling is excessive, remove all Cluisín and transfer to a new shellfish basket.
- Whilst transferring stock, count total live individuals.
- Remove and empty shells.
- Where fouling is excessive, Cluisín can be cleaned, sponges, for example, should be removed.
- Take a random sample of a minimum of 20 Cluisín used sampled for morphology and biomass, then frozen for contingent work (see sub sample method below).
- Close Shellfish basket by threading the entrance using PE cord or twine.
- Re- suspended from longlines using an anchor knot to avoid it sliding.
- Remove fouled baskets to be power-washed, cleaned, and stored.
- Report excessive mortalities/stock loss to the Fish Health Manager.
 - place Cluisín on length board and record shell length and height (see Figure 42).
 - remove shell fouling (sponges, squirts, spat) and record Cluisín weight.
 - remove sample from site and freeze to -20 °C for contingency/further analysis.

4.2.8 Sea Urchin (*Paracentrotus lividus*)

The gonads or roe of sea urchins are a highly sought after delicacy mainly in Asian markets²⁰. The spiny sea urchin (*Paracentrotus lividus*) (Figure 45) is a candidate to help meet some of this market demand. The production cycle (Figure 46) may vary according to marketable sizes required.

Figure 45. *Paracentrotus lividus* purple sea urchin. ©Marine Institute

The production cycle (Figure 46) may vary according to marketable sizes required.

²⁰ Stefánsson G., Krisinsson H., Ziemer N., Hannon C., James P. (2017). "Markets for sea urchins: a review of global supply and markets," in *Matís report* (Reykjavik: Skýrsluágríp Matís ohf - Icelandic Food and Biotech R&D).

Figure 46. Production cycle of farmed sea urchin²¹. ©Marine Institute

The optimal environmental growth parameters are described in Table 9.

Table 9. Optimum environmental parameter range for purple sea urchin growth²².

 pH				
7 - 22 °C	> 30 psu	> 90 %Sat	0.2 – 1 ms-1 Low-moderate	Very tolerant >7

4.2.8.1 Transport

Sea urchins are to be transported in the hatchery water, temperature is to be monitored and not allowed to fluctuate during transport and kept cool if necessary. Oxygen levels are measured throughout transportation and aeration added, if necessary, saturation should not fall below 90 %.

4.2.8.2 Deployment

1. Sea urchin are stocked in hexyl baskets (Figure 47).

Figure 47. Urchin baskets. ©Marine Institute

2. Stocking density should not exceed 30 adult sea urchin per basket.

²¹ Formery et al (2022). Developmental atlas of the indirect-developing sea urchin *Paracentrotus lividus*: From fertilization to juvenile stages. *Frontiers in Cell and Developmental Biology* 10.

²² Lawrence, J. M. (Ed.) (2013). *Sea urchins: biology and ecology*. Academic press.

3. Shellfish basket nets should be suspending from a submerged longline only and not a buoyant structure. If positioned on a longline, do not attach floats/buoys directly above them.
4. Shellfish basket nets are positively buoyant and require a weight.
5. Sea urchin should be submerged at a depth below 2 m to avoid the influence of freshwater.
6. Shellfish basket units will be suspended from longlines in the low trophic grid structure onsite.
7. Shellfish baskets are secured closed using 4 mm elastic and potting hooks.
8. All baskets should be checked for holes or damage to prevent stock loss.
9. Sea urchin should be checked fortnightly for excess morbidity, stock health and signs of predator damage or after a severe weather event.
10. Any sea urchin displaying poor health or spinal loss where the teste is now visible should be considered moribund and removed.
11. A full check of stock occurs every 3 months. This includes:
 - a. Shellfish basket should be cleaned by scrubbing the outside with a hard bristled brush. If fouling is excessive, transfer stock to a new clean basket.
 - b. Count total live individuals.
 - c. A sub sample (minimum 20) is taken for morphology and biomass, then frozen for contingent work.
 - d. Shellfish basket nets should be power-washed, cleaned, and stored if removed.

4.2.8.3 Feed

Seaweed should be added to the shellfish baskets.

1. Sea urchin should be fed every two weeks.
2. Where diet is not specified, urchin should be given a mix of kelps. The quantity should be enough to fill the basket. This helps to cushion the urchin during periods of intense wave action.

4.2.8.4 Growth Monitoring

- Biomass accumulation – Quarterly measure and weigh $n = 20$ individuals.
- Record of morbidity must be kept.
- Minimise time spent out of water.
- Avoid full sampling on very cold days.

Equipment: Length board, data sheet, 250 g scales, camera, digital callipers, PE cord, clean shellfish basket.

Sampling frequency: Quarterly

1. Secure boat alongside cage/ longline.
2. Record environmental conditions at location.
3. Using a boat hook – remove the shellfish basket from the water.
4. Estimate the level of fouling (Estimate the % cover biofouling of the holding structure. Record on data sheet. Repeat for each structure. Include any additional observations such as variation in fouling intensity around the shellfish basket, alien species, species types.).
5. Check for signs of predator damage.
6. Clean outside of basket using a hard bristled brush. If fouling is excessive, remove all sea urchin and transfer to a new shellfish basket.
7. Whilst transferring stock, count total live individuals.
8. Remove and empty shells.
9. Close shellfish basket by pressing down hard on the door clip until it clicks.
10. Further secure using 4mm elastic cord and potting hooks.
11. Re-suspended from longlines using an anchor knot to avoid it sliding.
12. Remove fouled baskets to be power-washed, cleaned, and stored.
13. Report excessive mortalities/stock loss to the Fish Health Manager.

4.2.8.5 Harvest

Sea urchin harvest usually occurs after 3 – 4 years of growth when the teste diameter is approximately 4 – 5 cm (Lawrence 2013)²³.

²³ Lawrence, J. M. (Ed.) (2013). Sea urchins: biology and ecology. Academic press.

4.2.9 Sea Cucumber (*Holothuria forskali*)

Sea cucumbers are a potential aquaculture species grown under aquaculture farms, not only as food, but as waste removers. The optimal environmental growth parameters are described in Table 10.

Table 10. Optimum environmental parameter range for sea cucumber growth.

 Depth				
5 - 15 °C	28 - 34 psu	Low mud	0.2 - 0.5 ms ⁻¹ Low-moderate	< 30 m

4.2.9.1 Transportation

Sea cucumber should be transported in seawater with aeration if necessary. The temperature of the transporting water should be equivalent to the temperature of the receiving body of water. The optimal environmental growth parameters are described in Table 10.

4.2.9.2 Deployment

Sea cucumber cages are made from plastic coated galvanised mesh (10 mm x 10 mm), with a surface area of 1 m² and dimensions of 200L x 100W x 50H cm (Figure 48). The cages are anchored to the seabed on weights. Cages are stocked with either a high (six animals per cage) or low density (three animals per cage).

Figure 48. sea cucumber *H. forskali* feeding on sediment from inside holding cages. ©Marine Institute & INEVAL.

4.2.9.3 Growth Monitoring

Regular growth monitoring should be carried out to assess the growth rate of the sea cucumbers. Individual animals should be gently dried of excess surface water and weighed routinely (Figure 49).

Figure 49. Weighing of sea cucumber. ©Marine Institute & INEVAL

4.2.9.4 Feed

Sea cucumbers form an active part in IMTA as they aid circularity by recycling nutrients, breaking down particulate and other organic matter from the benthos underneath the production site²⁴.

²⁴ Neofitou, N., Lolas, A., Ballios, I., Skordas, K., Tziantziou, L., Vafidis, D., 2019. Contribution of sea cucumber *Holothuria tubulosa* on organic load reduction from fish farming operation. *Aquaculture* 501, 97-103.

4.3 Environmental Assessments

4.3.1 Water Quality Monitoring

It is essential to monitor water quality parameters to ensure stock health. Regulatory requirements for the monitoring and reporting of water quality need to be continuously addressed. Optimal growth of all open-water IMTA species require good quality, well oxygenated water for optimal growth. Environmental parameters of interest and relevance and their recording frequency all depend on the operations scale, set-up, location, and species produced. For example, at sites holding fed species such as finfish, oxygen levels, water temperature, salinity and Secchi disk measurements should be recorded daily.

For many environmental parameters the site operator has the choice between manual water sampling and readily available off-the-shelf sensors for autonomous real-time monitoring. Most physical parameters such as water temperature and salinity are easily followed deploying such sensors and are low in cost and maintenance. However, manual water sampling and subsequent analyses by an accredited laboratory are often preferred for nutrient levels. At the IMTA labs water samples are taken monthly and analysed for seawater nutrients important for seaweed growth (nitrate, nitrite, ammonia and orthophosphate) and phytoplankton content (estimated from chlorophyll-a measurements) in conjunction with analysis for amount of particulate organic carbon (POC) and nitrogen (PON) for shellfish species. In relation to the latter, phytoplankton sampling using a 10 m lund tube is conducted and samples are analysed in the laboratory for nuisance or harmful phytoplankton species. The biomass rating of the predominant species is also monitored on a bi-monthly basis.

4.4 Health

Aquaculture establishments such as finfish farms and shellfish farms must operate in line with current aquatic animal health regulations. The EU Animal Health Regulation 2016/429 applies from April 21st, 2021. The Regulation lays down rules for the prevention and control of animal diseases which are transmissible to animals or humans.

EU Animal Health Regulations are as follows:

- Regulation (EU) 2016/429 on transmissible animal diseases and amending and repealing certain acts in the area of animal health ('Animal Health Law').

- Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2018/1882 on the application of certain disease prevention and control rules to categories of listed diseases and establishing a list of species and groups of species posing a considerable risk for the spread of those listed diseases.
- Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2019/2124 supplementing Regulation (EU) 2017/625 of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards rules for official controls of consignments of animals and goods in transit, transshipment and onward transportation through the European Union.
- Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2020/692 supplementing Regulation (EU) 2016/429 of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards rules for entry into the European Union, and the movement and handling after entry of consignments of certain animals, germinal products and products of animal origin.
- Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2020/990 supplementing Regulation (EU) 2016/429 of the European Parliament and of the Council, as regards animal health and certification requirements for movements within the European Union of aquatic animals and products of animal origin from aquatic animals.
- Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2020/687 supplementing Regulation (EU) 2016/429 of the European Parliament and the Council, as regards rules for the prevention and control of certain listed diseases.
- Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2020/689 supplementing Regulation (EU) 2016/429 of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards rules for surveillance, eradication programmes, and disease-free status for certain listed and emerging diseases.
- Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2020/690 laying down rules for the application of Regulation (EU) 2016/429 of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards the listed diseases subject to Union surveillance programmes, the geographical scope of such programmes and the listed diseases for which the disease-free status of compartments may be established.
- Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2020/691 supplementing Regulation (EU) 2016/429 of the European Parliament and of Council as regards rules for aquaculture establishments and transporters of aquatic animals.
- Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2021/260 approving national measures designed to limit the impact of certain diseases of aquatic animals in accordance with Article 226(3) of

Regulation (EU) 2016/429 of the European Parliament and of the Council and repealing Commission Decision 2010/221/EU.

- Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2021/620 laying down rules for the application of Regulation (EU) 2016/429 of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards the approval of the disease-free and non-vaccination status of certain Member States or zones or compartments thereof as regards certain listed diseases and the approval of eradication programmes for those listed diseases.

Marine finfish, shellfish and seaweed aquaculture in Scotland are licensable activities requiring a Marine Licence regulated by Marine Scotland – Licencing Operation Team (MS-LOT) on behalf of the Scottish Ministers. Additional entities such as NatureScot, the Scottish Environmental Protection Agency (SEPA), the Maritime and Coastguard Agency, the Northern Lighthouse Board and the Public (managed through public consultation events) are all statutory consultees on Marine Licence applications.

As well as a licence to operate farm equipment, a Seabed Lease to develop or operate in an area within 12 nautical miles of the UK coastline must be secured from the Crown Estate (Crown Estate Scotland). Since 2007, all new finfish and shellfish farms in development require planning permission under the 'Town and Country Planning Act', issued by the relevant Planning Authority. In order to operate a fin-/shellfish business, authorisation for an Aquaculture Production Business (APB) and Aquatic Animal Holding Site Details must be submitted to and granted by Marine Scotland - Fish Health Inspectorate (MS – FHI).

All aquaculture products entering the human food chain must comply with Food Standards Scotland (FSS) to ensure food safety such as monitoring for toxins, pesticides, and environmental and process contaminants.

4.4.1 Movement of Stock

Fish health status must be considered when evaluating the risks of moving stock, both shellfish and finfish. Fish health regulations should be followed; these require that all transporters of aquaculture animals take specific measures to protect the health of fish during transportation, thereby preventing the spread of aquatic diseases. All equipment used to transport must be cleaned and disinfected after each use which safeguards the health of the species being moved. The process minimizes the risk factors that may predispose the species to disease, minimizes transfer of disease-causing agents and reduces the risk of accidental loss of stock during transport activities.

Species are checked to ensure that they are clinically healthy prior to movement. All legislative requirements should be met and permissions sought, as required. A risk assessment should be conducted and the transfer of animals onto the site should only take place if the risk is acceptable.

All aquaculture production operations are legally bound to operate within their licence conditions regarding health of stock and biosecurity.

4.2.2 Feed and Nutrition

Only feeds that have been formulated specifically for the life-stage of the species being farmed are fed. Feeds and feeding rates are regularly reviewed. Organic feed should be used for organic IMTA production.

4.4.3 Handling of Stock

Handling is carried out with suitable equipment by competent personnel and during suitable environmental conditions. Environmental conditions are monitored as required (weather, water temperature, current, dissolved oxygen levels) to ensure optimum conditions. After a handling episode stocks are monitored for signs of poor handling such as injury. If such signs are noted, affected groups are carefully observed for increased rates of mortality or illness in the subsequent weeks. All handling events must be recorded in a daily log.

4.4.4 Stocking Density

Optimum stocking density varies according to the life stage, species, culture conditions and the environment. Stocking densities are monitored in relation to health, behaviour and water quality to ensure that welfare is not compromised.

4.4.5 Predator Control

Management methods are designed to reduce the attraction of predators to culture facilities and prevent predators attacking stocks thus avoiding stress that could result in an increased risk of disease.

4.4.6 Mortality Management

Mortality removal is carried out regularly to prevent re-infection occurring which could potentially compromise the health of the stocks and to prevent a deterioration of water quality. The frequency of mortality removal will be determined by the site manager based on time of year and numbers/type of mortalities. Records of mortalities must be maintained for each unit.

If a sudden mass mortality is experienced on a farm the following procedure should be implemented:

- The affected farm/site should be immediately designated as being in isolation.
- Where mortalities are due to infectious disease a zone of those units/sites deemed most at risk of exposure to infection should be established.
- Water quality should be analysed and all equipment regulating water supply and quality should be assessed for damage.
- If a notifiable disease is suspected the farm veterinarian and relevant authorities should be contacted immediately.
- Other farms within the 'at risk' zone should be notified of the diagnosis or suspected diagnosis.
- Non-essential deliveries or visits to the farm should be halted. Essential supplies should be delivered to the affected site last.
- Movement of equipment, vessels, personnel etc. between sites should be immediately halted. Movement of staff between the affected farm and other farms should be halted.
- Thorough disinfection of all equipment, clothing, vessels, etc. should take place if there is to be movement between affected and non-affected sites. Footbaths and, if practical, hand wash stations should be maintained and used by all personnel before accessing and leaving the site. These footbaths should be located at all access/exit points. They should be clearly visible and marked.
- Mortality removal frequency should be increased depending on the rate of mortality.
- Moribund stock should be slaughtered in a humane and rapid manner.
- Mortalities should be transported in sealed containers to avoid spread via spillage or predators.
- Stock should be transported to an approved disposal facility and rendered appropriately.
- Should slaughter of affected stock be necessary then strict disinfection and cleaning regimes should be adhered to. All blood-water should be contained and treated.
- An intensive sampling routine should be instated by the farm veterinarian and relevant authorities.

- All surfaces that come in contact with infected material should be thoroughly cleaned and disinfected.
- Unaffected stock should be placed under quarantine and monitored for a time period after the event, to be decided by the veterinarian, manager and relevant authorities.
- After the date of removal of the last affected stock from the facility an appropriate time period should elapse while the site remains fallow and before re-stocking takes place. Other sites in the 'at risk' zone should also follow this procedure.
- When restocked, the site should be monitored for a number of months for signs of disease.
- Additional measures may also be required in the event of an outbreak of a disease as listed in relevant legislative guidelines.
- Daily mortality records should be kept in relation to all affected pens. Records of all visitors to the site as well as details of all biosecurity measures put in place must be maintained and presented for inspection, on request.

4.4.7 Record Keeping

Maintaining good records is essential to maintaining consistently healthy stock. Facilities must have an information management system that provides timely information to identify and assess changes in stock health to allow for sound stock health management decisions. For individual groups of species in the facility, operators must keep up-to-date health records including disease history and patterns of mortality, and records of movements of stock within the facility.

With regard to fish stocks, accurate records of feeding rates (% body weight fed per day) and feed conversion rates ($FCR = \text{feed consumed} / \text{biomass increase}$) for each unit are particularly useful in tracking the health and performance of the stocks. Comparisons of feed rates and FCR between different batches of fish give vital clues as to the health of the population and the adequacy of the diet. Regular recording of growth performance and mortalities for each unit is essential for tracking trends over time and between sites. A weekly summary stock sheet should be produced. The stock sheet provides essential information for those who feed the fish but also for the site manager. This information is also required by the fish health professionals, regulators, insurers and for quality and customer audits.

The farm health records include:

- Inventory records – site name, pen/tank identification, stock type, number and biomass, pen/tank dimensions.
- Stock movement records – origin, strain, number, transporter details, mode of transport, dates.

- Mortality records including likely cause of death per farm unit.
- Daily stock observations.
- Veterinary reports.
- Vaccination records.
- Medicated feed records.
- Therapeutant treatment records.
- Records of mitigative actions (other than therapeutants) taken to prevent or reduce disease, e.g. taking stock off feed due to a plankton bloom.
- Results of disease surveillance, completed by a veterinary practitioner and by the competent authority.
- Disposal and movement of mortalities.
- Records of water quality parameters tested.
- Feeding records – feed type, feeding levels, FCR (Feed Conversion Rate).
- Biosecurity records – a Biosecurity Plan for the site as well as cleaning rotas, chemical logs, visitor records.
- Training records.

4.4.8 Adverse Events

Severe weather conditions have the potential to generate ‘emergency situations’. Staff are aware of the potential difficulties which may arise and are committed to mitigating any such problems. Structures and stock are assessed as soon as is safely possible after a storm event.

Structures are monitored routinely for fouling and are cleaned or replaced when required.

Extreme sea water temperatures should prompt the cessation of feeding and regular monitoring of dissolved oxygen.

Phytoplankton and jellyfish blooms can have a harmful effect on aquaculture. This occurrence should prompt the cessation of feeding and regular monitoring of dissolved oxygen.

4.5 Biosecurity

Best practice biosecurity should be carried out in all areas of the production facility. The implementation of an effective biosecurity management plan (BMP) is essential in reducing the risk of disease introduction to an aquaculture site. The BMP's objective is to ensure that the cultured stocks are reared in optimal husbandry conditions.

Biosecurity control measures should include:

- Introducing stock from disease-free providers and ensuring ongoing fish health and welfare.
- External barriers: Preventing the entry of pathogens.
- Internal barriers: Minimizing disease spread within a site.

External Barriers:

- Dips for footwear are positioned at the entry to the site.
- Ensure that transporters have carried out appropriate cleaning and disinfection procedures on vehicles, prior to entering a site.
- Visitor logbooks should be used with declarations of contact with other aquaculture stocks or wild stocks in the previous 72 hours.
- Ensure that there are adequate signs throughout the site informing visitors about biosecurity procedures.
- All regulatory requirements are followed.
- Predator control should be adequate for each site.

Internal Barriers:

- Each area should have its own equipment and where this is not possible; equipment should be thoroughly cleaned and disinfected when moved to another section.
- Clothing and equipment should be cleaned and disinfected before and after use.
- All disinfectants should be used according to the manufacturers' instructions.
- Logs of disinfectant replenishment should be kept.

Biosecurity audits should be carried out regularly to ensure that biosecurity standards are being continually met.

Table 11 sets out the requirements that should be followed to ensure the highest standard of onsite biosecurity.

Table 11. General Biosecurity Measures

Measures	Frequency of action
A Visitors Book is maintained to record details of all visitors to the site and to ensure relevant cleaning and disinfection procedures have been followed.	As required in the event of external visitors.
Footbaths/disinfection points are available at all entrances to the site and records of disinfectant used and frequency of maintenance are maintained.	Checked daily.
Separate hand nets are retained for each unit within the site for removing mortalities. These nets are disinfected after use and nets are changed before they become heavily fouled.	As required.
Every effort is made not to share equipment with other sites. If this is necessary, the item of equipment is thoroughly cleaned and disinfected before it leaves the site and prior to it being returned to the site. It is disinfected again, on arrival back at the site.	As required, dependent on frequency of use
Specific Personal Protective Equipment (PPE), including wet gear are to be used for the site. Visitors must clean and disinfect their gear before they visit the site.	As required in the event of external visitors.
Containment structures are cleaned and disinfected at the end of a production cycle.	As required.
Workboats are regularly cleaned and disinfected.	Weekly
Where harvest bins and lids are brought onto the site, they are fully cleaned and disinfected beforehand.	As required.
Where harvesting occurs at sea or at the water's edge, all effluent should be fully contained and never discharged into the water column.	As required.
Screening/netting is maintained to exclude avian predators from containment structures.	Daily observations are conducted.
All equipment used in the retrieval of dead or moribund stock is cleaned and disinfected after use.	As required.
Mortalities are removed on a regular basis to ensure that on-site infection pressure is kept as low as possible. Mortalities are removed from the site and disposed of appropriately.	In line with farm management practices.

Sources of information**AQUAPLAN INFORMATION LEAFLET – Cleaning and Disinfection**

https://www.fishhealth.ie/FHU/sites/default/files/FHU_Files/Documents/CleaningandDisinfectionLeaflet.pdf

AQUAPLAN INFORMATION LEAFLET – General Biosecurity

https://www.fishhealth.ie/FHU/sites/default/files/FHU_Files/Documents/BiosecurityLeaflet.pdf

4.6 Welfare

All aspects of stock production should be carried out to always maintain high welfare standards and continual commitment is given to promote improvements as advances in knowledge and techniques allow.

The 'Five Freedoms', shown below, are supported throughout all stages of the rearing process.

- Freedom from hunger and thirst.
- Freedom from discomfort.
- Freedom from pain, injury or disease.
- Freedom to express normal behaviour.
- Freedom from fear and distress.

These freedoms are provided by:

- a) caring and responsible planning and management.
- b) skilled, knowledgeable and conscientious of stock husbandry staff.
- c) appropriate environmental design.
- d) considerate handling and transport.
- e) humane slaughter.

4.6.1 Operational Welfare Indices (OWIs) for Atlantic Salmon *Salmo salar*

This protocol scores the welfare of individual fish based on a set of welfare indicators describing the appearance of the salmon. Each welfare indicator is divided into levels from good to bad. This OWI protocol can be used as an early warning system, alerting the farmer that something is potentially wrong with the salmon stock and warrants further investigation, preferably before mortality starts to increase. Mortality rate is the most used health related OWI. High or increased mortality rates indicate that there is a welfare problem on the farm. It is necessary to first confirm what is normal and then identify the causes of the observed mortality to take preventive actions. A low mortality rate does not necessarily mean that there is a welfare problem on a farm. Diseases and other issues may reduce welfare without causing death. An OWI scheme devised by Noble et al. (2018)²⁵ suggests scoring 14

²⁵ <https://nofima.com/publication/1636395/>

different indicators on a 0 – 3 scoring system: i) emaciation, ii) skin haemorrhages, iii) lesions/wounds, iv) scale loss, v) eye haemorrhages, vi) exophthalmia, vii) opercular damage, viii) snout damage, ix) vertebral deformities, x) upper jaw deformity, xi) lower jaw deformity, xii) sea lice infection, xiii) active fin damage, xiv) healed fin damage.

5 Land-Based IMTA

Land-based IMTA carried out in the ASTRAL project refers to species production in either recirculating inshore biofloc systems or land-based pump ashore systems with partial water recirculation. Recirculation of water enables more control of certain physical and chemical parameters in production systems, including temperature, dissolved oxygen, pH, and nutrients, with the level of independence from the ambient environment dependent on the extent of the recirculation and geographic location.

5.1 IMTA Lab South Africa – Land-Based Pump Ashore IMTA System

Location, Climate and Species

The land-based pump ashore IMTA production described in this manual has taken place at Buffeljags Abalone (<https://www.vikingaquaculture.co.za/abalone/farming/>), which is located on a pristine stretch of coastline near the remote settlement of Buffeljags on the Cape south coast (34°45'14.7" S 19°36'51.9" E) of South Africa (Figure 50).

Figure 50. Location of IMTA lab South Africa — Buffeljags Abalone Farm. ©B. Macey.

The Cape south coast has a temperate climate that is characterized by long warm and dry summers and cool and wet, but relatively short winters. The average annual temperature in the region is 17 °C and is at its highest in January/February and lowest in July.

Over the course of the year, the temperature typically varies from 8.8 °C to 24.5 °C and is rarely below 5 °C or above 29 °C²⁶. All seawater to produce the species at IMTA lab South Africa is pumped directly from the Atlantic Ocean, via an intake pipe located amongst the kelp beds directly in front of the farm. The mean water temperatures for the Atlantic Ocean in this area are 15.6 °C, with an absolute minimum of 9 °C to an absolute maximum of 23.5 °C (20-year average). Salinity at this site is ca. 35 psu.

The species at the IMTA lab South Africa (Table 12, Figure 51.1) are categorised as: fed, extractive, or novel species.

Table 12. Species cultivated at the site: South African abalone (Figure 51.).

<u>Common name</u>	<u>Latin name</u>	<u>Role in IMTA</u>
Abalone	<i>Haliotis midae</i>	Fed species
Sea lettuce	<i>Ulva lacunculata</i>	Extractive species
Collector sea urchin	<i>Tripneustes gratilla</i>	Fed species
Cape sea urchin	<i>Parechinus angulosus</i>	Novel species

The species at the IMTA lab South Africa (Table 12, Figure 51.1) are categorised as: fed, extractive, or novel species.

1. **Fed species:** Feed is inputted to the system for the South African abalone (*Haliotis midae*) and the tropical sea urchin (*Tripneustes gratilla*). As a result, the animals release waste/nutrients into the water that is used as a nutrient source for the extractive seaweed species grown in the integrated system.
2. **Extractive species:** Dissolved nutrients are extracted by the seaweed *Ulva lacunculata* that is grown in D-ended paddle raceway systems adjacent to the abalone and *Ulva* raceways systems. The seaweed absorbs the dissolved inorganic nitrogen (DIN), which allows for partial to full water recirculation, and *Ulva* grown in the system serves as a supplementary feed for the abalone and urchins.
3. **Novel species:** Tropical sea urchin, *Tripneustes gratilla*, are fed with seaweeds grown in the IMTA process enhancing circularity; and the temperate sea urchin, *Parechinus angulosus*, are

²⁶ <https://weatherspark.com/y/82961/Average-Weather-in-Cape-Town-South-Africa-Year-Round>

fed with seaweeds and their faecal material is used as supplementary feed/probiotic for juvenile abalone, *Haliotis midae*, improving abalone growth/health and enhancing circularity.

Figure 51. Species cultivated at IMTA lab South Africa. (A) South African abalone, *Haliotis midae*, ©J. Bolton; (B) sea lettuce, *Ulva lacunculata*, ©M. Cyrus; (C) collector sea urchin, *Tripneustes gratilla*, © B. de Vos; and (D) Cape sea urchin, *Parechinus angulosus*. ©M. Brink-Hull.

5.1.1 Integrated Abalone-*Ulva* Systems

Buffeljags Abalone farm produces approximately 450 tonnes of the abalone *Haliotis midae* and 600 tonnes of the green seaweed *Ulva lacunculata* annually. The farm is one of the first large commercial abalone farms in South Africa to consistently recirculate 50 % of their seawater by making use of the bioremediation capacity of *Ulva*. To augment biosecurity, Buffeljags Abalone has been specifically designed to consist of modular units. There are seven modular abalone-*Ulva* IMTA systems at the farm, referred to as platforms, which are each composed of four clusters that each consist of one D-ended *Ulva* paddle-raceway and 42 abalone raceway tanks (6 rows each made of 7 abalone raceway tanks) (Figure 52.52). All the effluent water leaving the abalone tanks is bioremediated by *Ulva* in the adjacent paddle-raceway before being mixed with 50 % fresh seawater in the sump. The sump is also equipped with a protein skimmer to remove further waste and dissolved organic nutrients from the

bioremediated seawater before it is returned to the abalone raceways. The clusters do not share water, equipment and other fomites, and various biosecurity measures are implemented to minimize the risk(s) of introducing an infectious disease and spreading it to the animals at a facility and/or between clusters.

Figure 52. Land-based pump ashore IMTA system to produce abalone (*Haliotis midae*) and seaweed (*Ulva lacinulata*) at Buffeljags Abalone Farm. (A) Aerial photograph of the modular abalone-*Ulva* IMTA, ©Viking Aquaculture. (B) Schematic of the IMTA process in a single abalone-*Ulva* cluster. ©B. Macey.

Abalone are cultivated in baskets ($L \times W \times D$: $0.8 \times 0.5 \times 0.5$ m), generally made of 6 mm oyster mesh or perforated PVC (Figure 53), that are suspended in the fiberglass abalone raceway tanks ($L \times W \times D$: $6 \times 1.8 \times 0.8$ m). Each tank has a volume of ca. 8.5 m^3 and can accommodate up to 20 baskets, which are each fitted with PVC dividers (Figure 53d) to increase the surface area within each basket for abalone to attach. The dividers (vertical plates) are typically covered with a feeding plate (Figure 53e) where formulated feed is placed. Seaweed, such as kelp (*Ecklonia maxima*) or *Ulva*, are placed under the feeding plate. Influent water enters on one side of the raceway tank and effluent water exits the opposite side of the tank through a standpipe (Figure 53). Typical flow rates in abalone raceways systems are between $5 - 9 \text{ L s}^{-1} \text{ t}^{-1}$ of abalone²⁷. In general, the total volume in an abalone raceway is replaced once every 2 hours. Water movement and aeration within the raceways is facilitated by air-diffusers that are positioned horizontally under the baskets at the base of the fiberglass raceways. Air to these diffusers is provided by large blowers.

Figure 53. Schematic (side view) of a typical abalone raceway tank used on most South African abalone farms. ©Yearsley, 2008. (a) Influent water enters raceway tank; (b) effluent water leaves through standpipe; (c) oyster mesh/perforated PVC baskets holding abalone; (d) vertical plates in abalone baskets; (e) feeding plate covering abalone baskets; (f) perforated PVC pipe attached to bottom of tank for aeration.

The D-ended *Ulva* paddle-raceways in each cluster have a volume of ca. 150 m^3 ($L \times W \times D$: $30 \times 10 \times 0.5$ m). The shallow paddle-raceways are generally constructed out of concrete and are lined with a white PVC liner to promote the reflection of sunlight and facilitate growth of *Ulva*. Paddle-raceways are typically stocked with $1\text{-}2 \text{ kg Ulva}$ per m^2 of the pond surface area, as this has been shown to be optimal for both the nitrogen content and production of *Ulva*²⁸. Tanks are harvested almost daily to provide feed for abalone and to maintain optimal stocking densities in the raceways. Exceeding optimal stocking densities not only leads to a reduction in production of *Ulva*, due to shading and insufficient nutrient availability, but can put excessive strain on the paddlewheel in the raceway. Seawater and *Ulva* are circulated through the raceway by a centrally located paddlewheel, which keeps

²⁷ Yearsley R.D., 2008. Water quality, abalone growth and the potential for integrated mariculture on a South African abalone *Haliotis midae* L. farm. MSc thesis, Rhodes University, Grahamstown, South Africa 77pp.

²⁸ Neori, A., Krom, M.D., Ellner, S.P., Boyd, C.E., Popper, D., Rabinovitch, R., Davison, P.J., Dvir, O., Zuber, D., Ucko, M., Angel, D., Gordin, H., 1996. Seaweed biofilters as regulators of water quality in integrated fish-seaweed culture units. *Aquaculture* 141, 183-199.

Ulva suspended in the water column and vertical migration of *Ulva* improves exposure to sunlight. Circulation of water in the *Ulva* raceways also ensures a constant supply of cool, aerated water for the growing abalone. Effluent water from the 42 abalone raceways in each cluster is gravity-fed into its adjacent *Ulva* paddle-raceway, where it is bioremediated by *Ulva* and 50 % of this bioremediated water is recirculated back to the abalone tanks once it has been mixed with 50 % fresh seawater in the sump at the end of the paddle-raceway.

5.1.2 Integrated sea urchin-*Ulva* System

Buffeljags Abalone Farm has recently adapted the abalone-*Ulva* IMTA process to produce a new (novel) high value species, the sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla*. The pilot commercial urchin-*Ulva* IMTA system at the site consists of five 8.5 m³ fiberglass raceway tanks (Figure 54), which have identical dimensions to the abalone raceway tanks (Figure 54A), that are interconnected with a 14,000 L D-ended *Ulva* paddle-raceway (Figure 54B) and a 14,000 L sump. The system is fitted with a drum-filter, protein skimmers and a heat-pump to maintain optimal water quality and a constant temperature of ca. 25 °C. The entire system is housed within a tunnel to further conserve heat. This design is necessary for the farming of a tropical species in the temperate environment, where Buffeljags Abalone is located.

Figure 54. Land-based pump-ashore IMTA system to produce sea urchin (*Tripneustes gratilla*) and seaweed (*Ulva lacunculata*) at Buffeljags abalone. The photograph shows (A) the sea urchin raceway tanks and (B) the *Ulva* paddle-raceway systems. ©M. Cyrus.

Effluent water exiting each of the urchin tanks flows into the D-ended *Ulva* paddle-raceway, after passing through the drum-filter to remove larger particulates. The bio-remediated seawater exiting the *Ulva* paddle-raceway enters the sump before being recirculated back to the sea urchin tanks. Water in the sump is consistently circulated through the heat pump to maintain a constant temperature of ca. 25 °C. The water replacement in this system, with fresh incoming seawater from the adjacent ocean, is 10 % per day. The sea urchins in each tank are grown in 6 mm oyster mesh baskets (L × W × D: 0.8 × 0.5 × 0.5 m), with 20 baskets suspended in each raceway. Seawater is circulated through the tanks and *Ulva* paddle-raceways, ensuring a constant supply of heated, aerated

water for the growing sea urchins. Animals are fed on a combination diet consisting of freshly harvested farmed *Ulva lacunculata* and formulated feed containing 20 % dried *Ulva lacunculata*²⁹.

5.2 Species Production

5.2.1 Farm Management

The management of a land-based pump ashore IMTA production system includes a number of daily/weekly/monthly activities that are common to all the production species.

5.2.1.1 Routine Operations (daily/weekly/monthly)

- Daily feeding of animals.
- Daily inspection and monitoring of animal health and behaviour must be conducted. This is most frequently done when feeding animals and cleaning systems. Health assessment should include observations of feed response (feeding less or more), animal behaviour (noting any abnormal behaviour), general appearance of animals (e.g., colour, visual marks, shell integrity, or sores/lesions, loss of spines), and presence of any external parasites (e.g., shell boring worms).
- Daily removal of any moribund or dead animals from the baskets. Records of daily morbidity/mortality must be kept, as this could provide early warning of emerging problems (e.g., disease, poor nutrition, adverse water quality) in the system.
- Daily/weekly recording of environmental parameters on site, including pH, salinity, temperature, dissolved oxygen, and nutrients such as phosphate, nitrate, nitrite, and ammonia.
- Daily system checks and system maintenance (when required).
- Daily maintenance of biosecurity check points (e.g., footbaths, hand sanitizers, sterilisation of equipment, including boots and overalls) and ensure all areas are tidy and free of clutter.
- Other routine activities on the farm include grading of animals to reduce stocking densities to optimal levels within baskets. Grading on most abalone farms generally occurs once every 3-4 months^{30,31}. Grading of sea urchins occurs weekly. The specific procedures for each of these

²⁹ Cyrus, M.D., Bolton, J.J., De Wet, L., Macey, B.M., 2014. The development of a formulated feed containing *Ulva* (Chlorophyta) to promote rapid growth and enhanced production of high-quality roe in the sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla* (Linnaeus). *Aquaculture Research* 45, 159–176.

³⁰ Brand, M.J., 2023. *Ulva* as a functional feed ingredient: A practical investigation into the effects of *Ulva lacunculata* on the growth, consumption, health and gut microbiome of the farmed abalone *Haliotis midae*. PhD thesis, University of Cape Town, Rondebosch, South Africa 203pp.

³¹ Yearsley R.D., 2008. Water quality, abalone growth and the potential for integrated mariculture on a South African abalone *Haliotis midae* L. farm. MSc thesis, Rhodes University, Grahamstown, South Africa 77pp.

activities, including maintenance of *Ulva* density in raceways, are discussed in detail below under production of each species.

5.2.1.2 Recordkeeping

- Stocking and feeding records to be updated as required.
- Record of daily/weekly environmental parameters.
- Record of daily morbidities and mortalities.
- Biosecurity records updated daily.
- Record of health checks/visits carried out.
- Site visitors log updated as required.

5.2.2 South African Abalone (*Haliotis midae*)

Haliotis midae is a marine mollusc belonging to the phylum Mollusca, a diverse group of organisms that includes, amongst others, the chitons, clams, snails, squids, and octopuses. There are approximately 100 species of abalone worldwide that are found in tropical, temperate, and cold waters, ranging in depth from the low tide line to depths exceeding 30 meters³². However, of all these species, only fifteen are commercially exploited³³. In South Africa, there are five endemic species of *Haliotis* (*H. midae*, *H. parvum* L., *H. spadicea*, *H. queketti*, and *H. speciosa*) that occur along specific regions of the coastline³⁴. Of these, only *Haliotis midae*, known locally as ‘perlemoen’, is of commercial significance and has been commercially exploited since 1949³⁵.

The South African abalone aquaculture industry is small in comparison to certain global aquaculture industries, but the country is nevertheless the third-largest producer of cultured abalone worldwide after China and South Korea³⁶. Abalone is by far the most successful aquaculture sub-sector in South Africa, in terms of value, and was comprised of 14 farms in 2021 that collectively produced around 2500 tonnes of abalone (fresh weight). Most of these farms have their own hatchery and do not rely on an external seed supply, with the hatchery phase of production taking ca. 9-months to complete and grow-out ca. another 2 – 3 years depending on the size of the final product (Figure 55), which typically ranges from 100-140 g (wet weight). All current commercial abalone farms in South Africa are land-based pump-ashore systems, with five of these farms operating integrated systems where they

³² Bevelander, G., 1988. Abalone: Gross and fine structure. The Boxwood Press, Pacific Grove, California.

³³ Britz, P. J., 1990. Global status of abalone aquaculture. In Perlemoen farming in South Africa. (Ed) Cook, P. Mariculture association of South Africa. pp 20-26.

³⁴ Branch, G. M., Griffiths, C. L., Branch, M. L., Beckley, L. E., 1994. Two Oceans. A guide to the marine life of Southern Africa. David Philip Publishers, South Africa.

³⁵ Tarr, R. (1992) The abalone fishery of South Africa. In Abalone of the world: Biology, fisheries, and culture. (Ed). Shepard, S. A., Tegner, M. J., del Preo, G. Blackwell Scientific Publication, Oxford. pp 438-447.

³⁶ <https://www.globalseafood.org/advocate/south-africa-abalone-farming-goes-gold/>.

grow the green macroalga *Ulva lacunculata* in the abalone effluent. This practice allows for partial recirculation, bioremediation of effluent water and production of a supplementary feed for the abalone.

Figure 55. Production cycle of the South African abalone *Haliotis midae*. ©DFFE & UCT.

Standard Operating Protocols (SOPs) to produce many of the commercially important abalone species, as well as other marine gastropods, have been described in detail by Hahn³⁷. However, since abalone aquaculture in South Africa only started in the early 1990's, this handbook contains limited information on the production, particularly grow-out technologies, of the South African abalone *Haliotis midae*. Regardless, most information in the "Handbook of culture of abalone and other marine molluscs" is still highly relevant to the production of *H. midae* and will provide a good initial guide to prospective abalone farmers.

The SOP outlined in this document includes some of the information provided in the Hahn (1989) handbook, but mostly incorporates information derived from an extensive review of published literature on *H. midae*, unpublished information obtained from student theses (when available on

³⁷ Hahn, K.O., 1989. Handbook of culture of abalone and other marine gastropods. CRC Press Inc., Florida, United States of America. 348pp.

online library databases) and the practical knowledge gained at IMTA lab SA. The cultivation and husbandry practices for *Tripneustes gratilla*, the new high valued invertebrate that has been introduced at IMTA lab SA, will be discussed in detail in section 5.2.3. Similarly, the cultivation and the husbandry practices for *Ulva*, grown in the integrated abalone-*Ulva* and urchin-*Ulva* IMTA systems at Buffeljags Abalone Farm, will be discussed in section 5.2.4. For additional detailed information on broodstock management, spawning, larval rearing, larval settlement, and weaning of *Haliotis midae*, please refer to Genade³⁸, Visser-Roux³⁹, and the FAO 'Training Manual on Artificial Breeding of Abalone'⁴⁰.

5.2.2.1 Conditioning, Spawning and Seed Production

5.2.2.1.1 Broodstock collection and conditioning

Haliotis midae generally do not spawn when mature/ripe individuals are collected from the wild, so a hatchery broodstock population must be established and conditioned using specific protocols to ensure that animals can be spawned successfully on a regular basis⁴¹. When collecting broodstock from the wild, it is highly recommended that broodstock animals are collected as close to the production facility as possible to establish a base population that resembles the genetic profile of the surrounding wild populations. If it is not possible to collect broodstock animals close to the hatchery/production facility, then animals from the same genetic stock should be sourced. These measures will ensure minimal genetic impact in the event of the escape of animals from the farming systems. It is also recommended that the base population be made up of sufficient numbers of broodstock (nmales - nfemales = 50-75) that are sourced from the surrounding wild populations in a random manner⁴². Most wild collected broodstock are approximately 15-years old, with an average length and weight of 20 ± 5 cm and 1.5 ± 0.5 kg, respectively³⁹. Male and female broodstock animals must be housed separately in the holding facility and be tagged to facilitate management of animals and/or spawning events in the hatchery.

Several methods have been proposed for conditioning broodstock animals, but the most common approach is to provide optimal living conditions (tailored to the ecology of the species) and to feed

³⁸ Genade, A.B., Hirst, A.L., Smith, C.J., 1998. Observations on the spawning, development and rearing of the South African abalone *Haliotis midae* Linn. South African Journal of Marine Science 6, 3-12.

³⁹ Visser-Roux, A., 2011. Reproduction of the South African Abalone, *Haliotis midae*. PhD, Animal Sciences, University of Stellenbosch, Stellenbosch, South Africa 88pp.

⁴⁰ <https://www.fao.org/3/ab731e/AB731E00.htm>.

⁴¹ Sales, J., Britz, P. J., 2001. Research on abalone (*Haliotis midae* L.) cultivation in South Africa. Aquaculture Research 32:863-874.

⁴² Department of Forestry, Fisheries, and the Environment (DFFE), Permit: Specific Conditions for Abalone, 2023.

animals *ad libitum*⁴³ with suitable feeds. *H. midae* broodstock are generally kept at a constant temperature of ca. 16-18°C under fluorescent lights that are set to provide a 12:12 day. Males and females are maintained in separate small holding tanks (generally 40-50 L fiberglass or plastic tanks — to facilitate removal of the animals when spawning and cleaning) at a low stocking density of ca. 3-5 individuals per tank⁴⁴. Each tank is supplied with constant air and filtered (0.45-1.0µm) seawater and cleaned regularly (2-3 times per week). Water in each of the holding tanks is replaced approximately 2-3 times per hour, and animals are generally fed a diet of natural seaweed consisting mainly of kelp (*Ecklonia maxima*) and *Ulva*, but other seaweeds (e.g., *Gracilaria*) may also be provided dependent on their availability. A conditioning period of at least 1-month is required when animals are maintained under the conditions described above⁴⁵.

New broodstock animals (F1 and beyond) are selected based on production parameters such as above average growth, shell condition, and general health. Although Tarr⁴⁵ showed that abalone from the wild reach 100 % sexual maturity at around 7.2 years, it has been demonstrated that abalone kept under cultured conditions mature earlier and 100 % sexual maturity may occur as early as 3 years of age⁴⁵. Newman⁴⁶ demonstrated that there is a linear relationship between fecundity and animal weight, with egg production per individual in the order of several million.

5.2.2.1.2 Spawning

Abalone hold matured eggs for 3 – 6 months and can be spawned and eggs artificially collected using various external stimuli. Common stimuli include rapidly increasing water temperature, subjecting abalone to a sudden change in pH, treating water in the holding tanks with UV-light, which releases hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), or by addition of H₂O₂ directly to the water in the holding tanks⁴⁵. One of the most commonly used methods for inducing abalone to spawn in hatcheries is by administering H₂O₂ to the water in holding tanks at a concentration of ca. 25 mg.kg⁻¹, due to the fast and inexpensive nature of the procedure. In South Africa, most farms initially treat the water in the holding tanks with sodium hydroxide to increase water pH before addition of H₂O₂ ca. 15 minutes later. Abalone are exposed to the H₂O₂ for ca. 3 hours, before tanks are emptied and washed out to remove residual chemicals that

⁴³ Hahn, K.O., 1989. Handbook of culture of abalone and other marine gastropods. CRC Press, Florida, United States of America. 348pp.

⁴⁴ Visser-Roux, A., 2011. Reproduction of the South African Abalone, *Haliotis midae*. PhD, Animal Sciences, University of Stellenbosch, Stellenbosch, South Africa 88pp.

⁴⁵ Tarr, R. (1992) The abalone fishery of South Africa. In Abalone of the world: Biology, fisheries, and culture. (Ed). Shepard, S. A., Tegner, M. J., del Preo, G. Blackwell Scientific Publication, Oxford. pp 438-447.

⁴⁶ Newman, G.G., 1966. Movement of the South African abalone *Haliotis midae*. Division of Sea Fisheries: Investigational Report, 56, pp.1-20.

could be toxic to the gametes⁴⁷ and refilled with fresh filtered seawater. Once filled, water flow is switched off to prevent dilution of gametes when spawning commences⁴⁸. Male abalone generally start to spawn after 4 hours and females after 6 hours⁵⁰. Following spawning, the quality of the released gametes should be carefully examined and the concentration of released sperm and eggs measured and adjusted accordingly. Visser-Roux⁵⁰ determined that a sperm concentration of 50,000 sperm.mL⁻¹ and egg concentrations of ≤50 eggs.mL⁻¹ produced the highest hatch-out rates for *H. midae*. It was further shown that while fertilisation volume did not influence fertilisation success, fertilisation potential of the eggs did decrease with time, with eggs older than 100 minutes exhibiting lower fertilisation potential than eggs fertilised earlier. It is recommended that eggs are fertilized within 60-minutes following release. Following fertilisation, eggs are carefully washed to remove excess sperm and other debris. Fertilisation success is then determined under a light microscope (which generally exceeds 80 %) and fertilised eggs are transferred to hatch-out tanks. Spawners should be matured for a further 80 days prior to a second spawning event. Under such conditions, the number and quality of released eggs are ensured⁴⁹.

5.2.2.1.3 Hatch-out, larval rearing and settlement

Hatch-out trays are generally shallow plastic containers filled with filtered (0.45-1.0µm) seawater maintained at the same temperature as the broodstock holding tanks, to prevent temperature shock to transferred eggs (Figure 56a). Trochophores (Figure 56b) tend to concentrate at the surface of the plastic containers (negative geotaxis), and healthy veliger's (Figure 56c) congregate in vertical columns and repeatedly (every few minutes) tumble to the bottom of the tanks, scatter and regroup to reform new columns. Development from cleavage through to hatch-out normally occurs after 12-hours post-fertilisation and at 24-hours post-fertilisation the veliger larvae are transferred to larval rearing tanks. Other developmental stages of *H. midae* include: The inflate-shell veliger larvae (torsion; 207×265µm) with retractor muscle (Figure 56d); Operculate veliger (pre-eye spot) (Figure 56e); Operculate veliger larvae (pre-eye spot) with retracted velum (figure 56f); Crawling and settling stage (Figure 56g); Peristomial growth (Figure 56h); Circular-shell post-larvae (±600µm) (Figure 56i); Whole shell with no respiratory pores (Figure 56j); Juveniles showing dietary pigmentation on shell (Figure 56k); Juveniles of approximately 1-year of age (Figure 56l)⁵⁰.

⁴⁷ Morse, D.E., Duncan, H., Hooker, N., Morse, A., 1977. Hydrogen peroxide induces spawning in mollusks, with activation of prostaglandin endoperoxide synthetase. *Science*, 196, pp.298-300.

⁴⁸ Visser-Roux, A., 2011. Reproduction of the South African Abalone, *Haliotis midae*. PhD, Animal Sciences, University of Stellenbosch, Stellenbosch, South Africa 88pp.

⁴⁹ <https://www.fao.org/3/ab731e/AB731E00.htm>.

⁵⁰ Genade, A.B., Hirst, A.L., Smith, C.J., 1988. Observations on the spawning, development and rearing of the South African abalone *Haliotis midae* Linn. *South African Journal of Marine Science* 6, 3-12.

Generally, the upper water layer of the hatching tank is collected and transferred to the larval rearing tanks as this contains the actively swimming, healthy larvae, while the underdeveloped or abnormal larvae at the bottom of the hatching tanks are flushed.

Figure 56. Developmental stages of the South African abalone *Haliotis midae*. ©Genade et al., 1988⁵¹.

Once the veliger larvae are transferred to the larval rearing tanks, their metamorphosis and growth should be closely monitored. Larval development of *Haliotis* sp. is temperature dependent, with development occurring faster at higher temperatures⁵². The larval development rate is measured by the time required for larvae to exhibit features that are distinctive to each stage (Figure 56), with settlement, metamorphosis, and deposition of the peristomal shell marking the transition from larval to post-larval development.

Larval rearing normally takes place in conical fiberglass or plastic tanks that are filled with filtered and sterilized seawater maintained at the same temperature as the broodstock rearing tanks (specific to

⁵¹ Genade, A.B., Hirst, A.L., Smith, C.J., 1988. Observations on the spawning, development and rearing of the South African abalone *Haliotis midae* Linn. South African Journal of Marine Science 6, 3-12.

⁵² Hahn, 1989. Handbook of culture of abalone and other marine gastropods. CRC Press Inc., Florida, United States of America. 348pp.

the physiological requirements of the species being cultivated). The temperature of the water added to the rearing tanks should be within ± 1 °C so the transferred trochophore larvae are not killed by thermal shock. Aeration is generally not used in the larval rearing tanks as this can cause injury to the fragile larvae. For many Haliotid species, a larval density of approximately 300 larvae/L is recommended⁵³. The rearing tanks with the newly hatched trochophore larvae are maintained in a dark, temperature-controlled room until the larval shell is completely formed. The progress of larval development is summarized in Figure 56 above and takes approximately 5 – 7 days before the crawling and settling stage (Figure 56g) is reached. It is at this stage that larvae are moved to settlement tanks containing settlement plates precoated with an appropriate settlement substrate.

Induction of settlement is a critical step in the cultivation of *Haliotis* sp. During larval rearing, from fertilization to veliger's competent to settle, survival rates can be as high as 95 %, whereas survival rates of ca. 10 % are common during the transition from planktonic veliger to benthic juvenile⁵⁴. Competent larvae display distinctive behaviours, including a repeated upward swimming and sinking behaviours as they search for a suitable (inducing) substrate to settle on. When a suitable settlement substrate is provided, the larvae will change shape several times before the spat begin to actively graze on the benthic diatoms provided on the plates. Settlement plates are generally made from flat or corrugated plastic sheets that have been pre-coated or seeded with either naturally occurring benthic diatoms or specific strains of diatoms that have been cultured in the hatchery. Benthic diatoms commonly used in abalone hatcheries include species of *Cocconeis*, *Nitzschia*, *Navicula* and *Amphora*⁵⁶. Some hatcheries also use plates that have been grazed by juvenile abalone, which results in the succession of a secondary diatom community and a layer of polysaccharide mucus — a known settlement inducer for abalone. Settlement plates are prepared 2 – 3 weeks in advance of settlement by suspending the plates in a slurry of the diatom(s) that is poured into the settlement tanks. Settlement tanks used at different hatcheries can vary substantially in size and shape, but generally consist of rectangular fiberglass tanks in which the vertical settlement plates can be suspended. Indoor tanks should have sufficient lighting above the tanks to facilitate growth of the benthic diatoms and optimal coating of the plates with the benthic diatoms. For some *Haliotis* sp., the density of benthic diatoms on the settlement plates is recommended to be ca. 3000 cells/mm² for optimal settlement and survival⁵⁵. Once the competent larvae are added to the settlement tanks, the tanks should be maintained under constant lighting (to facilitate growth of the benthic diatoms, gentle aeration should be provided and there should be a daily exchange of water. Juvenile stocking density should be ca. 400

⁵³ <https://www.fao.org/3/ab731e/AB731E00.htm>.

⁵⁴ Hahn, 1989. Handbook of culture of abalone and other marine gastropods. CRC Press Inc., Florida, United States of America. 348pp.

– 500 spat/m². Growth of the benthic diatoms on the plates should be carefully monitored during this phase of cultivation and occasional shading (e.g., by covering tanks with 50 % shade netting) may be required to control the growth of the benthic diatom communities. Water quality in the tanks must be monitored daily. Newly settled larvae can feed on benthic diatoms measuring between 5 – 10 µm during the first ca. 2 weeks and after ca. 20 days the spat are capable of consuming diatoms of 20 µm⁵⁵. When the juveniles reach a size of ca. 1.5 mm shell length (SL), which takes approximately 3 months for *H. midae*, the animals are transferred from the settlement plates (de-plated) to juvenile rearing tanks. These tanks are typically shallow rectangular fiberglass tanks equipped with suitable housing, such as PVC half-round piping, to provide refuge for the juveniles. Tanks are provided with constant aeration and flowing water maintained at the temperature of 15 – 18 °C. During this phase of production, the juveniles are fed on a diet consisting of formulated feed (1 – 4 mm pellet size, depending on size of juveniles) or seaweeds (e.g., *Gracilaria* and *Ulva*). Uneaten food and excrement at the bottom of the tanks must be removed daily before new feed is administered. Juvenile *Haliotis midae* are maintained in these tanks until they reach a size of approximately 16 – 18 mm SL, which takes ca. 6 – 7 months, before they are moved to the grow-out platforms on the farm.

5.2.2.2 Feed & Nutrition

As with most intensive farming operations, feed constitutes a major proportion of the production costs on South African abalone farms. Abalone on most farms in South Africa are typically fed various combinations of wild harvested kelp *Ecklonia maxima* (Figure 57A) or formulated feed (Figure 57B)⁵⁶.⁵⁷ Of these, kelp is still the major feed on most farms and wild harvests for this purpose reached a peak of ca. 7000 tonnes (fresh) in 2011⁵⁸. Harvests have since dropped, partly due to the increased use of formulated feed on abalone farms, but also because of the use of other seaweeds, such as *Ulva* and *Gracilaria*, that are cultivated on certain farms (Figures 57C and D, respectively). There are currently five integrated seaweed-abalone farms in South Africa that do this and collectively grow more than 2000 tonnes of *Ulva lacunculata* per annum, mostly in abalone effluent, to use as a feed for abalone⁵⁹.

⁵⁵ <https://www.fao.org/3/ab731e/AB731E00.htm>.

⁵⁶ Yearsley R.D., 2008. Water quality, abalone growth and the potential for integrated mariculture on a South African abalone *Haliotis midae* L. farm. MSc thesis, Rhodes University, Grahamstown, South Africa 77pp.

⁵⁷ Troell M., Robertson-Andersson D., Anderson R.J., Bolton J.J., Maneveldt G., Halling C., Probyn, T., 2006. Abalone farming in South Africa: An overview with perspectives on kelp resources, abalone feed, potential for on-farm seaweed production and socio-economic importance. *Aquaculture* 257(1-4), 266-281.

⁵⁸ Rothman, M.D., Anderson, R.J., Kanjengo, L., Bolton, J.J., 2020. Trends in seaweed resource use and aquaculture in South Africa and Namibia over the last 30 years. *Botanica Marina* <https://doi.org/10.1515/bot-2019-0074>.

⁵⁹ Bachoo, T., Bolton, J.J., Macey, B.M., Kandjengo, L., Reddy, M.M., 2023. Resolving the identity of commercially cultivated *Ulva* (Ulvaaceae, Chlorophyta) in integrated seaweed-abalone aquaculture farms in South Africa. *Journal of Phycology* 2023:1-12. DOI: 10.1111/jpy.13391.

Figure 57. Photographs of typical feeds administered to cultured abalone *Haliotis midae* in South Africa. (A) Wild harvested kelp *Ecklonia maxima*, ©J. Bolton. (B) Formulated feed, ©Marifeed. (C) Sea lettuce *Ulva lacunculata*, ©Viking Aquaculture. (D) *Gracilaria* sp. ©J. Bolton.

None of this *Ulva* grown on South African abalone farms is currently sold for other purposes⁶⁰. There are also a few farms that grow *Gracilaria* in tanks as feed (Figure 63D), mostly for juvenile abalone in the hatchery and weaning phases, and production is estimated to be around 600 tonnes (wet weight) per annum⁶¹. Formulated feed use on South African abalone farms was estimated to be around 200 tonnes (dry weight) in 2004⁶². However, production of abalone has practically doubled since then, from 833 tonnes in 2006 to 1,656 tonnes in 2019⁶³, and it is projected that the use of formulated feed has increased proportionally with this increase in production. Formulated feeds, which are relatively high in protein (Figure 63B, 26 – 34 %), are preferred by most South African abalone farmers as they are

⁶⁰ Bolton, J.J., Cyrus, M.D., Brand, M.J., Joubert, M., Macey, B.M., 2016. Why grow *Ulva*? Its potential in the future of aquaculture. *Perspectives in Phycology* 3(3), 113-120.

⁶¹ Rothman, M.D., Anderson, R.J., Kanjengo, L., Bolton, J.J., 2020. Trends in seaweed resource use and aquaculture in South Africa and Namibia over the last 30 years. *Botanica Marina* <https://doi.org/10.1515/bot-2019-0074>.

⁶² Troell M., Robertson-Andersson D., Anderson R.J., Bolton J.J., Maneveldt G., Halling C., Probyn, T., 2006. Abalone farming in South Africa: An overview with perspectives on kelp resources, abalone feed, potential for on-farm seaweed production and socio-economic importance. *Aquaculture* 257(1-4), 266-281.

⁶³ Department of Forestry, Fisheries, and the Environment (DFFE) Aquaculture 2020 Yearbook, South Africa.

regarded as fundamental to the growth of abalone in intensive systems and because of their convenience to farm operations and management⁶⁴. Most of the formulated feed used on South African abalone farms is produced locally by two feed manufacturers' — Marifeed (Pty) Ltd.⁶⁵ and Specialized Aquatic Feeds⁶⁶. These formulated feeds contain mainly fishmeal, defatted soybean meal, starch, vitamins, and minerals⁶⁷. Both fishmeal and soybean meal are included as it has been shown that a combination of these ingredients results in faster growth of abalone than diets containing fishmeal as the sole protein source^{68, 69}. More recently, there has been an increase in the inclusion of seaweeds, such as kelps (mostly *E. maxima*), *Ulva* and to a lesser extent *Gracilaria*, as alternative protein sources and primarily for their use as functional feed ingredients⁷⁰. Research has also shown that mixed diets, for example combinations of seaweeds or formulated feed supplemented with fresh seaweed(s), produce better growth rates than single-species diets⁷¹.

Since abalone are nocturnal feeders, they are generally fed daily late in the afternoon on most abalone farms to promote optimal uptake of feed(s) and reduce leaching of ingredients from formulated feeds. Previous studies have shown that feeding rates for *H. midae* are rapid, averaging 0.45 – 0.48 % body weight per hour over a 24-hour period, with the bulk of the feed consumed between 18H00 and 24H00⁷². On most abalone farms in South Africa, including Buffeljags Abalone, formulated feeds are added on top of the feeding plates, whereas seaweeds such as kelp and *Ulva* are added below the feeding plates between the vertical plates within each basket. During the night, abalone will move onto the top of the feeding plates to consume the formulated feeds. On farms where *Ulva* is provided as feed, it is either grown in paddle-raceway systems receiving abalone effluent or fertilized at least once a week. The crude protein levels of effluent grown or fertilized *Ulva* has been reported to range

⁶⁴ Sales, J., Britz, P. J., 2001. Research on abalone (*Haliotis midae* L.) cultivation in South Africa. *Aquaculture Research* 32:863-874.

⁶⁵ <https://marifeed.com/>.

⁶⁶ <https://www.specialisedaquaticfeeds.com>.

⁶⁷ Troell M., Robertson-Andersson D., Anderson R.J., Bolton J.J., Maneveldt G., Halling C., Probyn, T., 2006. Abalone farming in South Africa: An overview with perspectives on kelp resources, abalone feed, potential for on-farm seaweed production and socio-economic importance. *Aquaculture* 257(1-4), 266-281.

⁶⁸ Riddin, N.A., 2013. Growth and gonad size in cultured South African abalone, *Haliotis midae*. MSc thesis, Rhodes University, South Africa.

⁶⁹ Wu, Y., Kaiser, H., Jones, C.L.W., 2019. A first study on the effect of dietary soya levels and crystalline isoflavones on growth, gonad development and gonad histology of farmed abalone, *Haliotis midae*. *Aquaculture International* 27, 167-193.

⁷⁰ Brand, M.J., 2023. *Ulva* as a functional feed: A practical investigation into the effects of *Ulva lacunculata* on the growth, consumption, health, and gut microbiota of the farmed abalone *Haliotis midae*. PhD, Department of Biological Sciences, University of Cape Town, Rondebosch 203pp.

⁷¹ Naidoo, K., Maneveldt, G., Ruck, K., Bolton, J.J., 2006. A comparison of various seaweed-based diets and formulated feed on growth rate of abalone in a land-based aquaculture system. *Journal of Applied Phycology* 18(3-5), 437-443. DOI: 10.1007/s10811-006-9045-7.

⁷² Sales, J., Britz, P. J., 2001. Research on abalone (*Haliotis midae* L.) cultivation in South Africa. *Aquaculture Research* 32, 863-874.

from 7.8 – 25.8 %^{73, 74, 75} and is consistently higher when compared to that of wild harvested kelp (9.73 %). At Buffeljags Abalone, crude protein level of *Ulva* grown in abalone effluent ranges between 18 – 22 % and varies with season, being higher in the summer months when temperatures are higher. Kelp is harvested from the wild and farmers in South Africa require a Right from the Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment (DFFE) to harvest. Alternatively, kelp is procured from an existing Rights holder near the farm. Harvesting of *Ecklonia maxima* for abalone as feed involves the cutting of fronds during low tide and is generally done from boats⁷⁶.

Numerous studies have investigated daily feed intake for *H. midae*^{77, 78, 79}. Feeding rates can vary from 0.3 – 0.5 % body weight (BW) per day, and will depend on the type of feed, system type and environmental conditions. For example, Britz et al. (2001)⁸⁰ reported feeding rates of 0.35 – 0.4 % BW/day for abalone fed formulated feed and demonstrated a reduction in feeding rates with increasing size of abalone. Conversely, abalone fed with kelp (*E. maxima*) exhibited slightly higher feeding rates of ca. 0.48 % BW/day⁸¹, which is comparable to the feeding rates (0.48 % BW/day) of abalone fed a mixed diet of formulated feed supplemented with either kelp or *Ulva*⁸². One of the main formulated feed suppliers in South Africa, Marifeed (Pty) Ltd. recommends that abalone farmers start by feeding 0.3 % of the abalone's body weight per day, and if all the feed is consumed within 24 hours to increase the daily feeding rate⁸¹. "The supplementation of macroalgae into the diets of farmed abalone is done *ad lib* under standard production methods" on most S. African abalone farms⁶³. However, Brand (2023)⁸² clearly demonstrated that much as 60 % of the formulated feed administered to abalone daily can be supplemented with either *Ulva* or *E. maxima* without negatively altering

⁷³ Robertson-Andersson, D.V., Maneveldt, G.W., Naidoo, K., 2011. Effects of wild and farm-grown macroalgae on the growth of juvenile South African abalone *Haliotis midae* Linnaeus. African Journal of Aquatic Science 36(3):331–337. DOI: 10.2989/16085914.2011.636910.

⁷⁴ Shuuluka, D., Bolton, J.J., Anderson, R.J., 2013. Protein content, amino acid composition and nitrogen-to-protein conversion factors of *Ulva rigida* and *Ulva capensis* from natural populations and *Ulva lactuca* from an aquaculture system, in South Africa. Journal of Applied Phycology 25, 677–685. DOI: 10.1007/s10811-012-9902-5.

⁷⁵ Queirós, A.S., Circuncisão, A.R., Pereira, E., Válega, M., Abreu, M.H., Silva, A.M.S., Cardoso, S.M., 2021. Valuable Nutrients from *Ulva rigida*: Modulation by Seasonal and Cultivation Factors. Applied Sciences. 11(13), 6137. DOI: 10.3390/app11136137.

⁷⁶ Troell M., Robertson-Andersson D., Anderson R.J., Bolton J.J., Maneveldt G., Halling C., Probyn, T., 2006. Abalone farming in South Africa: An overview with perspectives on kelp resources, abalone feed, potential for on-farm seaweed production and socio-economic importance. Aquaculture 257(1-4), 266-281.

⁷⁷ Britz, P.J., Hecht, T., Mangold, S., 1997. Effect of temperature on growth, feed consumption and nutritional indices of *Haliotis midae* fed a formulated diet. Aquaculture 152, 191–203.

⁷⁸ Francis, T.L., Maneveldt, G.W., Venter, J. 2008. Determining the most appropriate feeding regime for the South African abalone *Haliotis midae* Linnaeus grown on kelp. Journal of Applied Phycology 20, 597–602. DOI: 10.1007/s10811-007-9266-4.

⁷⁹ Brand, M.J., 2023. *Ulva* as a functional feed: A practical investigation into the effects of *Ulva lacunculata* on the growth, consumption, health, and gut microbiota of the farmed abalone *Haliotis midae*. PhD, Department of Biological Sciences, University of Cape Town, Rondebosch 203pp.

⁸⁰ Sales, J., Britz, P. J., 2001. Research on abalone (*Haliotis midae* L.) cultivation in South Africa. Aquaculture Research 32:863-874.

⁸¹ https://marifeed.com/choosing-your-feed/#tips_on_feeding.

specific growth rate, shell growth, or condition factor of farmed abalone. He further demonstrated that feeding small amounts of seaweed improved overall consumption of feeds, highlighting the advantages of a mixed feeding regime, and providing additional support to previous research on this topic/species.

5.2.2.3 Stocking Density

Animals in intensive farming systems are generally kept at densities that far exceed what would normally be found in nature, which is necessary for achieving optimal production and economic yields. *Haliotis midae* in the wild have been reported to occur at densities ranging from 82 – 133 g/m², but farmed abalone are kept at far higher stocking densities of ca. 2 kg/m⁸². Suboptimal stocking densities are considered one of the major stress attributing factors in intensive aquaculture, resulting in increased competition for space and food and will also adversely impact water quality in the tanks, as well as animal condition, growth, and survival rates⁸³. Optimal stocking density will differ from farm to farm and depends on a variety of interrelated factors, including the farming system utilized (e.g., flow-through vs. recirculation), the flow-rates achievable within the raceway systems, size class of animal, feed administered on the farm and its quality, and the environmental conditions at the specific site.

The stocking density of abalone on most farms in South Africa is generally expressed as the percentage of available surface area (ASA) in a basket that can be covered by the abalone, and this is then frequently translated to a kg/basket value for practical purposes. To increase the available surface area, each basket is fitted with vertical plates that are made from PVC and separated by plastic dividers (Figure 59). Stocking density on abalone farms generally ranges from 16 – 18 % of the ASA in a basket, but “may be increased until a size dependant threshold is reached at which growth rates and animal health may be reduced”⁸⁴. Flow rates within raceways tanks will depend on the stocking density and should increase with increasing stocking density to avoid adverse impacts on growth through competition for space and degradation of water quality. Nicholson⁸⁶ studied the effects of varying stocking density (16 %, 20 %, 22 % and 24 % of ASA) on different size classes of abalone (15 – 35 g, 45 – 65 g, and 70 – 90 g starting weight) and demonstrated a reduction in weight gain with increasing stocking density for all size classes of abalone tested. Conversely, food conversion ratio (FCR) and condition factor were not significantly affected.

⁸² Yearsley R.D., 2008. Water quality, abalone growth and the potential for integrated mariculture on a South African abalone *Haliotis midae* L. farm. MSc thesis, Rhodes University, Grahamstown, South Africa 77pp.

⁸³ Nicholson, G.H., 2014. Towards understanding the effects of stocking density on famed South African abalone, *Haliotis midae*. MSc, Department of Ichthyology, Rhodes University, Grahamstown 79pp.

⁸⁴ Meusel, E., Menanteau-Ledouble, S., Naylor, M., Kaiser, H., El-Matbouli, M., 2020. Gonad development in farmed male and female South African abalone, *Haliotis midae*, fed artificial and natural diets under a range of husbandry conditions. *Aquaculture International* 30, 1279-1293. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10499-022-00850-6>.

Most abalone farms in South Africa stock at an initial density of 10 kg/basket during the grow-out phase of production. Once every 3 – 4 months, animals are graded into size classes (small, medium, large, or rejects), and re-stocked at 10 kg/basket. Damaged abalone are generally grouped as rejects, which are removed from the general production for alternative uses (most frequently used as product for canning). The density per basket is readjusted to 10 kg/basket following every sorting event to account for abalone growth, which is projected to be approximately 1 kg/basket/month on most abalone farms⁸⁵. These adjustments are made to optimize space allocated to growing abalone and the management of feeding regimes to ensure maximum yields as measured by weight of the abalone produced.

5.2.2.4 Optimal Environmental Ranges

The commercially exploited South African abalone *Haliotis midae* is distributed from St Helena Bay on the west coast to just north of Port St Johns on the east coast of Southern Africa⁸⁶. All the abalone farms in South Africa fall within the natural range of *Haliotis midae* (Figure 58), apart from the northern Cape farms (Diamond Coast Abalone and Port Nolloth Seafarms, where *H. midae* does not occur naturally but conditions are still suitable for growth), so the animals are adapted to the environmental conditions of the coastal waters that are pumped ashore to supply the farmed animals⁸⁷.

⁸⁵ Brand, M.J., 2023. Ulva as a functional feed: A practical investigation into the effects of *Ulva lacunculata* on the growth, consumption, health, and gut microbiota of the farmed abalone *Haliotis midae*. PhD, Department of Biological Sciences, University of Cape Town, Rondebosch 203pp.

⁸⁶ Simpson, B.J.A., 1994. An investigation of diet management strategies for the culture of the South African abalone, *Haliotis midae*. MSc thesis, University of Cape Town, Cape Town, South Africa.

⁸⁷ Yearsley R.D., 2008. Water quality, abalone growth and the potential for integrated mariculture on a South African abalone *Haliotis midae* L. farm. MSc thesis, Rhodes University, Grahamstown, South Africa 77pp.

Figure 58. Distribution of mariculture farms along the South African coast, with the location of abalone farms depicted by the green lines/dots. ©DFFE.

5.2.2.4.1 Temperature

Temperature is regarded as the primary environmental factor affecting the physiology of abalone, directly affecting oxygen levels and feed consumption, ammonia excretion, growth, and survival rates⁸⁸. For cultured abalone, these factors can significantly impact the production and profitability of the aquaculture operation. Wild abalone are frequently found in water temperatures ranging from 12 – 13 °C, the mean monthly temperature range on the west coast of South Africa⁹¹, and up to a maximum of 23 – 26 °C, which is the seawater temperature range for Haga Haga (Eastern Cape Wild Coast of South Africa, 60 km east of East London) during the peak of summer (around February) — where the species occurs naturally and where the most northerly based commercial abalone farm (Wild Coast Abalone) is located (Figure 58). Britz et al. (1997)⁹¹ demonstrated that a temperature range

⁸⁸ Britz, P.J., Hecht, T., Mangold, S., 1997. Effect of temperature on growth, feed consumption and nutritional indices of *Haliotis midae* fed a formulated diet. *Aquaculture* 152, 191–203.

of 12 – 20 °C is physiologically optimal for the production of *H. midae* (Table 13), with growth, feed conversion ratio, and protein efficiency ratio increasing from 12 to 20 °C and then declining sharply at temperatures above 20 °C. Abalone maintained at temperatures at and above 22 °C exhibit visible signs of stress and tend to “walkout” of the water and occupy the upper portion of the baskets — sides of the baskets above the water line and on top of the feeding plates. When farms experience warm seawater temperature events (>20 °C), it is recommended that a feed with a lower protein content is used. The typical protein content of feeds formulated for abalone are ca. 34 %. Green et al.⁸⁹ demonstrated a reduction in mortality for abalone fed formulated feeds with a 22 % protein content during elevated temperature. Feeding protein rich formulated feeds to abalone maintained at water temperatures exceeding 22 °C has been shown to be detrimental to the health of cultured abalone, leading to a condition known as “bloat” that is caused by an increase in microbial activity in the digestive tract of abalone⁹⁰. When water temperatures increase, the solubility of oxygen in the water column also decreases. Oxygen consumption rates and the relative energy consumed by individual abalone also increase⁹¹.

Table 13. Optimal environmental ranges for growth of the South African abalone *Haliotis midae* in land based partially recirculating systems.

|
Nutrients |
|--|---|---|--|--|
| 12 – 20°C | 30 – 35psu | >90% (7 – 8 mg. L ⁻¹) | 7.7 – 8.2 | FAN < 7.5 µg.L ⁻¹ |

⁸⁹ Green, A.J., Jones, C.L.W., Britz, P.J., 2011. The protein and energy requirements of farmed South African abalone *Haliotis midae* L. cultured at optimal and elevated water temperatures. *Aquaculture Research* 42(11), 1653–1663. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2109.2010.02759>.

⁹⁰ Macey, B.M., Coyne, V.E., 2005. Improved growth rate and disease resistance in farmed *Haliotis midae* through probiotic treatment. *Aquaculture* 245(1–4), 249–261. DOI:10.1016/j.aquaculture.2004.11.031.

⁹¹ Brand, M.J., 2023. *Ulva* as a functional feed: A practical investigation into the effects of *Ulva lacunculata* on the growth, consumption, health, and gut microbiota of the farmed abalone *Haliotis midae*. PhD, Department of Biological Sciences, University of Cape Town, Rondebosch 203pp.

5.2.2.4.2 Dissolved oxygen

Dissolved oxygen concentrations in abalone aquaculture systems in South Africa can fluctuate between 7.2 – 8.2 mg O₂/L and often depends on the distance of the animal or basket from the tank inlet and time of day⁹². *Haliotis midae* is a nocturnal feeder, with the bulk of the feed administered to the animals consumed between 18H00 and 24H00⁹³. During feeding, more oxygen is consumed and there is an increase in excretion of waste products (CO₂ and ammonia). Oxygen consumption of *H. midae* also increases linearly with increasing temperature⁹⁶. Other factors affecting the levels/utilisation of dissolved oxygen in the water are stocking density and oxygen supply (e.g., water flow rate, aeration efficiency, temperature-dependent oxygen solubility)⁹⁴. Vosloo and Vosloo (2013)⁹⁷ assessed organismal (rates of oxygen consumption and ammonia excretion) and cellular (heat shock protein expression, antioxidant enzymes) responses of juvenile and adult *H. midae* exposed to low (6.5 mg/L), intermediate (7.6 mg/L) or high (8.5 mg/L) oxygen levels and showed that juvenile and adult abalone reacted differently to changes in environmental oxygen levels. Juvenile *H. midae* exhibited an apparent insensitivity to moderate changes in ambient oxygen, supporting observations for juvenile *H. laevigata* exposed to 81 and 117 % of oxygen saturation⁹⁵. Conversely, adult *H. midae* had increased DNA damage under hypoxic and hyperoxic conditions. Under more extreme hypoxia condition (ca. 60 % saturation), decreased oxygen consumption rates can result in histopathological changes (e.g., necrosis and changes in mucus cell structure) in gills, as demonstrated for juvenile *H. laevigata*⁹⁸. Based on these findings, it is suggested that optimal oxygen levels for the cultivation of *H. midae* should be maintained between 7 – 8 mg/L (Table 13).

5.2.2.4.3 Salinity

The average salinity of seawater is around 35 g/L or practical salinity unit (psu), and Na⁺ and Cl⁻ ions are the two primary constituents. An optimal salinity range of 30-35 psu is recommended for *Haliotis midae* (Table 13). Since all abalone farms in South Africa are land-based pump ashore systems that utilize large volumes of seawater for their cultivation systems (typically replacing 100 % of the water in each tank at least once every two hours), the salinity on the farm is normally dependant on the

⁹² Yearsley R.D., 2008. Water quality, abalone growth and the potential for integrated mariculture on a South African abalone *Haliotis midae* L. farm. MSc thesis, Rhodes University, Grahamstown, South Africa 77pp.

⁹³ Sales, J., Britz, P. J., 2001. Research on abalone (*Haliotis midae* L.) cultivation in South Africa. *Aquaculture Research* 32:863-874.

⁹⁴ Vosloo A, Laas A., Vosloo D., 2013. Differential responses of juvenile and adult South African abalone (*Haliotis midae* Linnaeus) to low and high oxygen levels. *Comparative biochemistry and physiology. Part A, molecular and integrative physiology*, 164(1), 192-9. doi: 10.1016/j.cbpa.2012.09.002.

⁹⁵ Harris, J.O., B. Maguire, G., Edwards, S.J., Johns, D.R., 1999. Low dissolved oxygen reduces growth rate and oxygen consumption rate of juvenile greenlip abalone, *Haliotis laevigata* Donovan. *Aquaculture* 174, 265–278.

location of the abalone culture system, and the natural oceanic conditions, but do not vary significantly 35 ± 1 psu.

5.2.2.4.4 Ammonia

The primary nitrogenous by-product of protein metabolism excreted by abalone is ammonia. In aqueous solution ammonia exists in equilibrium between its un-ionized (NH_3) and ionized (NH_4) forms, with the sum of the two forms referred to as the total ammonia-nitrogen TAN ($\text{NH}_{3-4}\text{-N}$)⁹⁶. Of particular concern for farmers is the fraction of unionised ammonia (NH_3), expressed as free ammonia-nitrogen (FAN) in the water column⁹⁷, as it can more easily diffuse across cell-membranes and is hence regarded as more toxic⁹⁸. The ionization of ammonia is driven by other water quality variables including temperature, pH, and salinity, with increasing temperature and pH resulting in a higher proportion of ammonia existing as FAN⁹⁹. Reddy-Lopata et al.⁹⁹ investigated the toxicity of FAN to *H. midae* following an acute (36-hour) exposure and demonstrated that juveniles (10 – 15 mm) and adults (100 – 150 mm) differed in their susceptibility to NH_3 — with a FAN concentration of 9.8 $\mu\text{g/L}$ causing 50 % mortality in juveniles, whereas a higher concentration of 16.4 $\mu\text{g/L}$ caused 50 % mortality in adults. These authors further demonstrated that chronic (3-month) exposure of abalone to sub-lethal levels of FAN (7.4 $\mu\text{g/L}$; TAN of 0.56 mg/L) caused a 50 % reduction in growth of *H. midae* when compared with a control group (no ammonium chloride added). Conversely, chronic (\pm 2-month) exposure of the greenlip abalone *H. laevisgata* and green ormer *H. tuberculata* to FAN concentrations of 41 – 45 $\mu\text{g/L}$ resulted in only minor reductions in growth and less than 2 % mortality for both species^{100, 101}. Similarly, *H. midae* (80 g animals) exposed to ca. 60 $\mu\text{g/L}$ FAN for a 48-hour period resulted in no mortality¹⁰². Collectively, these studies indicate that exposure to high sub-lethal concentrations of ammonia retard growth of abalone and can lead to mortality. The general rule of thumb for aquarists is that FAN concentrations above 0.02 mg/L (20 $\mu\text{g/L}$ NH_3) may be toxic to fish. According to the WWF 'Abalone Aquaculture Dialogue Standards' (2010), TAN concentrations should not exceed 0.6 mg/L. Based on the results of the acute

⁹⁶ Bower, C.E., Bidwell, J.P., 1978. Ionization of Ammonia in Seawater: Effects of Temperature, pH, and Salinity. Journal Fish Research Board Canada 35, 1012–1016.

⁹⁷ De Prisco, J. 2019. An investigation of some key physico-chemical water quality parameters of an Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) system operating recirculation methodology in the Western Cape of South Africa. MSc in Applied Ocean Science, University of Cape Town, Rondebosch, South Africa 70pp.

⁹⁸ Yearsley R.D., 2008. Water quality, abalone growth and the potential for integrated mariculture on a South African abalone *Haliotis midae* L. farm. MSc thesis, Rhodes University, Grahamstown, South Africa 77pp.

⁹⁹ Reddy-Lopata, K., Auerswald, L. and Cook, P. (2006) 'Ammonia toxicity and its effect on the growth of the South African abalone *Haliotis midae* Linnaeus'. Aquaculture 261(2), 678–687. doi:10.1016/j.aquaculture.2006.06.020.

¹⁰⁰ Harris, J.O., Maguire, G.B., Handler, J.H., 1998. Effects of chronic exposure of greenlip abalone, *Haliotis laevisgata* Donovan, to high ammonia, nitrite, and low dissolved oxygen concentrations on gill and kidney structure. Journal of Shellfish Research 17, 683–687.

¹⁰¹ Basuyaux, O., Mathieu, M., 1999. Inorganic nitrogen and its effect on the growth of the abalone *Haliotis tuberculata* Linnaeus and the sea urchin *Paracentrotus lividus* Lamarck. Aquaculture 174, 95–107.

¹⁰² Yearsley R.D., 2008. Water quality, abalone growth and the potential for integrated mariculture on a South African abalone *Haliotis midae* L. farm. MSc thesis, Rhodes University, Grahamstown, South Africa 77pp.

and chronic ammonia toxicity and exposure tests conducted on *H. midae*, Reddy-Lopata et al.¹⁰³ suggest a safe FAN level for *H. midae* of below 7.5 µg/L (Table 13).

5.2.2.4.5 pH

The pH scale in a simplistic form is a measure of the amount of H⁺ ions in a solution and is a fundamental chemical characteristic of water. The pH of the seawater may become altered due to the production of H⁺ ions when CO₂ reacts with water to form a HCO₃⁻ molecule and a H⁺ ion¹⁰⁴. Common seawater pH is 8.0, but abalone change the carbonate system by excreting CO₂ during respiration, which combines with water molecules to form carbonic acid. This carbonic acid formed rapidly dissociates into HCO₃⁻ and H⁺, and the generation of H⁺ then decreases the pH¹⁰⁵. Exposure of juvenile greenlip abalone *Haliotis laevigata* and blacklip abalone *Haliotis rubra* to low levels of pH (ca. 7.16) was shown to cause enlarged tubules and lumen of the kidney and abnormalities in the gill structures of the exposed abalone¹⁰⁶. More recently, Lester¹⁰⁷ demonstrated that chronic exposure of *H. midae* to reduced pH (7.66 ± 0.07) led to a reduction in animal growth and shell strength. Low pH and the associated changes in bicarbonate chemistry can also adversely impact shell quality and the sale price for live abalone on export markets, by reducing shell strength and increasing shell breakage as well as increasing the number of “shiny” shells caused by decalcification¹⁰⁸. The optimal pH to produce *Haliotis midae* is 7.7 – 8.2 (Table 13). However, because of the diurnal feeding, oxygen consumption and excretory patterns of abalone on farms, these values can and will fluctuate and fall outside of these ranges for short periods of time.

5.2.2.5 Handling

Handling of abalone is generally kept to a minimum on farms as it can cause stress and even injuries and may adversely impact feed consumption rates as well as growth of the abalone when done too frequently. Abalone are generally only handled when tanks are cleaned, which requires temporary

¹⁰³ Reddy-Lopata, K., Auerswald, L. and Cook, P. (2006) 'Ammonia toxicity and its effect on the growth of the South African abalone *Haliotis midae* Linnaeus'. Aquaculture 261(2), 678–687. doi:10.1016/j.aquaculture.2006.06.020.

¹⁰⁴ Smith, R. G., 1988. Inorganic carbon transport in biological systems. Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology, Part B 90(4), 639–654. doi: 10.1016/0305-0491(88)90319-7.

¹⁰⁵ De Prisco, J. 2019. An investigation of some key physico-chemical water quality parameters of an Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) system operating recirculation methodology in the Western Cape of South Africa. MSc in Applied Ocean Science, University of Cape Town, Rondebosch, South Africa 70pp.

¹⁰⁶ Harris, J.O., Maguire, G.B., Edwards, S.J., Hindrum, S.M., 1999. Effect of pH on growth rate, oxygen consumption rate, and histopathology of gill and kidney tissue for juvenile greenlip abalone, *Haliotis laevigata* Donovan and blacklip abalone, *Haliotis rubra* Leach. Journal of Shellfish Research 18(2), 61-619.

¹⁰⁷ Lester, N.C., 2021. The interaction of acidification and warming on the South African abalone, *Haliotis midae*, and the potential for mitigation in aquaculture. PhD in Faculty of Science, Department of Biological Sciences, University of Cape Town, Rondebosch, South Africa 178pp.

¹⁰⁸ Lester, N.C., 2021. The interaction of acidification and warming on the South African abalone, *Haliotis midae*, and the potential for mitigation in aquaculture. PhD in Faculty of Science, Department of Biological Sciences, University of Cape Town, Rondebosch, South Africa 178pp.

removal of the baskets from the rearing tanks, and when the animals are graded and sorted, which requires longer term removal of baskets. Cleaning occurs 1 – 2 times per week and depends on the type of production system and locality of the farm. Farms utilising recirculation technologies (e.g., Buffeljags Abalone) and/or located in warmer areas (e.g., Wild Coast Abalone) tend to clean more frequently (twice per week), due to a higher accumulation of particulate organic matter (POM) and/or biofouling in the system. During cleaning of tanks, baskets are removed from tanks, briefly washed down with fresh seawater using a hose to remove debris attached to the baskets and dividers and immediately transferred to an open (clean) raceway tank close by if space is available on the farm — to minimise stress to the animals while the raceway tank is flushed and rinsed. Once all the baskets containing animals have been moved to a clean tank, the dirty tank is drained fully (by opening a valve at the base of the tanks that allows this water to be flushed to waste) and washed with a high-pressure hose. Cleaning of tanks is normally done on a rotational basis, so not all tanks are cleaned on the same day. Grading and sorting of abalone on the other hand only occurs once every 3 – 4 months on most abalone farms in South Africa. This process necessitates the removal of the abalone from the baskets and dividers, as the animals need to be graded, weighted, measured, and sorted — either by hand or using machinery. Animals are anaesthetized during this procedure to minimize stress and damage to the animals — specific procedures described below under section 5.2.2.6. Baskets are also more thoroughly cleaned, using an industrial high-pressure cleaner, during grading and sorting events.

5.2.2.6 Growth Monitoring

Growth is affected by many factors such as source of stock, density, type and amount of feed, water flow and quality, handling techniques, temperature, and the type of culture system. Regular monitoring of growth during each phase of the production cycle (e.g., hatchery, weaning, and grow-out; see Figure 55) is essential for tracking and managing the health of stock on the farm. During grow-out, most abalone farms in South Africa stock at an initial density of 10 kg/basket, and every 3 – 4 months abalone growth and stocking density is measured and recorded and the stocking densities in the baskets re-adjusted to 10 kg/basket. During grow-out, most abalone farms in South Africa stock at an initial density of 10 kg/basket, and every 3 – 4 months abalone growth and stocking density is measured and recorded and the stocking densities in the baskets re-adjusted to 10 kg/basket. This is done to optimise space allocated and management of feeding regimes to ensure maximum yields of the abalone produced. Basic procedure is as follows:

- The total basket weight (i.e., weight of basket with animals) is recorded, using an electronic balance, immediately after removing the basket from the raceway, to determine total animal weight gain in the basket over the growth period.

- Immediately after recording basket weight, the entire basket with animals is placed in a small tank/bucket containing anaesthetic — to assist with the removal of abalone from the basket walls and plate dividers. This is essential for abalone as they tend to pull down rapidly and tightly onto the surfaces of baskets and dividers when disturbed, which makes removal difficult¹⁰⁹. Mechanical removal of abalone without using anaesthetic is not practiced, as it is too time consuming, and can cause stress and injury to the animals. Anaesthetics commonly used on abalone farms include magnesium sulphate (effective concentrations are 4, 14 and 22 g/100mL for the size classes 5 ± 15, 20 ± 50 and 60 ± 90 mm shell length, respectively) or carbon dioxide: oxygen gas mixture (11.3 % : 88.7 %) delivered into the seawater at a rate of 2 L/min¹¹⁰.
- Once anaesthetised and detached from the substratum, the abalone are graded into size classes (small, medium, large, or rejects) and counted before being returned to their respective baskets containing fresh oxygenated seawater to recover. The density of abalone per basket is readjusted during grading to 10 kg/basket before being returned to their respective raceway. Grading is either done by hand or using automated size graders.
- When grading by hand, a subpopulation from each basket is often individually weighed (using an electronic balance to the nearest 0.01 g) and measured (using a caliper along the longest length of the shell to the nearest 0.01 mm) to obtain more detailed growth data, whereas most automated size graders can record individual animal weights and store this information electronically.

5.2.2.7 Predator Control and Treatment

Disease/pest agents that have been identified from the South African abalone *Haliotis midae* include a range of opportunistic *Vibrio* species, such as *V. anguillarum*¹¹¹ and *V. alginolyticus*¹¹²; the oomycetes *Haliphthoros milfordensis*¹¹³ and *Halioticida noduliformans*^{114, 115}; polychaetes, such as the sabellid

¹⁰⁹ Sales, J., Britz, P. J., 2001. Research on abalone (*Haliotis midae* L.) cultivation in South Africa. *Aquaculture Research* 32, 863-874.

¹¹⁰ White, H.I., 1995. Anaesthesia in abalone, *Haliotis midae*. MSc thesis, Rhodes University, Grahamstown, South Africa 97pp.

¹¹¹ Macey, B.M., Coyne, V.E., 2005. Improved growth rate and disease resistance in farmed *Haliotis midae* through probiotic treatment. *Aquaculture* 245(1–4), 249–261. DOI:10.1016/j.aquaculture.2004.11.031.

¹¹² Dixon, M.G., Hecht, T., Brandt, C.R., 1991. Identification and treatment of a *Clostridium* and *Vibrio* infection in South African abalone, *Haliotis midae* L. *Journal of Fish Diseases* 14, 693–695.

¹¹³ Hatai, K., 1982. On the fungus *Haliphthoros milfordensis* isolated from temporarily held abalone (*Haliotis sieboldii*). *Fish Pathology* 17, 199–204.

¹¹⁴ Macey, B.M., Christison, K.W., Mouton, A., 2011. *Halioticida noduliformans* isolated from cultured abalone (*Haliotis midae*) in South Africa. *Aquaculture* 315, 187–195.

¹¹⁵ Greeff, M.R., Christison, K.W., Macey, B.M., 2012. Development and preliminary evaluation of a real-time PCR assay for *Halioticida noduliformans* in abalone tissues. *Diseases of Aquatic Organisms* 99, 103–117.

worm *Terebrasabella heterouncinata*^{116, 117} and several *Boccardia* and *Diploydora* spp.¹¹⁸; a sessile peritrichous ciliate (*Mantoscyphidia midae*)¹¹⁹; as well as gut and digestive gland protozoa¹²⁰.

None of the above-mentioned parasites, except for *H. noduliformans*, have caused large scale mortalities on commercial abalone farms (regarded as production diseases that do not require reporting to the WOA), but can adversely impact production, sales and ultimately farm profits. Infestations with these parasites are routinely monitored, during grading and cleaning events on the farm (as described above) through visual observation of shells (worm tunnels in shells, broken shells, lack of new ridges, shiny shells) and controlled through strict adherence to biosecurity, helping to limit spread of the parasite within and between facilities, and good husbandry/sanitation practices, particularly on farms utilizing formulated feed — which has been shown to increase prevalence of worms as uneaten feed provides a food source for the worms. Abalone tubercle mycosis in South Africa is the most recent disease diagnosed from *H. midae* in 2006 and caused large scale mortalities on at least three commercial farms¹²¹. However, it is currently regarded as a production disease and effective containment has been achieved by destocking of affected raceways/facilities, sterilization of equipment, removal, and decontamination of biological filter material (when present) and adherence to suitable fallowing periods. Moreover, strict adherence to biosecurity, optimal husbandry practices, and early detection and subsequent management are regarded as effective means to reduce the occurrence of this pathogen, as is the case for other production diseases.

5.2.2.8 Harvesting

Most abalone farms in South African focus on producing abalone which are ca. 100 – 140 mm in size, which take approximately 4 – 5 years to produce. Cultured abalone are a premium seafood delicacy that is mainly consumed in the Far East, and traded as either live, frozen, dried, or canned products. Prices for these products, produced by South Africa abalone farms, fetch on average US\$ 30-50/kg on Asian markets. When the abalone are ready for sale, they are moved to the processing facility on the farm, if the farm has its own fish processing establishment (FPE), or to the FPE nearest to the farm —

¹¹⁶ Gray, M.S., Kaiser, H., 2007. Settlement pattern and survival of a shell-infesting sabellid polychaete, *Terebrasabella heterouncinata*, on South African abalone, *Haliotis midae*, fed two diets. African Journal of Aquatic Science 32, 275–279.

¹¹⁷ Ruck, K.R., Cook, P.A., 1998. Sabellid infestations in the shells of South African molluscs: implications for abalone mariculture. Journal of Shellfish Research 17, 693–699.

¹¹⁸ Boonzaaier, M., Neethling, S., Mouton, A., Simon, C.A., 2014. Polydorid polychaetes (Polychaeta: Spionidae) on farmed and wild abalone (*Haliotis midae*) in South Africa - an epidemiological survey. African Journal of Marine Science Submitted:21.

¹¹⁹ Botes, H., 1999. *Sessiline ciliophorans* associated with *Haliotis* species (Mollusca: Archaeogastropoda) from the south coast of South Africa. University of the Free State 229pp.

¹²⁰ Mouton, A., Gummow, B., 2011. The occurrence of gut associated parasites in the South African abalone, *Haliotis midae*, in Western Cape aquaculture facilities. Aquaculture 313, 1–6.

¹²¹ Macey, B.M., Christison, K.W., Mouton, A., 2011. *Halioticida noduliformans* isolated from cultured abalone (*Haliotis midae*) in South Africa. Aquaculture 315, 187–195.

where the abalone are processed for live export or into frozen, canned, or dried products. When transporting live abalone, transit times should be kept to a minimum and should not exceed 36-hours¹²². Live abalone for long shipments (e.g., South African to China) are generally packaged into Styrofoam boxes that contain ice packs, to maintain a cool temperature during transit, as well as moist foam (to maintain a humid environment), and the boxes are filled with oxygen immediately prior to sealing and shipment. It is also recommended to starve and purge animals for 2 – 3 days prior to transportation to reduce stress and bloating (due to microbial activity in the digestive tract) of abalone and minimise the production of faecal matter/waste during transport¹²⁵. Temperature fluctuations during long shipments should also be kept to a minimum to avoid stress and mortality. Harvested animals are treated in a similar manner to animals during grading and sorting, with baskets containing abalone initially placed in a small tank containing anaesthetic to assist with the removal of abalone from the basket walls and plate dividers, which minimizes stress and damage to animals. Abalone are also sorted according to size prior to packing (for live transport) as well as for frozen products, canning or drying (Figure 59).

Figure 59. Typical products from South African abalone farms, including (a) live, (b) frozen, (c) canned, and (d) dried.

¹²² Sales, J., Britz, P. J., 2001. Research on abalone (*Haliotis midae* L.) cultivation in South Africa. *Aquaculture Research* 32, 863-874.

5.2.3 Sea urchin (*Tripneustes gratilla*)

5.2.3.1 Sea Urchin Distribution, Life Cycle and Production Cycle

The sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla* occurs globally in tropical and subtropical regions, where broodstock animals can be collected from deep or shallow ocean floors along its distribution range (Figure 60) but are most abundant at 2 – 15 m offshore. Sea urchin life cycles are characterised by two developmental stages: a free-swimming larval phase, and a benthic juvenile and adult phase¹²³ (Figure 61). Given that the sea urchin life cycle has been closed for aquaculture production^{124,125}, careful consideration should be given to the different needs of the sea urchins at the respective phases of their life cycles. Briefly, the sea urchin larval phase starts after a fertilised egg hatches and a prism-shaped larva form. For the first seven days of development, *T. gratilla* have access to the nutrients that were present in the egg (maternal reserves)^{126,127}, but larvae will require active feeding for the duration of larval rearing (25 – 40 days) with microalgal feeds. The larva will go through various larval phases, first developing four arms after approximately 5 days, which will be followed by an eight-armed phase after 20 days. During larval development the larvae remain in the water column, where they feed on microalgae to fuel this development. At the end of larval rearing, larvae will undergo metamorphosis into benthic juveniles upon exposure to settlement cues¹²⁸. Juvenile sea urchins take approximately three weeks to develop the structures of an adult sea urchin and is considered mature after one year (Figure 61).

¹²³ Toha, A.H.A., Sumitro, S.B., Hakim, L., Widodo, N., Binur, R., Suhaemi., & Anggoro, A.W., 2017. Review: Biology of the commercially used sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Echinoidea: Echinodermata). *Ocean Life* 1, 1–10.

¹²⁴ Scholtz, R., Bolton, J.J., & Macey, B.M., 2013. Effects of different microalgal feeds and their influence on larval development in the white-spined sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla*. *African Journal of Marine Science* 3537–41.

¹²⁵ Cyrus, M.D., Bolton, J.J., & Macey, B.M., 2015. The role of green seaweed *Ulva* as a dietary supplement for full life-cycle grow-out of *Tripneustes gratilla*. *Aquaculture* 446, 187–197.

¹²⁶ Brink-Hull, M., Cyrus, M.D., Macey, B.M., Rhode, C., Hull, K.L., & Roodt-Wilding, R., 2022. Dietary effects on the reproductive performance of the sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla* I: Implications for broodstock conditioning. *Aquaculture*, 552.

¹²⁷ Byrne, M., Prowse, T.A.A., Sewell, M.A., Dworjanyn, S., Williamson, J.E., & Vaitilingon, D., 2008. Maternal provisioning for larvae and larval provisioning for juveniles in the toxopneustid sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla*. *Marine Biology* 155, 473–482.

¹²⁸ Dworjanyn, S.A., & Pirozzi, I., 2008. Induction of settlement in the sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla* by macroalgae, biofilms, and conspecifics: a role for bacteria? *Aquaculture* 274, 268–274.

Figure 60. *Tripneustes gratilla* distribution along tropical and subtropical regions (Adapted from Toha et al., 2017).

Figure 61. *Tripneustes gratilla* life cycle separated into the free-swimming larval phase, and benthic juvenile and adult phase as described in Toha et al. 2017. m: minutes, d: days, w: weeks.

Sea urchin production is therefore divided into (i) a hatchery phase where free-swimming larvae are raised until they undergo metamorphosis and (ii) a grow-out phase where sea urchins are fed optimal

diets for growth, and gonads are developed until suitable for market (Figure 61). In the hatchery, broodstock animals need to be kept and maintained to enable spawning and the collection of gametes (eggs and sperm). Eggs and sperm are combined to fertilise the eggs taking 1 – 2 days until larvae hatch (Figure 61). Once hatched, larvae are transferred and raised in a controlled hatchery environment until deemed ready for settlement and metamorphosis. In the hatchery, a day:night cycle of 12h:12h should be maintained and water quality should be preserved using a protein skimmer, bio-filter, sand-filter and 100 µm filter bags^{129,127}. Good incoming water quality is needed to maintain sea urchin larvae, as well as during grow-out, and therefore a land-based site should preferably be situated close to the sea. The juveniles are grown for roughly a month and fed the green seaweed *Ulva*, whereafter a land-based sea urchin-*Ulva* IMTA grow-out system can be stocked when sea urchins that have a diameter of approximately 10 mm. Sea urchins are grown under natural light conditions during grow-out. When the urchins are grown in integrated systems with *Ulva*, the light conditions should be carefully considered to allow for optimal access to light and growth of the *Ulva* in the integrated system. Seawater temperature is an important criterion for this sea urchin species, which grows optimally at 24 – 28 °C^{128,130,131}, but can tolerate temperatures up to 32 °C. These temperature conditions mean that the site ideally needs to be located where seawater is warmer or a heat pump (which is costly to run) needs to be used to warm the water. The species/strain of *Ulva* grown in the IMTA system also needs to be compatible with the rearing temperature of the sea urchins. Sea urchin production takes approximately one year from the larval stage to producing sea urchins that are ready for market (Figure 62). It should be noted that production methods for *T. gratilla* are not limited to the protocols outlined in this manual and other approaches have also proved successful¹¹³, particularly with regards to the diet used at hatchery and grow-out stage^{127,128}.

¹²⁹ Brink-Hull, M., Cyrus, M.D., Macey, B.M., Rhode, C., Hull, K.L., & Roodt-Wilding, R., 2022. Dietary effects on the reproductive performance of the sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla* II: Implications for offspring performance. *Aquaculture*, 553.

¹³⁰ Mos, B., Dworjanyn, S.A., Cowden, K.L., 2012. Potential for the commercial culture of the tropical sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla* in Australia. Rural industries research and development corporation (RIRDC) publication no: 12/052.

¹³¹ Mos, B., Dworjanyn, S., 2020. Boosting the productivity of sea urchin aquaculture using advanced culture protocols and dietary intervention. *AgriFutures Australia* publication no: 21-143.

Figure 62. Land-based sea urchin production cycle consisting of a ca. 1-3 month hatchery phase followed by a 9-12 month grow-out phase. ©UCT & DFFE.

5.2.3.2 Broodstock Daily/Routine Operations

The daily operations will differ depending on production stage, i.e. hatchery vs. grow-out. In the hatchery, wild collected *Triploneustes gratilla* broodstock (80 – 150mm test diameter) that have been sexed by inducing spawning after collection, can be maintained in small individual tanks (ca. 11 L) connected to a heated (24 – 25 °C) recirculating aquaculture seawater system (RAS). The daily system water replacement rate should be at least 30 % of the system volume, which is achieved by the addition of fresh seawater filtered to 1 µm. Each 11 L broodstock tank must be supplied with aeration and heated (24 – 25 °C) filtered (100 µm) seawater at a water exchange rate of ca. 300 – 360 tank volumes per day. This high flow rate ensures optimal water quality and health of the animals in the event of spawning (ensures gametes are flushed rapidly, thereby mitigating against risk of poor water quality). Broodstock animals should be maintained on conditioning diets for a minimum of three months prior to spawning. Wild broodstock are spawned on a rotational basis in laboratory setting.

5.2.3.3 Broodstock Conditioning (Feeding)

Feeding regimes will largely depend on the phase of production for sea urchins. Sea urchin broodstock can be conditioned on a mixed diet of seaweeds (*Ecklonia maxima* and *Ulva lacunculata*). Animals should be fed every second day to apparent satiation, with each seaweed species being alternated weekly. At each feeding, uneaten food is removed, and the tanks cleaned before adding fresh feed. The feeds

used for broodstock conditioning impact larval growth, development and survival¹¹⁰ and the inclusion of seaweeds in broodstock conditioning feeding regimes has been found to benefit gametogenesis and egg quality¹²⁸. These benefits stem from the maternal nutrients invested in the eggs that will be used to fuel the early larval developmental stages, prior to the development of feeding structures and a digestive tract.

5.2.3.4 Broodstock Spawning

Supplies and equipment needed:

- Autoclaved 2M potassium chloride (KCl) solution (14.92 g of KCl in 100 mL of sterile distilled water)
- 0.2 µm filtered autoclaved seawater maintained at 24 – 25 °C
- 1 mL syringes
- 26G×5/8" (0.45 × 16 mm) needles
- 4000 mL autoclaved glass beakers
- 1000 mL autoclaved glass beakers
- 500 mL autoclaved glass Erlenmeyer flasks – Wide neck
- 15 mL sample tubes
- Test tube rack to hold 15 mL tubes
- 100 µm sieve
- 60 µm sieve
- 37 µm sieve
- 500 mL long nozzle squeeze bottle (2)
- 100 µL pipette with tips
- Haemocytometer and cover slip for quantifying sperm
- Bogorov tray for egg quantification
- Compound Microscope (400× magnification)
- Dissecting Microscope (40× magnification)
- Cavity slides
- 1000 µL pipette with tips
- 100 µL pipette with tips
- Hatching tanks (number & size dependent on larval requirements)

Sea urchin spawning is induced by carefully placing a sea urchin aboral side down on a wide-necked Erlenmeyer flask (Figure 63) filled to the brim with 0.22 µm filtered seawater (25 °C) and injecting 0.5 mL 2M KCl into the peristomial membrane (Figure 64). Care should be taken to avoid injecting the

gonad or other tissues/organs. However, this is not the only method for spawning induction and other methods including thermal, saline or mechanical shock^{132,133} have also been reported.

Figure 63. Sea urchins placed aboral side down to collect gametes in 500 mL flask. ©M. Brink-Hull.

Figure 64. Sea urchin aboral side down showing injection site (peristomial membrane). ©M. Cyrus.

When gamete release starts, the below steps can be followed:

1. When gamete release begins, note the time, and ensure that gametes are entering the Erlenmeyer flask and not spilling out. Separate the sexes for ease of monitoring:

¹³² Gago, J.M., Luis, O.J., Repolho, T.R., 2009. Fatty acid nutritional quality of sea urchin *Paracentrotus lividus* (Lamarck 1816) eggs and endotrophic larvae: relevance for feeding of marine larval fish. *Aquaculture Nutrition* 15, 379.

¹³³ Osanai, K., 1975. Handling Japanese sea urchins and their embryos. In: Czihak, G. (Ed.), *The Sea Urchin Embryo. Biochemistry and Morphogenesis*, Springer Verlag, Berlin, pp 26–40.

- Males will release sperm, which is distinguishable by its milky white colour and suspended distribution in the flask (Figure 65A).
- Females will release eggs, which are generally orange to yellow in colour, and will sink in clumps to the bottom of the flask (Figure 65B).

Figure 65. Male sea urchin (left) releasing sperm and female sea urchin (right) releasing eggs. ©M. Cyrus.

2. During spawning, regularly pour small amounts of filtered 24°C seawater over the urchins to ensure they remain moist and ensure the flask is completely full and gonadal pores covered.
3. If an urchin does not start to produce gametes after 5 min, gently remove the urchin from the top of the flask and swirl or invert it gently, then place it back on the flask. If an urchin still does not initiate spawning, inject the remaining 0.5mL KCl solution. If the urchin still does not spawn after an additional 5min, remove the urchin and place it back in its respective broodstock holding tank.
4. Once an urchin has completed gamete release (Figure 66), remove the urchin and place it back into its respective labelled tank for recovery, ensuring high water turnover rates in case of additional gamete release during recovery.

Figure 66. Spawned sea urchins, where eggs and sperm can be seen on the bottom of the 500 mL flasks (front row: females; back row: males). ©M. Brink-Hull.

5. Inspect the collected gametes for general quality, urchins that produce low amounts of sperm or eggs should be discarded as gonads can be assumed immature.
6. Sperm from individual males should be passed through a 60 μm screen to remove unwanted particulates and collected in individual marked 1000 mL beakers. Samples of the individual urchin's sperm should be collected in 15 mL sample tubes and labelled for quality assessments.
7. Sperm samples should be assessed under a compound microscope at 400 \times magnification to confirm good motility.
8. After confirmation of sperm motility, equal quantities from up to five males should be combined in a single 4000 mL beaker and stored until used (within 1 h). Sperm from animals that do not exhibit efficient motility should be discarded and not combined with other male sperm. Sperm from individual males can be kept separate and individual crosses for each male and female conducted to avoid parental skews (one male dominating a spawning event).
9. Invert tubes gently to ensure even distribution of gametes before loading onto a haemocytometer. Sperm concentration of the mixed (or individual) male(s) should be determined using a haemocytometer at 400 \times magnification to calculate the concentration per mL determined, dilute (in seawater) to 1000 \times or 10,000 \times if necessary. Follow the manufacturer's instructions to use the haemocytometer and use the below as a guide:
 - a. Count all, or a representative sample, of the cells in the grid of 16 squares.
 - b. In the event of cells on lines --- count cells on right and lower lines only.
 - c. Calculations:

$$\frac{\text{Number of cells}}{\text{mL}} = \frac{\left(n \times \frac{16 \text{ Squares}}{\# \text{ of Squares Counted}} \right)}{0.1 \text{ mm}^3} \times \frac{10^3 \text{ mm}^3}{\text{mL}} \times \text{dilution factor}$$

$$\frac{\text{Number of cells}}{\text{mL}} = \frac{\left(n \times \frac{16 \text{ Squares}}{\# \text{ of Squares Counted}} \right)}{0.1 \text{ mm}^3} \times \frac{10^3 \text{ mm}^3}{\text{mL}} \times \text{dilution factor}$$

where n = total number of cells counted count. The dilution factor part of the equation is a reminder to account for any dilution of your sample prior to counting.

10. Eggs from individual females should be filtered through a 100 µm screen to remove unwanted particulates and while transferring them to individual marked 1000 mL beakers. Samples of the individual urchin's eggs should be collected in a 15 mL sample tube and labelled for quality assessments.
11. Egg samples should be assessed under a microscope for each spawned female at 100× magnification. Egg health can be confirmed by the appearance of a uniform round shape with full and uniform internal texture. Only select females that produced eggs with a healthy appearance and discard eggs from individuals that are not.
12. Egg concentration for each spawned urchin should be determined by counting the number of eggs per mL using a Bogorov tray under a dissecting microscope at 30× magnification, dilute to 10× or 100× if necessary, prior to counting. Invert tubes gently to ensure even distribution of gametes before loading the Bogorov tray. Keep eggs separate until fertilisation.
13. For each urchin spawned, the volume of water and egg concentration per mL is used to calculate the total egg number. Use this value to determine the amount of sperm required for fertilisation at a ratio of 100:1 (sperm:eggs). Amount of sperm to add = [(egg concentration per mL x total volume of eggs in mL) x 100]/amount of sperm per mL]. Mix sperm into individual 1000 mL beakers containing individually spawned urchin eggs, stir gently and allow to stand for 10 min.
14. Confirm fertilisation success for each female by placing a drop of eggs onto a cavity slide and observing it under the microscope at 100× magnification. A fertilisation membrane (Figure 67) should be present on at least 95 % of the eggs, if found to be lower than this, discard these eggs.

Figure 67. Unfertilised and fertilised sea urchin eggs. ©M. Cyrus.

After fertilisation is confirmed, the below steps can be followed:

- 1.) The eggs should be rinsed with 0.22 μm filtered seawater to remove excess sperm on a 60 μm sieve, as they are roughly 80 μm in diameter and will remain on the sieve while the excess sperm is washed away.
- 2.) The collected fertilised eggs can be placed in tanks (ca. 90 L tank required for fertilised eggs from two females) containing 0.22 μm filtered seawater pre-heated to 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and supplied with fine aeration (Figure 68).

Figure 68. Sea urchin egg hatching containers fitted with fine aeration and kept at 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. ©B. Macey.

- 3.) The eggs should hatch in 24 – 48 h, where after prism shaped larvae (Figure 69a) will be visible when viewing larvae under a microscope.

Figure 69. Larval stages of *Tripneustes gratilla* (a) day 2, prism; (b) day 3, 2-arm stage; (c) day 6, 4-arm stage; (d) day 10, 6-arm stage; (e) day 18; 8-arm stage and (f) day 25, late 8-arm stage. ©M. Cyrus.

5.2.3.5 Sea Urchin Larval System Setup and Stocking

Larval rearing can be done using a static or flow-through system in either flat-bottom or conical tanks (Figure 70). For a static system, no banjo sieves are needed in tanks and water replacements should be done twice a week or as needed.

Figure 70. Larval rearing system with (A) flat-bottom or (B, C) conical shape. ©B. Macey & M. Brink-Hull.

Larval rearing system consists of:

- 8 × UV filters (55 W)
- Fine sand filter (3-Bag)
- 1 µm filter
- Bio-filter
- Protein skimmer
- Heat-pump
- Conical or flat rearing tanks
- 300 W rod heater per tank
- Airstone per tank or glass rods (0.5 cm diameter)
- 120 µm Banjo sieve per tank
- 200 µm Banjo sieve per tank
- 4000 mL glass beakers (4)

- 1000 mL glass beakers
- 15 mL sample tubes per tank
- Test tube rack
- 1000 μ L pipette with tips
- 100 μ L pipette with tips
- Haemocytometer and cover slips
- Bogorov tray
- Cavity slides
- Dissecting microscope (40x magnification)

Larval system stocking protocol:

1. After larval hatching (24 – 48 hours post-fertilisation), hatching tanks should be gently cleaned of dead larvae (pink/red patches) that have accumulated on the bottom by siphoning with a narrow diameter pipe. This is done to reduce the transfer of dead larvae and subsequent bacterial growth associated with them.
2. Homogenous water samples from each hatching tank should be collected and stored in marked 15 mL sample tubes for larval counting.
3. Larval concentration (larvae/mL) should be calculated by using the dissecting microscope at 40X magnification to count the number of larvae in 1mL aliquots within the Bogorov tray. Samples may need to be diluted 10x or 100x to accurately count the larvae.
4. Conical rearing tanks fitted with 120 μ m Banjo sieves on the outflows (in order to retain larvae within the tank during water exchanges) should be prepared with filtered heated seawater (\sim 25 $^{\circ}$ C) from the rearing system and a 300 W rod heater to maintain temperature (\sim 25 $^{\circ}$ C). The banjo sieves should be cleaned twice a week or when needed.
5. Aeration should be provided at all times, with 0.20 μ m filters attached to each tank's airline. Although fine aeration (airstones) can be used in larval rearing tanks, a diagonal thin glass rod (0.5 – 1 cm wide) attached to aeration tubing is a good strategy for maintaining optimal water circulation in the tank. A tap fitting on the aeration tubing should be used to maintain slow aeration.
6. Photoperiod is maintained on a 12:12hr light:dark cycle.
7. Check individual tank temperatures before transferring larvae into them.
8. Healthy larvae should then be transferred from the hatching tanks to the prepared conical rearing tanks using the 4000mL beakers and stocked at a density of approximately 5 larvae/mL. Lower starting stocking densities of 1 larvae/mL can help improve larval access to feed.

9. If a flow-through system is used, the bottom of the conical larval rearing tanks should be briefly flushed every second day and the sides of the cone siphoned carefully using a long glass rod with a diameter of 0.5 – 1 cm, to remove dead larvae and uneaten food at the bottom of the tanks. If a static system is used, a full tank replacement needs to be done twice a week by siphoning into a 100 – 150 µm sieve in a container that has already been filled with seawater at 25 °C. Open tap at the bottom of the tank to slowly drain water as the siphoning progresses. Thereafter the original tank that larvae were kept in should be thoroughly cleaned and refilled with fresh seawater at 25 °C before returning larvae. Be sure to gently rinse the sieve to ensure that no larvae were left on the sieve.

5.2.3.6 Sea Urchin Larval Rearing

Routine hatchery tasks include water quality monitoring (temperature, aeration, cleanliness and system functionality), tank water replacements (biweekly or as needed), daily assessment of larval development and larval counting to assess stocking density. Daily larval feeding requires continuous microalgal feed preparation, which requires growing microalgal cultures using F2-media (and sodium-metasilicate where appropriate), and quantification of microalgal cells prior to feeding the sea urchin larvae. Lastly, while raising larvae, which takes ca. 25 – 40 days, containers with settlement substrates need to be prepared and maintained until larvae are deemed competent for settlement.

Larval feeding can be done in two ways: (i) a gradual increase in the number of microalgal cells throughout the larval rearing period as described in steps 8 – 11, or (ii) feeding at a constant 10 000 cells/mL tank volume from day 2 of larval rearing by starting with a mixed diet of *Isochrysis* and *Chaetoceros* at 5000 cells/mL each, and including *Rhodomonas* towards day 7 of larval rearing and feeding approximately 3400 cells/mL of each microalgal feed (*Isochrysis*, *Chaetoceros*, *Rhodomonas*).

Larval rearing procedure:

1. After 2 days of static water flow and no feeding, the larvae are fed on a diet of *Isochrysis galbana* (or *Tisochrysis lutea*) at a ratio of 1000 cells/mL for 2 days. If running as a flow-through system for the remainder of the larval rearing period, tanks are supplied with fresh seawater from the rearing system during the night cycle at a replacement rate of 70 % per day.
2. Larval counts should be conducted every 2nd day during the rearing period to guide feeding rates.
3. On day 5, the larvae are fed an equal portion diet of *Isochrysis galbana* (or *Tisochrysis lutea*) and *Chaetoceros muelleri* at a ratio of 2000 cells/mL. Feeding volume is increase daily by 500 cells/larvae for the next 4 days. Increase feeding rates if larvae show signs of insufficient feeding i.e. skeleton protruding from arms.

4. On day 10, larvae are fed an equal portion diet of *Isochrysis galbana* (or *Tisochrysis lutea*), *Chaetoceros muelleri* and *Rhodomonas salina* at a ratio of 6000 cells/larvae. This is increased daily by 1000 cells/mL up until a maximum feeding rate of 10,000 cells/mL.
5. If making use of a flow-through system: once larvae reach a size greater than 200 μm , the 120 μm Banjo sieves can be replaced with 200 μm sieves to reduce the blockage of the sieves by flushed algae.
6. Full water tank replacements should be performed twice a week in static systems but can be used in flow-through systems to improve rearing success. This is done by draining the contents of the tank into a 100 – 200 μm bucket sieve (sieve size depending on larval sizes) and collecting the concentrated larvae, which are transferred to a clean tank.
7. Larvae are reared as described above for approximately 30 days until considered competent to settle. However, it should be noted that larval rearing can continue for as long as 40 days. Larvae are deemed competent for settlement when the rudiment (large black structure in the centre of the larva in Figure 71A) is larger than 400 μm and/or when pedicellariae (tube feet) are observed. Larvae are then drained from the rearing tanks into a 200 μm sieve and concentrated for transfer to prepared settlement tanks (see preparation guide below).

Figure 71. Sea urchin larva (A, B) competent for settlement after 35 days of larval rearing and (C, D) after metamorphosis. ©M. Brink-Hull & B. Macey.

8. When these features are observed, larvae should be moved to a container pre-prepared with a settlement substrate as described above. Settlement success is improved by adding small amounts of *Ulva* (cut to small pieces in a blender).

5.2.3.7 Microalgal Feed and Settlement Substrate Preparation

Standard protocols to grow microalgae are available^{134,135} and should be referred to in conjunction with the below instructions.

Equipment needed:

- Algal stocks: *Isochrysis/Tisochrysis*, *Chaetoceros*, *Rhodomonas*
- Algal tubes/bags to bulk up microalgae
- F2 growth media (check expiry dates) at a concentration of 100 g/L
- Sodium metasilicate at a concentration of 40 g/L
- Measuring cylinder
- Siphon
- Haemocytometer
- Dissecting Microscope (40x magnification)
- Settlement tanks
- Settlement substrates (options): *Cocconeis*, *Ulvella*, *Nitzschia*

Microalgal feeds need to be prepared as described below prior to starting larval rearing to allow enough time for feeds to reach high cell concentrations (ca. 7 million cells/mL).

Microalgal feed preparation protocol:

1. Microalgal cultures (*Isochrysis*, *Chaetoceros*, and *Rhodomonas*) should be continuously bulked up in 0.22 µm filtered seawater from stocks (Figure 72). Algal stocks should be used to first culture 2L microalgae in autoclaved 0.22 µm filtered seawater using 150 mL of stock culture and F2 media at a concentration of 1 mL/L for all microalgal cultures, and 1 mL/L sodium metasilicate for *Chaetoceros*. Each bottle is fitted with aeration (glass tubing) and continuous light.
2. After 5 – 7 days, or when microalgal density has noticeably increased (checked with haemocytometer), the 2L bottles can be used to seed larger volumes of 50 – 70 L of 0.22 µm filtered seawater (Figure 72). To avoid contamination, the growth tubes/bags should be filled with 0.22 µm filtered seawater 24h before adding microalgae, supplied with aeration (glass rod) and should be treated with chlorine dioxide (e-oxide LQ).

¹³⁴ Helm, M., Bourne, N., 2004. Hatchery culture of bivalves. A practical manual. FAO Fisheries Technical Paper 471. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. Rome, 2004.

¹³⁵ Jaramillo, J.C., 1996. Microalgae Culture Protocol. Aquaculture Division Harbor Branch Oceanographic Institution Incorporated.

Figure 72. Microalgal feed including (A) *Rhodomonas*, *Chaetoceros* and *Isochrysis*, and (B) bulked up *Chaetoceros* used to feed sea urchin larvae. ©M. Brink-Hull & B. Macey.

3. Once microalgae have been added to the larger volumes, F2 media and/or sodium metasilicate should be added at 1 mL/L.
4. Settlement substrates should be prepared at the start of larval rearing or earlier (e.g. *Ulvela*). Diatoms such as *Cocconeis* and *Nitzschia* should be bulked up from stock cultures as described in step 2, with the addition of 1 mL/L F2 media and 1 mL/L metasilicate. Once noticeable growth is observed (5 – 7 days), the 2 L bottles can be used to seed a settlement container [90 L settlement containers (L x W x H: 80 x 42 x 26 cm)]. To avoid contamination, the settlement tanks should be filled with 0.22 µm filtered seawater 24h before adding microalgae, supplied with aeration and should be treated with chlorine dioxide (e-oxide LQ).
5. The settlement tanks can also be fitted with plastic racks to coat a higher surface area with the settlement substrate. To effectively coat racks, the racks should be turned on a weekly basis for improved access to light.
6. Once microalgae have been added, these tanks should be supplied with constant light, fine aeration and 1 mL/L F2 media and 1 mL/L metasilicate.
7. Larval metamorphosis is dependent on settlement cues, one of which is the presence of a suitable settlement substrate. *Ulvela* settlement tanks show a high settlement success rate for sea urchins but requires sporulation to seed settlement tanks¹³⁶. See the protocol outlined in Hannon et al. (2014) for more details.

¹³⁶ Hannon, C., Officer, R.A., Le Dorven, J., Chamberlain, J., 2014. Culture methods of live algal feeds for European aquaculture: optimising culture conditions for *Ulvela lens*. *Aquaculture International* 22, 1813–1822.

5.2.3.8 Sea Urchin Deplating and Juvenile Growth

After settlement (metamorphosis) juvenile sea urchins are grown in the settlement troughs for ca. 1 month, while adding small amounts of the green seaweed *Ulva*. During this time, daily water quality assessments and cleaning is performed to remove faecal matter. Juvenile sea urchins are moved to grow-out tanks when they reach ca. 5 – 10 cm and are fed only *Ulva* for the first month of grow-out, whereafter kelp (*Ecklonia maxima*) can also be fed (Figure 73).

Figure 73. (A, B) Juvenile sea urchins on settlement plates, (C) feeding on *Ulva* after deplating and (D) feeding on *Ulva* and kelp for early grow-out stages (1-2 months). ©B. Macey.

5.2.3.9 Sea Urchin Grow-out Daily Activities

When urchins are grown in land-based integrated systems where the sea urchin effluent water is linked to a paddle-raceway with *Ulva*, as for the ASTRAL IMTA lab South Africa, the daily activities include animal health and biosecurity assessments, tank cleaning to remove uneaten feed, feeding, system functionality (aeration, water flow, filters) assessments, system maintenance (when required), draining and cleaning *Ulva* paddle-raceway (when required). The *Ulva* required for feed is harvested daily and the raceways are monitored to ensure optimal functionality. The *Ulva* system is fully drained and cleaned every 2 – 3 months and restocked. Size grading is particularly important during early grow-out stages as sea urchin growth is fast at this stage and a high degree of variation in growth is generally observed, which if left unmonitored/ungraded can lead to cannibalism by the larger animals, as well as limited access to feed for the smaller ones. During grading, animals that are noticeably larger or smaller are moved into new baskets with an optimal basket depth of 15 cm to ensure optimal access to feed¹⁴³. The optimal stocking density for *T. gratilla* is estimated at a density of ca. 20 % basket internal surface coverage or 6 – 8 kg/m², with limited differences in animal performance¹³⁷. This subtropical/tropical sea urchin takes approximately 9 – 12 months from settlement to reach a marketable

¹³⁷ De Vos, B.C., Cyrus, M.D., Bolton, J.J., Macey, B.M., 2024. Effect of basket height and stocking density on production of the sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla*: insights and recommendations. Aquaculture International: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10499-024-01412-8>.

size and are size graded throughout production (monthly or as needed) to maintain optimal stocking densities.

During grow-out, sea urchins are held in raceway tanks and are distributed into 6mm mesh baskets to allow faecal material to fall through (Figure 74). These tanks are fitted with aeration and water is kept at ca. 25 °C at the South African IMTA lab using a heat pump. The seawater needs to be heated because of where the IMTA site is located, but a farm could be run without a heat pump further up the east coast of South Africa where the water temperatures are higher and *T. gratilla* naturally occurs.

Figure 74. (A) Land-based sea urchin grow-out system, with (B) 6 mm mesh baskets subdivided into four where (C) sea urchins are feeding on *Ulva* and a formulated feed. ©B. Macey.

Sea urchins are fed daily, and the feeding regime used depends on the approximate age/size of the sea urchins. Sea urchin aquaculture is characterised by two main growth stages: somatic growth (first ca. 6 – 7 months) and gonad enhancement (last 3 – 4 months). Somatic (body) growth is characterised by an increase in body size while limited gonad growth/development is observed. During gonad enhancement the weight of the five gonads in the urchin test increases while there is a small degree of somatic growth. Sea urchin feeding regimes may also depend on the availability of seaweeds near the site. The seaweeds *E. maxima* and *U. lacunculata* have been successfully used to produce sea urchins (Table 14). In the ASTRAL IMTA lab South Africa a diet of IMTA-produced *Ulva* and a formulated feed containing 20 % *Ulva* have been tested based on previous works that show that 20 % dry *Ulva* (w/w) inclusion in formulated feeds improves feed palatability, acts as a source of carotenoids that contribute to the orange colouration of the gonads, and acts as a feeding stimulant for sea urchins, thereby promoting gonad development^{128,138}. This formulated feed has a protein content of 25.69 %, a fat content of 2.31 % and a carbohydrate content of 43.75 %¹²⁸ (Table 14). Sea urchins require moderate

¹³⁸ Cyrus, M.D., Bolton, J.J., Scholtz, R., Macey, B.M., 2015. The advantages of *Ulva* (Chlorophyta) as an additive in sea urchin formulated feeds: effects on palatability, consumption and digestibility. *Aquaculture Nutrition* 21, 578–591.

protein inclusion (20 – 40%) in diets to produce commercially viable gonads^{128,139,140}, with higher protein levels negatively impacting sea urchin growth rates¹⁴¹. This is attributed to the high energetic cost of metabolising protein¹⁴³. In terms of their carbohydrate requirements, it has been found that sea urchins display no difference in growth at a wide range of carbohydrate concentrations (21 – 39 %) ¹⁴², and the 20U formulated feed falls within the optimal ranges for sea urchin gonad development.

Table 14. Nutrients in recommended *T. gratilla* feeds (*Ecklonia maxima*, *Ulva lacunculata*, formulated feed with 20 % *Ulva* inclusion) as described by (a) ¹⁴³Smith 2007, (b) ¹²⁸Cyrus et al., 2015 and (c) ¹⁴⁴Shuuluka 2011. All estimates are expressed as % dry weight. n.d. not determined.

Nutrients (% dw)	<i>Ecklonia maxima</i>	<i>Ulva lacunculata</i>	Formulated feed (20U)
Protein	11.00 ^a	18.31 ^b	25.69 ^b
Fat	1.16 ^a	0.38 ^b	2.31 ^b
Moisture (% ww)	79.39 ^a	80.60 ^c	9.61 ^b
Ash	19.41 ^a	32.66 ^b	13.89 ^b
Gross energy (MJ/kg)	n.d.	9.44 ^b	15.49 ^b
Fibre	41.34 ^a	6.02 ^b	4.75 ^b
Carbon/Carbohydrate	33.82 ^a	27.33 ^b	43.75 ^b

During the somatic growth phase, sea urchins are fed *Ulva* or kelp three times a week at roughly 8.5 % and 10 %, respectively, of the average sea urchin body weight (bw) per feeding. Formulated feeds could also be fed for the full duration of grow-out, but as these encourage gonad development, these are better suited for the last months of grow-out where gonad enhancement should be prioritised.

¹³⁹ Akiyama, T., Unuma, T., Yamamoto, T., 2001. Optimum protein level in a purified diet for young red sea urchin *Pseudocentrotus depressus*. Fisheries Science 67: 361–363.

¹⁴⁰ Powell, M.L., Marsh, A.G., Watts, S.A., 2020. Chapter 4: Biochemical and energy requirements of gonad development in regular sea urchins. In Lawrence J.M. (Ed.), *Sea urchins: biology and ecology*, 4th Ed., Elsevier, Oxford, UK, pp. 51–62.

¹⁴¹ Eddy, S.D., Brown, N.P., Kling, A.L., Watts, S.A., Lawrence, A., 2012. Growth of juvenile green sea urchins, *Strongylocentrotus droebachiensis*, fed formulated feeds with varying protein levels compared with a macroalgal diet and a commercial abalone feed. Journal of the World Aquaculture Society 43, 159–173.

¹⁴² Heflin, L.E., Gibbs, V.K., Powell, M.L., Makowsky, R., Lawrence, J.M., Lawrence, A.L., & Watts, S.A., 2012. Effect of dietary protein and carbohydrate levels on weight gain and gonad production in the sea urchin *Lytechinus variegatus*. Aquaculture 359–359, 235–261

¹⁴³ Smith M.J., 2007. Seasonal variation in nutritional content of the kelp *Ecklonia maxima* on the west and south west coasts of South Africa, with reference to its use as abalone feed. MSc thesis (Unpublished), Faculty of Science, University of Cape Town, South Africa.

¹⁴⁴ Shuuluka, D., 2011. Ecophysiological studies of three South African *Ulva* species from integrated seaweed/abalone aquaculture and natural populations. PhD thesis (Unpublished), Faculty of Science, University of Cape Town, South Africa.

During gonad enhancement, formulated feeds are fed at 0.6 – 1.5 % bw three times a week, but can also be fed fresh seaweeds, such as the IMTA-produced *Ulva*, to improve water quality conditions. While feeding *Ulva* a feed conversion ratio (FCR) of 1.1 % can be expected, whereas formulated feed fed animals have an FCR of 0.4 %, as observed in the South African IMTA lab. It should be noted that it is generally considered best practice to only have one feed in the tank at a time to avoid the urchins showing a preference towards one feed, leaving the other to disintegrate and negatively impact water quality parameters.

5.2.3.10 *Sea Urchin Growth Monitoring During Grow-out*

During different grow-out stages (i.e. somatic and gonad growth), sea urchins should be measured and dissected to assess gonad development. Sea urchin body weight (g) and test diameter (cm) should be measured, which can be done using the open-source sea urchin measuring software developed in the ASTRAL South African IMTA lab¹⁴⁵, or this can be performed manually with a scale and callipers. Sea urchins should be periodically dissected to assess gonad development. There are five gonads organised penta-radially inside the urchin test (Figure 75). From the exterior of the urchin, the gonads are situated in the areas of test where less tube feet can be observed. Therefore the sea urchins should be dissected by cutting on the areas of the test where tube feet are observed.

¹⁴⁵ De Vos, B.C., Cyrus M.D., Macey B.M., Batik T., Bolton J.J., 2023. Combining computer vision and standardised protocols for improved measurement of live sea urchins for research and industry. *Aquaculture, Fish and Fisheries* 3, 507–517.

Figure 75. (A) External and (B) internal anatomy of a sea urchin where five gonads are held inside an exoskeleton (test). ©Rupert and Barnes 1994.

Sea urchin dissection protocol:

1. Prepare dissection tray with scissors, tweezers, a spatula and seawater in a container.
2. Weigh animal and measure sea urchin diameter, and record information on datasheet.
3. Use scissors to cut into the peristome at an angle (Figure 76) whereby the scissors are pointed in the direction of test covered in tube feet.

Figure 76. Diagram of the oral side of a sea urchin where the incision should be made to dissect the animal.

4. Once the incision has been made, cut through to the top of the urchin test.

5. At the top, the direction of the cut should be changed to avoid cutting through a gonad (as depicted in Figure 82).
6. Using tweezers, remove the sea urchin intestines and other tissues.
7. Use the seawater to rinse any feed or loose tissue that may be present.
8. Repeat steps 6 and 7 until only the five gonads remain as depicted in Figure 77.

Figure 77. Dissected sea urchin with five gonads in the test cavity. ©M. Brink-Hull .

9. Use the spatula to scoop out the gonads into a weigh boat as depicted in Figure 78.

Figure 78. Sea urchin gonads that have been scooped out of the urchin test using a spatula. ©M. Brink-Hull.

10. Weigh the gonads and record the weight on a datasheet.

This method can be used to calculate the gonad somatic index (GSI) of the sea urchin, which represents the proportion of the sea urchin's weight that can be attributed to the gonad¹⁴⁹. $GSI (\%) = [\text{gonad wet weight (g)} / \text{total animal weight (g)}] \times 100$. For market purposes, a GSI of 20 % is aimed for, but can reach values as high as 35 %¹⁵⁰. The GSI is not the only indicator of market readiness, as gonad development and gonad colour are also good indicators and are important factors for the final monetary value of the product. Gonad development is dependent on the reproductive maturity of the sea urchin, where six sea urchin reproductive stages are described in literature, namely (1) recovery, (2) growing, (3) premature, (4) mature, (5) partly spawned and (6) spent¹⁴⁶. See the detailed guide by James and Siikavuopio (2012)¹⁴⁷ for more information of the staging of reproductive phases and the implications for market acceptability. Of these, the optimal reproductive stage for market is “growing” as firm sea urchin gonads containing few or no gametes are preferred. Therefore, histological approaches should be used to assess gonad development. A single gonad from each urchin will be randomly selected and transferred into Davidson's Fixative (per litre: 300 mL 95 % ethyl alcohol, 200 mL 100 % formalin, 100 mL glycerol, 100 mL glacial acetic acid and 300 mL distilled water) immediately following dissection and fixed for 48h, before being transferred into 70 % ethanol and processed for routine paraffin histology¹⁴⁸.

5.2.3.11 Stocking Density During Grow-out

Sea urchins should be stocked at roughly 6 – 8 kg/m² based on the experimental system in the IMTA lab South Africa or at 20 % basket surface coverage¹⁴⁸, but stocking densities should be decided on based on the site and the scale of the farming operation. This is particularly important in the case of a sea urchin-*Ulva* IMTA where the farm is dependent on the green seaweed *Ulva*'s capacity for nutrient uptake. If this experimental system was upscaled to a similar size as the abalone system and stocked at 6.36 kg/m², a total of 0.75 tonnes of gonad could be produced per month in 42 tanks (357 m³) as determined in the studies conducted in the ASTRAL IMTA lab South Africa.

5.2.3.12 Record Keeping

Biosecurity checks are conducted daily on all animals (broodstock) in the hatchery, including system functionality, habitus, animal behaviour, mortality, morbidity and feed response. During larval rearing,

¹⁴⁶ Cyrus M.D., 2013. The use of *Ulva* as a feed supplement in the development of an artificial diet and feeding regimes to produce export quality roe from the sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla* (Linnaeus). PhD thesis (Unpublished), Faculty of Science, University of Cape Town, South Africa.

¹⁴⁷ James, P., Siikavuopio, S., 2012. A guide to the sea urchin reproductive cycle and staging sea urchin gonad samples. The Norwegian Institute of Food, Fisheries and Aquaculture Research (NOFIMA), Norway.

¹⁴⁸ Bucke, D., 1989. Histology. In Austin B., Austin D.A. (Eds.), *Methods for the Microbiological Examination of Fish and Shellfish*, Ellis Horwood, Chichester.

daily observations are made of system functionality, larval density, feed density and larval development, and records of these parameters are kept. Water temperature is logged daily. Throughout grow-out, animal growth and health should be monitored, and daily assessments of animal health, feeding, habitus, morbidity, mortality and system functionality should be performed, and a record should be kept of these assessments.

5.2.3.13 Handling

Broodstock animals are only handled when necessary for tank cleaning or when used for spawning procedures. During spawning and larval rearing, strict biosecurity measures are put in place for any animal handling, with frequent use of 70 % ethanol to spray surfaces, glassware and hands before handling larval rearing equipment. After broodstock are spawned, they are held in a quarantine tank that is not linked with any other tank containing sea urchins to ensure that any residual spawning does not induce spawning of other animals.

Minimal larval handling is recommended where possible. Daily or every second day, 5 mL of the seawater containing larvae in each larval tank is collected to count larvae and assess larval development. Additionally, larvae are handled twice a week (if a static system is used) when water full tank exchanges are performed by siphoning larvae into a sieve (<100 µm for the first week and <150 µm for the remainder of larval rearing) and discarding the tank water so that the tank can be thoroughly cleaned, refilled with filtered 25 °C seawater and the sieve is gently placed in the newly filled tank to release larvae. The sieve is sprayed gently with seawater to move any remaining larvae back into the tank. The container used to collect all wastewater should be thoroughly cleaned between tanks while performing water exchanges.

During grow-out, sea urchins are handled to perform growth measurements and during weekly cleaning activities as baskets containing the urchins are removed from the tanks to completely drain and thoroughly clean them. To ensure that sea urchins spend limited time out of the water to avoid shock spawning, a clean tank can be prepared to simplify the cleaning process by moving the baskets into the clean tank before cleaning the previous tank. Similarly, the *Ulva* raceway and sump should be cleaned once a month or as needed.

5.2.3.14 Optimal Environmental Conditions

Though an optimal temperature range of 24 – 28 °C has been established for *T. gratilla* (Table 15), fast changes in temperature is more detrimental than absolute changes in temperature as this causes a stress response in the animals and has the potential to result in animals shock spawning. Optimal salinity for *T. gratilla* is 35 psu and dissolved oxygen of 90 % is considered optimal. Nutrients such as free ammonia nitrogen (FAN) in the water column and seawater pH (optimal at a pH = 8.0 – 8.2) should

be monitored to ensure optimal water quality, as this can affect sea urchin growth^{133,149}. Nutrient levels for FAN, total ammonia nitrogen (TAN), nitrite and nitrate should all remain low (as close to zero as possible) in the system, where high flow rates and the use of seaweeds in integrated systems can aid in removing these nutrients. It has been observed that *Tripneustes* have very low nitrogen emissions¹³³ (Bas de Vos, pers. comm.), but FAN levels as low as 0.016 mg/L have been shown to reduce gonad size in other sea urchin species¹⁵⁰. Given that TAN levels are dependent on the water pH, no specific threshold has been established. If the pH is high, ammonia becomes un-ionised and toxic^{133,153,151}. In contrast, low pH can inhibit calcification and affect sea urchin production negatively as this is important for test (exoskeleton) development. Alkalinity is also an important consideration in sea urchin aquaculture systems and is considered optimal at 120 mg/L CaCO₃¹⁵², as low alkalinities of < 20 mg/L may lower the buffering capacity of the seawater¹⁵³, which can negatively affect the FAN concentration. Lastly, a total suspended solids (TSS) threshold similar to that of the abalone standard of the Aquaculture Stewardship Council of less than 5 mg/L is recommended. Daily to weekly measurements of the relevant water quality parameters are performed, with the most important parameters including temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen and FAN.

Table 15. Optimal environmental conditions for the sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla* in land-based aquaculture systems.

|
Nutrients |
|---|--|--|---|---|
| 24 – 28°C | 35 psu | > 90%; > 6 mg.L ⁻¹ | 8.0 – 8.2 | FAN < 0.016 mg.L ⁻¹ |

¹⁴⁹ Shpigel, M., Erez, J., 2020. Effect of diets and light regimes on calcification and somatic growth of the sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla elatensis*. *Aquaculture* 735547.

¹⁵⁰ Siikavuopio, S.I., Dale, T., Foss, A., Mortensen, A., 2004. Effects of chronic ammonia exposure on gonad growth and survival in green sea urchin *Strongylocentrotus droebachiensis*. *Aquaculture* 242, 313–320.

¹⁵¹ Mos, B., Byrne, M., Dworjanyn, S.A., 2016. Biogenic acidification reduces sea urchin gonad growth and increases susceptibility of aquaculture to ocean acidification. *Marine Environmental Research* 113, 39–48.

¹⁵² Boyd, C.E., Tucker, C.S., Somridhivej, B., 2016. Alkalinity and hardness: critical but elusive concepts in aquaculture. *Journal of the World Aquaculture Society* 47, 6–41.

¹⁵³ Hariyadi, S., Tucker, C.S., Steeby, J.A., van der Roeg, M., Boyd, C.E., 1994. Environmental conditions

5.2.3.15 *Disease Control and Treatment*

Sea urchin microbial consortia can be sensitive to stressors, including animal handling, grading, sudden environmental changes (e.g., system failures) or poor food quality. These stressors could result in a state of microbial dysbiosis and a reduction in beneficial microbes that may facilitate infection(s) by opportunistic pathogens(s), that may ultimately lead to mortalities¹⁵⁴. Disease in sea urchins is characterised by spine loss and bald spots on the body (test) surface where the spines used to be. Daily animal health monitoring is used to avoid mortalities from these diseases as animals should be quarantined if infections are observed. Sea urchins also display cannibalism, particularly during early growth stages or when stocking densities are high. This can be avoided to some extent by ensuring consistent food availability by feeding *ad libitum* and by actively grading animals during early growth stages to ensure that animals with different size classes are not held in the same basket. Size grading will not only assist in avoiding cannibalism but will also result in faster growth rates for smaller animals if they are not competing with larger sea urchins for food.

5.2.3.16 *Harvesting*

Sea urchins are considered ready for harvesting when they are approximately 55 – 60 mm in test diameter, and if gonads are developed. Post-production processes include harvesting sea urchin gonads, assessing gonad quality, performing food safety tests and processing the gonads for export. If transport is required for harvesting, animals should be gently placed in Styrofoam boxes that are lined with moist foam to place the sea urchins on. If animals spawn during transport, they can be rinsed with seawater upon arrival or placed in tanks with high water flow prior to harvesting.

Animals should be carefully monitored towards the end of grow-out as gonad quality, and its corresponding market value, is influenced by their reproductive phase. Gonads containing few or no gametes are preferred and therefore histological assessment of the gonads is recommended in the three months prior to harvesting. Product/gonad quality (firmness, colour, texture, taste) and food safety should be assessed prior to export to adhere to export food safety standards. High quality gonads with a bright and firm yellow or orange appearance have the highest market value¹⁵⁵ and

¹⁵⁴ Brink M., Rhode C., Macey B.M., Christison K.W., Roodt-Wilding R., 2019. Metagenomic assessment of body surface bacterial communities of the sea urchin, *Tripneustes gratilla*. *Marine Genomics* 47, 100675.

¹⁵⁵ Robinson, S.M.C., Castell, J.D., Kennedy, E.J., 2002. Developing suitable colour in the gonads of cultured green sea urchins (*Stongylocentrotus droebachiensis*). *Aquaculture* 206, 289–303.

should therefore be exported as fresh product (harvested or as whole urchins)¹⁵⁶ (Figure 79). Lower quality products can be processed for market by baking, freezing, steaming and salting¹⁵⁷.

Figure 79. Fresh *Tripneustes gratilla* gonads/uni served on rice from animals produced at the DFFE Marine Research Aquarium in Sea Point, Cape Town. ©M. Cyrus.

5.2.4 Green seaweed (*Ulva lacinulata*)

5.2.4.1 Choice of *Ulva* species/strain

A critical initial step in cultivating *Ulva* is the selection of the species to be grown. The *Ulva* on South African abalone farms was chosen not because it is a marketable product, but because of its fast consistent growth rates throughout the year, efficient ammonia uptake, and quality as feed for abalone. The identity of *Ulva* species has been the subject of much recent research: it is often not possible currently to accurately identify *Ulva* species by morphology, and DNA techniques are necessary¹⁵⁸. This has resulted in several different names having been used for the *Ulva* grown on

¹⁵⁶ Stefánsson, G., Kristinsson, H., Ziemer, N., Hannon, C., James, P., 2017. Markets for sea urchins: a review of global supply and markets. NOFIMA: Icelandic food and biotechnology research and development. Report nr.: 10-17.

¹⁵⁷ Exploration Unlimited Incorporated. 2006. Sea urchin fishery profiles. Benchmarked competitiveness study of BC's sea urchin fisheries. Brentwood Bay, British Columbia, Canada: Exploration Unlimited Incorporated.

¹⁵⁸ Tran, L.T., Vieira C., Steinhagen, S., Maggs, C.A., Hiraoka, M., Shimada, S., Van Nguyen, T., De Clerk, O., Leliaert, F., 2022. An appraisal of *Ulva* (Ulvophyceae, Chlorophyta) taxonomy. *Journal of Applied Phycology* 34, 2689–2703.

South African abalone farms over the last 20 years. Most *Ulva* species grow attached on rocky seashores and reproduce by spore production regularly (commonly every two weeks, with a lunar reproductive cycle). Spore release causes significant portions of the *Ulva* thallus to deteriorate, with a large detrimental effect on production. A few species are capable of growth free-living (unattached) in nature, growing vegetatively without spore production, and some of these form large problem growths in sheltered waters, sometimes known as ‘green tides’. Initial selection of *Ulva* material on South African abalone farms, beginning more than two decades ago, was from such free-living populations, and material has thus selected itself for growth in the systems (Figure 80). It has recently been shown in this project, by molecular barcoding, that material grown in abalone farms all around South Africa, in a number of biogeographic regions, is a single species, now correctly known as *Ulva lacinulata*¹⁵⁹ (Figure 81). Contaminants of other *Ulva* species do sometimes occur and can prove a problem (see later). *Ulva lacinulata* is also grown commercially, selected independently, in Europe, e.g. in Portugal¹⁶².

Figure 80. *Ulva lacinulata* grown in a paddle raceway on a South African abalone farm. ©J. Bolton.

¹⁵⁹ Bachoo, T., Bolton, J.J., Macey, B.M., Kandjengo, L., Reddy, M.M., 2023. Resolving the identity of commercially cultivated *Ulva* (Ulvaceae, Chlorophyta) in integrated seaweed-abalone aquaculture farms in South Africa. *Journal of Phycology* 59, 1272–1283.

Figure 81. Morphology of *Ulva lacinulata* from Buffeljags Abalone farm. B & C: Surface view and transverse section through edge region of the thallus. D & E: Surface view and transverse section through middle region of the thallus. ©Bachoo, 2021.

The successful growth of *Ulva* in land-based culture in various countries has had several factors in common:

- Generally foliose species of *Ulva* rather than tubular species (formerly *Enteromorpha*) are grown, often recorded as *Ulva lactuca* (a name used generally in the past for various species of foliose *Ulva* around the world), as well as *Ulva lacinulata*, *Ulva ohnoi*, *Ulva reticulata* etc., in various geographical locations.
- These are often collected initially in sheltered locations, from free-living populations.
- They are tested in the aquaculture systems in which they will be cultured, and the species which grow well in these systems can be cultured for long periods without problems with breakup from reproductive events. For example, Ryther (1982) in the USA did extensive culture work with a foliose *Ulva* which was given to him by a local aquafarmer who had found that it grew well in tanks¹⁶⁰.

Selection of a species/strain which grows well in any aquaculture system is critical to the success of *Ulva* cultivation but has not been studied in a particularly scientific way, as yet. Fort et al. (2020) have

¹⁶⁰ Ryther, J.H., 1982. Cultivation of macroscopic marine algae (Solar Energy Research Institute No. SERI/STR-231-1820). National Technical Information Service, US Department of Commerce.

recently shown in strain selection experiments that laboratory growth rates can be higher in free-living ‘green tide’ populations¹⁶¹, which matches the anecdotal information from aquafarmers growing *Ulva*. What is critical is production rates and *Ulva* quality in farm conditions, not in laboratory conditions, which are generally very different.

The *Ulva lacunculata* which is grown on South African abalone farms was produced from material originally collected in sheltered locations on the coastline, primarily Saldanha Bay on the west coast, although some farmers also collected from other locations (including Gansbaai and Simon’s Town harbours). Initial data from Bachoo et al. (2023) suggests that *Ulva lacunculata* is rare growing attached on South African seashores and was not found in a collection of foliose *Ulva* on seashores around Hermanus harbour, where *Ulva lacunculata* has been grown on local farms for many years¹⁶².

5.2.4.2 Daily and Routine Operations

Ulva is grown on South African abalone farms in a year-round operation. It has good yield all year round, as a result of the mid-latitude position of the country. In a region with colder, darker winters (e.g. Northern Europe, Canadian Maritimes) this sort of year-round production would not be feasible, but it is practised in Southern Europe (e.g. Portugal, Helena Abreu, pers. comm.) and tropical Queensland, Australia (Rocky de Nys, pers. comm.). Monthly yields in South Africa tend to be higher in summer months¹⁶³. Daily routine involves visual monitoring of health and abundance. Darker green *Ulva* has higher nitrogen, and hence protein content¹⁶⁴. Paddle raceways which become over-fouled by other benthic organisms, or where other floating organisms or sediment loads become a problem, are emptied and manually cleaned, followed by re-stocking.

Ulva is grown in abalone effluent directly fed from the abalone raceways, and as such does not need extra fertilisation at Buffeljags. In some South African abalone farms, the surface of the *Ulva* has occasionally become infected with a brown crustose seaweed (*Myrionema strangulans*), which can eventually cause thallus deterioration¹⁶⁵. This tends to happen in Spring/early Summer when the *Ulva* is growing rapidly and may use up available nutrients. Evidence for this is that it has been

¹⁶¹ Fort, A., Mannion, C., Farinas-Franco, J.M., Sulpice, R., 2020. Green tides select for fast expanding *Ulva* strains. *Science for the Total Environment* 698, 134337.

¹⁶² Bachoo, T., Bolton, J.J., Macey, B.M., Kandjengo, L., Reddy, M.M., 2023. Resolving the identity of commercially cultivated *Ulva* (Ulvaceae, Chlorophyta) in integrated seaweed-abalone aquaculture farms in South Africa. *Journal of Phycology* 59, 1272–1283.

¹⁶³ Bolton, J.J., Robertson-Andersson, D.V., Shuuluka, D., Kandjengo, L., 2009. Growing *Ulva* (Chlorophyta) in integrated systems as a commercial crop for abalone feed in South Africa: A SWOT analysis. *Journal of Applied Phycology* 21, 575–583.

¹⁶⁴ Robertson-Andersson, D.V., Wilson, D.T., Bolton, J.J., Anderson, R.J., Maneveldt, G.W., 2009. Rapid assessment of tissue nitrogen in cultivated *Gracilaria gracilis* (Rhodophyta) and *Ulva lactuca* (Chlorophyta). *African Journal of Aquatic Science* 34, 169–172

¹⁶⁵ Robertson-Andersson, D.V., Potgieter, M., Hansen, J., Bolton, J.J., Troell, M., Anderson, R.J., Halling, C., Probyn, T., 2008. Integrated seaweed cultivation on an abalone farm in South Africa. *Journal of Applied Phycology* 20, 579–595.

experimentally shown that fertilisation can reduce the incidence of the *Myrionema*¹⁶⁹. This has not proven a problem at Buffeljags Abalone.

In some South African abalone farms *Ulva* is grown as a feed component in seawater rather than in abalone effluent, in similar paddle raceways. In this case, nitrogen and ammonium fertiliser is added. At one farm, Shuuluka (2011)¹⁶⁶ reported that once a week each raceway pond is fertilised with 1.5 kg of ammonium sulphate and "Supergrow"[®] (P: 203 g/kg, S: 23.6 g/kg, Ca: 171.4 g/kg) in a ratio of 6:1. The fertiliser is added in the late afternoon after disconnecting the raceway pond from the rest of the system by closing the inlet- and outlet sluice gates. The amount of nutrients added was the same for all raceway ponds, and thus independent of seaweed density in the raceway ponds. Similar fertilisation happens *ad hoc* very occasionally at Buffeljags if *Ulva* growth is poor.

5.2.4.3 Optimal Environmental Conditions

Ulva lacinulata grown in these farms has relatively wide environmental tolerances, as shown by the fact that it is grown throughout the year commercially from Kleinsee to Haga Haga, with a range of monthly mean ambient seawater temperatures from 11.3 – 18.6 °C¹⁶⁷. In 15-day laboratory investigations (as *Ulva lactuca*) this species grew in a wide range of temperatures from 5 to 25 °C, died at 30 °C, with optimal growth at 15 – 20 °C¹⁶⁹. Growth at 25 °C was ca. 75 % of optimal. The latter showed promise for the same species being used at this higher temperature in integrated culture with the warm water urchin *Tripneustes gratilla*.

Ulva lacinulata also grew optimally at salinities of 25 to 40, showed some growth as low as 5, and survived 15 days in freshwater with added Provasoli nutrient medium¹⁶⁹. The latter can prove useful in brief washing with freshwater to remove certain biotic contaminants (e.g. mobile invertebrates such as isopods). In the same study the farm material was shown to have a higher light saturation for growth than two abundant local seashore species. Light is of course a critical factor for growth of photosynthetic organisms. The paddle wheel movement ensures continual flow so that individual *Ulva* plants are constantly circulated within the water column receiving alternately lighter and darker conditions. These paddle raceways were first used for microalgae such as *Spirulina*. In high density microalgal production units, microalgae alternate between light and complete darkness, whereas this is not the case with the *Ulva* in South African paddle raceways. It has been observed that light reaches

¹⁶⁶ Shuuluka, D., Bolton, J. J., & Anderson, R. J. (2013). Protein content, amino acid composition and nitrogen-to- protein conversion factors of *Ulva rigida* and *Ulva capensis* from natural populations and *Ulva lactuca* from an aquaculture system, in South Africa. *Journal of Applied Phycology*, 25, 677–685.

¹⁶⁷ Bachoo, T., 2021. Characterization of *Ulva* (Ulveae, Chlorophyta) species cultured in commercial abalone farms in South Africa, and comparison with closely related wild species, using morpho-anatomical and molecular methods. MSc thesis, University of Cape Town.

the bottom of the *Ulva* paddle raceways, at Irvine & Johnson Cape Abalone in Gansbaai, even in winter in high density just before harvesting.

A major factor in algal growth is water nutrient concentration. It is not possible to state standard nutrient concentrations which limit growth, though, as the ability of a seaweed to take up nutrients is closely linked with water movement. Another critical factor in nutrient availability is nutrient replenishment, which in these systems depends on the water exchange rate into the *Ulva paddle* raceways. In still conditions, nutrient uptake over the thallus creates a nutrient deprived boundary layer over the surface of the seaweed. As water movement increases, growth increases until a saturation point is reached. In still culture in the laboratory, growth is increased by using culture media with much higher levels of available nutrients (in specified nutrient media). The paddle raceways used to grow *Ulva* on abalone farms are a compromise solution. Seaweeds take up both major (especially dissolved inorganic nitrogen and phosphorus) and minor nutrients as well as dissolved gases (particularly carbon as dissolved carbon dioxide or bicarbonate for photosynthesis, and oxygen for respiration) from the water. The uptake of dissolved gases can be improved by aeration, but this is expensive to provide. The paddle raceways provide sufficient water movement for reasonable levels of nutrient uptake but are not optimal growth conditions. They are a financially viable option for *Ulva* efficient production, made more economical as one motor is used to run paddles for two adjacent raceways (Figure 82). It is considered by us to be generally ineffective to test strains of *Ulva* or other seaweeds for growth in laboratory systems and use the data to assume they are the best strains for growth in commercial systems.

Figure 82. Two adjacent paddle raceways at Buffeljags abalone farm, growing *Ulva lacunculata*. Note the single motor for two paddles, and the sump in foreground for mixing bioremediated abalone effluent with fresh seaweeds (normally 50 %). ©J. Bolton.

The initial abalone/*Ulva* system with 50 % bioremediated effluent recirculation was set up at I&J in 2005, designed by current VIKING manager, Nick Loubser. That system ran with a water exchange rate of ca. 13.3 water volume exchanges per day. This value would have to vary on different farms, both those recirculating bioremediated effluent and those not, as well depending on the number of abalone producing the effluent running into the raceway. All these factors cannot be standardised and specified, as they will depend on various individual aspects of the systems. All abalone farms are subject to a large variety different environmental conditions and abalone/seaweed culture techniques, and things like seasonal water flow rates will need to be tested on any new system. In South Africa the major upwelling system on the west coast ensures relatively high seawater nutrient concentrations in the ambient seawater, whereas in the North Atlantic many sites will have very low nutrient concentrations in the summer. This will affect required water turnover rates and possible need to fertilisation at certain times of year.

5.2.4.4 Grazer Control and Ulva contamination

Grazing animals are not a major problem in *Ulva* systems at Buffeljags. Occasionally colonies of small invertebrates trap sediment, but these are removed with routine paddle pond cleaning. In initial studies towards *Ulva* growth on South African abalone farms, there were some problems with mobile grazers. Various amphipod, isopod species and a keyhole limpet were recorded in *Ulva* tanks systems

and could be managed, as in the current commercial systems, by regular cleaning. In the case of the keyhole limpets they could be treated by soaking for 20 minutes with freshwater, which the *Ulva* can survive¹⁶⁷. The latter has not proven to be a problem in later commercial systems.

During the ASTRAL project some of the *Ulva* paddle ponds at Buffeljags, and also at the VIKING sister farm Diamond Coast Abalone at Kleinsee, became contaminated with a different *Ulva* species, morphologically identified as *Ulva linza* (*sensu* Stegenga et al. 1997)¹⁶⁸. This is a partially tubular species, formerly in the genus *Enteromorpha*, and it floats close to the water surface (Figure 83). This is problematic, as floating *Ulva* shades the *Ulva lacinulata* in the water column and the flotation means that it is not available if fed to the abalone. This is being successfully managed by emptying contaminated raceways and restocking with *Ulva lacinulata*.

Figure 83. Floating *Ulva linza* growing in a paddle raceway on a South African abalone farm. ©J. Bolton.

5.2.4.5 Stocking Density and Harvesting

Stocking density and harvesting regime for *Ulva* integrated with invertebrates depends on the main use of the *Ulva* in the system. In farms such as Buffeljags abalone, where the main reason to grow *Ulva* is for bioremediation of effluent to enable partial water recirculation, then the *Ulva* must be stocked at relatively high levels and harvested often, generally weekly. In other farms in South Africa where the *Ulva* is grown predominantly as feed for the abalone, *Ulva* raceways are stocked at lower levels

¹⁶⁸ Stegenga, H., Bolton J.J., Anderson R.J., 1997. Seaweeds of the South African west coast. Contributions from the Bolus Herbarium 18, 1–655.

and fully emptied for harvest and restocked each month. The latter farms harvest different raceways in rotation to enable regular availability of *Ulva*, whereas at Buffeljags each raceway is partially harvested weekly (Figure 84). Harvesting is carried out manually at Buffeljags. At other South African farms where paddle raceways are fully harvested once per month, the raceway is emptied and *Ulva* is manually brushed to one end of the raceway for manual harvesting in crates.

At a system at I&J Cape Abalone, where paddle raceways are emptied monthly, each raceway “has an underground drainpipe which surfaces from the raceways on the sea side. During harvest, the pipe gate is opened to drain out the *Ulva* from the raceway ponds and *Ulva* is harvested in perforated baskets to allow the water to drain through.... The raceway ponds (are) immediately reseeded with 500 kg of the *Ulva*”¹⁶⁹.

Stocking density in the paddle raceways at Buffeljags between 1 – 2 kg *Ulva* per m² of the pond surface area, which equates to a total biomass of roughly 1 – 1.5 tonnes of *Ulva* per raceway.

Figure 84. Manual harvesting of *Ulva lacinulata* at Buffeljags abalone. ©Viking Aquaculture.

5.3 Health

The DFFE has developed a National Aquatic Animal Health Strategic Framework (hereafter referred to as the Framework) in South Africa to provide overarching strategic guidance for the management, control and regulation of aquatic animal health, welfare, and disease management in South Africa to facilitate export of abalone (and other aquacultured products) to international markets¹⁶⁹ (DAFF, 2013). Abalone cultivated in South Africa are mostly exported to Asian countries, primarily China, with a smaller percentage going to Taiwan, Singapore, and Malaysia. The World Organization for Animal

¹⁶⁹ Department of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries (DAFF), National Aquatic Animal Health Strategic Framework 2013.

Health (WOAH) publishes two international standards —the ‘Aquatic Animal Health Code’ and ‘Manual of Diagnostic Tests for Aquatic Animals’ — that forms the basis of the Framework. The South African legislation and regulations relevant to aquatic animal health include:

- The Fertilizers, Farm Feeds, Agricultural Remedies and Stock Remedies Act, 1947 (Act No 36 of 1947). This Act aims to “To provide for the appointment of a Registrar of Fertilizers, Farm Feeds and Agricultural Remedies, and for the registration of fertilizers, farm feeds, agricultural remedies, stock remedies, sterilizing plants and pest control operators, and to regulate or prohibit the importation, sale, acquisition, disposal or use of fertilizers, farm feeds, agricultural remedies and stock remedies, and to provide for the designation of technical advisers and analysts, and to provide for matters incidental thereto.”
- The Animals Protection Act, 1962 (Act No 71 of 1962) and Societies for the Prevention of Cruelty to Animals Act, 1993 (Act No 169 of 1993). These Acts cover all aspects of cruelty to animals and the prevention thereof, including “being the owner of any animal, deliberately or negligently keeps such animal in a dirty or parasitic condition or allows it to become infested with external parasites or fails to render or procure veterinary or other medical treatment or attention which he or she is able to render or procure for any such animal in need of such treatment or attention, whether through disease, injury, delivery of young or any other cause, or fails to destroy or cause to be destroyed any such animal which is so seriously injured or diseased or in such a physical condition that to prolong its life would be cruel and would cause such animal unnecessary suffering.”
- The Medicines and Related Substances Control Act, 1965 (Act No 101 of 1965) and Medicines and Related Substances Control Amendment Act, 1997 (Act No 90 of 1997). These Acts aim to "To provide for the registration of medicines intended for human and for animal use, and for the registration of medical devices, and for the establishment of a Medicines Control Council, for the control of medicines, scheduled substances and medical devices, for the control of manufacturers, wholesalers and distributors of medicines and medical devices, and for the control of persons who may compound and dispense medicines, and for matters incidental thereto."
- The Veterinary and Paraveterinary Professions Act, 1982 (Act No 19 of 1982). This Act aims "To provide for the establishment, powers and functions of the South African Veterinary Council, for the registration of persons practicing veterinary professions and paraveterinary professions, and for control over the practicing of veterinary professions and paraveterinary professions, and for matters connected therewith."

- The Animal Diseases Act, 1984 (Act No 35 of 1984) and Animal Disease Regulations. This Act and the regulations aim “To provide for the control of animal diseases and parasites, for measures to promote animal health, and for matters connected therewith.”
- The Meat Safety Act, 2000 (Act No 40 of 2000). This Act aims “To provide for measures to promote meat safety and the safety of animal products; to establish and maintain essential national standards in respect of abattoirs; to regulate the importation and exportation of meat; to establish meat safety schemes; and to provide for matters connected herewith.”
- Other relevant legislation pertaining to animal health and welfare includes:
 - A list of all legislation which may impact on veterinarians can be found at the Faculty of Veterinary Science library (site <http://www.ais.up.ac.za/vet/vetacts.htm>)
 - Animal disease legislation and controls can be found at <http://www.doa.agric.za/> under Division of Veterinary Services.
 - More information is also available at the South African Veterinary Council site, <http://www.savc.co.za/>, including the rules pertaining to the veterinary profession.

In addition to the above, protocols and standards have been developed specifically for aquaculture, addressing issues such as disease-free zones and stock movements, emergency response and preparedness, quarantine, listing of diseases, prevention of suffering, disposal of mortalities, decontamination, biosecurity, operation of harvesting vessels and processing facilities, and compliance and enforcement. The specific conditions are outlined in the various types of permits required to engage in marine aquaculture. A “right to engage in marine aquaculture” must be obtained from the DFFE when undertaking any commercial marine aquaculture activity, in terms of section 18 of the Marine Living Resources Act, 1998 (Act No. 18 of 1998) (MLRA). Permission to exercise such a “right” is granted by means of an annual permit, and rights holders must abide by the specific regulations outlined in the various permits governing, for example, hatcheries, grow-out, broodstock collection, transport, processing, and the import and export of marine aquaculture species and products. A “right to engage in marine aquaculture” is valid for 15 years, whereas marine aquaculture permits are renewable and valid for a period of 12 months.

More specifically to cultivate abalone, all farmers (Permit Holders) must comply with the active and passive components of the approved official surveillance program (Appendix A of the Health Management Procedures for South African Abalone produced for export).

5.4 Biosecurity

Biosecurity in aquaculture consists of practices that minimise the risk of introducing an infectious disease and spreading it to the animals at a facility and the risk that diseased animals or infectious agents will leave a facility and spread to other sites and to other susceptible species. These practices also reduce stress to the animals, thus making them less susceptible to disease agents¹⁷⁰.

Robust biosecurity systems are an essential pillar to healthy aquaculture production and a sustainable industry, protecting producers and emerging aquaculture sectors from the risks and threats of aquatic pathogens and diseases. The Animal Disease Act (Act 35 of 1984) in South Africa makes provision for the control of animal diseases and parasites and for measures to promote animal health¹⁷¹. Aquaculture animals and products that are exported from South Africa require health certification. The latter has resulted in the development of animal health procedures to provide assurances of disease freedom and to demonstrate the maintenance of the animals' health status through the implementation of basic biosecurity conditions in accordance with WOAHP standards¹⁷². Health management procedures for sea urchin and seaweed currently do not exist in South Africa. Conversely, specific procedures have been developed for abalone to comply with the basic biosecurity conditions prescribed by the WOAHP¹⁷³. These procedures stipulate that in order to export abalone permit holders must demonstrate freedom from the three diseases currently listed by the WOAHP for *Haliotis* species, namely, infections with abalone herpesvirus, *Perkinsus olseni* and *Xenohaliotis californiensis* — even though these diseases have never been detected in our local abalone species and *H. midae* has not been listed as a susceptible host species for any of these diseases¹⁶⁹.

Moreover, the health management procedures for South African abalone produced for export requires implementation of both passive and active surveillance programmes to ensure early detection of disease introductions. Passive surveillance relies on the farm personnel, who are in contact with the animals daily, to recognise and report any suspected infections with WOAHP listed diseases, whereas targeted surveillance requires clinical inspection of the farmed population by a trained veterinarian. Biosecurity at the farm level is generally regarded as the responsibility of individual farms and in South Africa the Abalone Farmers Association of South Africa (AFASA), in conjunction with their private animal health service providers, have developed a basic biosecurity standard for farmed abalone¹⁶⁹.

¹⁷⁰ <https://thefishsite.com/articles/biosecurity-in-aquaculture-part-1-an-overview>.

¹⁷¹ Government of South Africa (1984). – The Animal Diseases Act (Act 35 of 1984). National Gazette No. **9152** (3), 63 pp. Available at: www.nda.agric.za/vetweb/Legislation/Animal%20Diseases%20Act%20MAIN.htm.

¹⁷² World Organisation for Animal Health (OIE) (2018). – Aquatic Animal Health Code, 21st Ed. OIE, Paris, France. Available at: www.oie.int/standard-setting/aquatic-code/access-online/.

¹⁷³ Christison, K.W. (2019) Building a sustainable aquaculture industry in South Africa: the role of biosecurity. Rev. Sci. Tech. Off. Int. Epiz. **38**(2), 589-600.

Major goals of the biosecurity programme include the following key aspects:

- Animal management—obtaining healthy stocks and optimizing their health and immunity through good husbandry practices on farms.
- Pathogen management—preventing, reducing, or eliminating pathogens.
- People management—educating and managing staff and visitors.

Health surveillance is a critical component of a biosecurity programme, and the health and well-being of the animals must form part of the routine management tasks on the farm. These tasks must include, amongst others, daily inspection and monitoring when feeding animals and cleaning tanks as well as monthly internal health audits and comprehensive health checks by a trained veterinarian (once every 2 – 3 months) — to provide management with an early indication of potential health issues on the farm. Daily/monthly animal health monitoring on the farm should include, amongst other things, observations of the following:

- Feed response: Are the eating more or less?
- Behaviour: Any abnormal behaviour?
- Breathing: Struggling for air or congregating at top of baskets?
- Appearance: Visual marks, lesions, or sores?
- Water quality: O₂, pH, Temperature, Salinity, TAN, FAN
- Morbidity or mortality

On-going or sudden increase in mortality should be reported to attending veterinarian immediately and to the competent authority in the country (normally required as part of standard permitting conditions). This is vital to ensure immediate response/management measures are implemented and that a proper diagnosis is made that will inform effective treatment and management interventions.

To minimise the risk of introducing and spreading an infectious disease agent at a facility and spreading it to other areas within the farm or to other sites/farms, biosecurity checkpoints are essential. Checkpoints typically include footbaths and hand sanitizers when entering and leaving the farm or different dedicated areas of the farm (e.g., hatchery, weaning and different sections of the grow-out platforms on the farm). Specific items of equipment are also dedicated to different areas to prevent spread of infectious disease agents and each section generally has dedicated workers. In the case of Buffeljags Abalone, the farm has been specifically designed to consist of modular units, with each abalone/sea urchin cluster linked to a single *Ulva* raceway regarded as an independent/epidemiological unit that can be isolated in the event of a disease outbreak without impacting production on the remainder of the farm. Biosecurity checkpoints require daily maintenance, and include, for example, replacement of disinfectant (e.g. Virkon-S) in footbaths,

tidying of areas, sterilising equipment and uniform compliance. Daily records of all biosecurity and animal health procedures/monitoring must be maintained and reviewed on a regular basis by the biosecurity coordinator and farm management.

5.5 Welfare

Animal health and welfare are interrelated, with animals in good health regarded as animals capable of performing physiological functions at normal levels and lacking disease or injury. Welfare, on the other hand, is the physical and mental state of an animal in relation to the conditions in which it lives and the capacity of the animal to cope with its environment. When responsible farming practices are implemented, such as those described in this document for the various species, then good health and welfare can be supported.

Animal welfare should be monitored daily, as described above, by assessing feed responses, animal behaviour and animal appearance. A daily check list that keeps track of the animal inventory, system functionality, morbidity, mortality, feed response and habitus must be maintained to monitor animal welfare and provide early indication of suboptimal health/welfare. System functionality is a vital factor in land-based systems with partial recirculation, where water quality needs to be regularly monitored maintained within the optimal ranges for specific species and aeration needs to be continuously provided. Sea urchins are easily affected by poor water quality conditions and shock spawning, as a result of a system fault, can cause water quality to rapidly deteriorate and result in mortality. Therefore, it is vital that system functionality is assessed and maintained as needed as part of animal welfare assessments. A scoring system can be used to track feed responses, as animals not feeding is generally an indicator of poor animal welfare or an early indicator of stress and disease: (4) excellent, (3) good, (2) fair and (1) poor. Animal habitus can also be scored: (4) animals are behaving normally, (3) some animals with lesions/abnormalities or abnormal behaviour, (2) approximately half the animals display abnormal behaviour, (1) all animals displaying abnormal behaviour and (0) mass mortality. For sea urchins and abalone, abnormal behaviour would include animals not holding on to the baskets, all animals being at the bottom of a basket or being unresponsive.

6 RAS Biofloc IMTA System

The Federal University of Rio Grande (FURG) IMTA production system is situated in the southernmost region of Brazil ($32^{\circ}17'52.30''$ S – $52^{\circ}15'59.80''$ W), experiencing a humid subtropical climate. This climate is characterized by hot, humid summers (with maximum temperatures reaching 40°C) and cold (add minimum $^{\circ}\text{C}$) to very mild winters, resulting in a relatively broad annual temperature range. The laboratory operates as a land-based IMTA system within a greenhouse, utilizing full recirculation approach and cultivating various species, including marine shrimps (*Litopenaeus vannamei*), tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*), oysters (*Crassostrea gasar*), halophyte (*Salicornia neei*) and macroalgae (*Ulva lactuca*). The super-intensive production in biofloc system serves as a sustainable and biosecure alternative to traditional intensive culture systems. Biofloc consists of uneaten feed, faeces, secretions, and their associated algal, bacterial, and microplankton communities.

Shrimp are cultivated in tanks at a high-density rate, exceeding conventional systems by 25 %, with a concentrated presence of water nutrients such as phosphates, nitrates, and organic matter—known as bioflocs in BFT system. To manage the elevated organic matter levels, tilapias are reared in separate tanks (Figure 85). Functioning as filter feeders, tilapias extract and consume bioflocs, repurposing the organic material within the production system. The nutrient-rich effluent water from the shrimp tanks is utilized as a food source for the fish, reducing the need for external feed inputs. The bioflocs and bacteria present in the system serve as supplementary feed for shrimps and an indirect source of nutrients for the plant and seaweed species.

Figure 85. IMTA system in Brazil. Consisting of just 3 tanks and a submersible pump to recirculate the water. No filters or other equipment to maintain water quality.

Water from the tilapia tank flows to another tank hosting seaweeds, which efficiently absorb dissolved nutrients, including reused nitrates and phosphates accumulated in the system. These seaweeds exhibit resilience to organic loads and capitalize on the transformation of nitrogenous compounds facilitated by bacteria present in the bioflocs. The blades of the seaweeds assimilate nitrogen compounds from fish and shrimp excretion, such as ammonia and nitrites, effectively removing and converting them into usable seaweed biomass.

The water from the primary tank, designated for shrimp production (Figure 86), is pumped into the fish tank. Through gravity, the effluent from fish production flows to the seaweed tank. Subsequently, the water returns by gravity to the main tank containing shrimps, completing the integrated and sustainable circulation within the production system.

Figure 86. Multi-trophic system (left) and shrimp tank with biofloc (brown water).

Considering the climatic variations in the southern region of Brazil and the unsuitable temperatures for tropical species (tilapia and marine shrimp) during autumn and spring, cultivation is carried out in greenhouses to extend the production period to 9-10 months/year.

Table 16 shows the list of species trialled at IMTA lab Brazil.

Table 16. Species trialled at IMTA lab Brazil.

<u>Common name</u>	<u>Latin name</u>	<u>Role in IMTA</u>
White shrimp	<i>Litopenaeus vannamei</i>	Fed species
Tilapia	<i>Oreochromis niloticus</i>	Fed species
Native oyster	<i>Crassostrea gasar</i>	Extractive species
Seaweed	<i>Ulva lactuca</i>	Extractive species
Sea asparagus	<i>Salicornia neei</i>	Extractive species

The species at the IMTA lab Brazil are categorised as: fed and extractive species.

1. **Fed species:** The feed is used to grow shrimp and tilapia, but the fish are underfed and forced to eat biofloc. As a result, the animals release waste/nutrients into the water that is used as a nutrient source for the extractive seaweed species grown in the integrated system.
2. **Extractive species:** Dissolved nutrients are consumed by the seaweed *Ulva lactuca* and the organic material (biofloc) is controlled in the system by tilapias and oysters.

6.1 Species Production

Standard Operating Systems (SOPs) for all species here – refer to established industry protocols, if available.

6.1.1 Marine shrimp - *Litopenaeus vannamei*

6.1.1.1 Daily/Routine Operations

The daily routine in shrimp production tanks consists of taking temperature, pH, and oxygen data in the early hours of the morning (7 a.m.). After these measurements, water samples are collected for daily analysis of ammonia and nitrite. Only after the water samples are collected do the animals receive their first feeding, provided that oxygen levels are within the pre-established limits.

Once this step is completed, the samples of ammonia and nitrite are analysed, and actions to be taken in case of values that may compromise the cultivation are determined. These actions may include adding a carbon source to reduce ammonia or, in cases of high nitrite values, possibly renewing the water.

New feeding should be carried out at the beginning of the afternoon (2 p.m.). However, there is no need to check oxygen and temperature parameters at this time if the values observed in the morning are at adequate levels. By late afternoon (5 p.m.), new temperature and oxygen measurements should be taken to determine the total temperature variation in the cultivation tanks throughout the day. A final feeding should be provided in the evening (7 p.m.), concluding the daily feedings for the animals.

6.1.1.2 Feed & Nutrition

As previously mentioned, daily feedings are conducted in three periods with commercial pellets. Regarding nutrition, juveniles weighing up to 0.4 g are provided with starter rations containing 40 % crude protein and fine particle size. Animals weighing between 0.4 and 1 g also receive rations with 40 % crude protein, but with a larger particle size. Once they reach 1 g, the transition is made to a 1.6 mm pellet size feed, maintaining the 40 % crude protein composition. This feed is utilized until the animals reach the desired size for commercialization. Being part of a biofloc system, the shrimp utilize the biofloc as a supplementary source of food, contributing to improved food conversion rates in cultivation.

6.1.1.3 Stocking Density The IMTA system, utilizing bioflocs, can accommodate stocking densities of up to 450 shrimp /m³, achieving a final cultivation productivity of 4.5 kg/m².

Regarding water quality parameters (Table 17), some values must be observed so that cultivation remains within acceptable levels for all organisms involved in the IMTA system. For shrimp, dissolved

oxygen levels must be maintained above 5 mg/L. Extreme temperatures should be avoided, ideally maintaining the temperature in the range of 25 to 32 °C. Temperatures below this range lead to a reduction in the amount of feed to be offered to the animals, while temperatures above this range cause problems with dissolved oxygen, often making it impossible to offer the correct amount of food to the animals. The pH values must be maintained between 7.6 and 8.2 and the alkalinity above 150 mg/L of CaCO₃, mainly to enhance the action of bioflocs in the nitrification processes. Regarding Total Suspended Solids levels, these must be maintained in the range of 300 to 450 mg/L, an increase in this level of solids can lead to oxygen problems and also to the accumulation of organic matter at the bottom of the tanks.

Table 17. Optimal Environmental Ranges, oxygen, salinity, temp etc. for marine shrimp.

|
Nutrients |
|--|---|---|--|--|
| 25-32 C | 4-37 | >5,0 mg/L | 7,6-8,2 | NH ₄ ⁺ < 1,0 mg/L
NO ₂ ⁻ < 15,0 mg/L |

Nitrogenous compounds must be kept at low levels, ammonia must be kept below 1 mg/L, nitrite below 5 mg/L. Nitrate values will only become a problem if the cultivation water is reused for several cycles, as the accumulation of this compound is slower in the system. Phosphate values in the biofloc system are typically maintained at or below 2 mg/L.

6.1.1.4 Record Keeping

Water quality data are documented through manual methods, using paper spreadsheets that are subsequently digitized for long-term storage. These records serve as a valuable resource in the event of issues, capturing daily problems and documenting the measures taken to address them. This documentation becomes a vital reference for future problem-solving, particularly as work teams change over time.

Additionally, automatic systems for measuring parameters such as temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen, and total suspended solids are employed. Beyond recording variable values, these systems generate alarms when crucial cultivation parameters, like dissolved oxygen levels, experience significant drops.

6.1.1.5 Handling

Minimizing animal handling is crucial to reduce stress associated with removal from and return to the water. In shrimp farming tanks, animals are handled only once a week, specifically for biometric measurements.

6.1.1.6 Growth monitoring

Shrimp growth is evaluated on a weekly basis through biometric measurements. Randomly selected groups of 50 to 100 animals are individually weighed to determine the average shrimp weight (Figure 87). Using this average weight, the total biomass of each tank is calculated. Subsequently, considering both the biomass and the environmental parameters of the cultivation, feeding rates for the upcoming week are meticulously calculated.

Figure 87. Shrimp sampling (left) and shrimp stocking in the tank (right).

6.1.1.7 Predator Control

Predator control measures are deemed unnecessary in this cultivation system, given that it is conducted within a greenhouse environment. The greenhouse effectively prevents the presence of predators, ensuring a controlled and secure space for the animals.

6.1.1.8 Treatments

No direct disease treatments are administered to shrimp in this cultivation system. Instead, preventive measures are implemented throughout the entire cultivation cycle. This involves the application of probiotics to establish a robust bacterial community that effectively excludes potential pathogens through competitive mechanisms.

6.1.1.9 Mortality Removal & Disposal

Dead animals retrieved from the cultivation tank are frozen, and a specialized biological waste management company collects them at predetermined intervals. In the event of substantial mortalities, the collection of dead animals is conducted on demand.

6.1.1.10 Harvesting

Shrimp harvesting includes both total and partial approaches. During total harvesting, water from the shrimp farming tank is drained—either by pumping or gravity—into a reservoir tank for subsequent reuse. The drained tanks retain shrimp in mesh nets suitable for their size, facilitating accurate weighing. Following weighing, the shrimp undergo a rapid chlorination process with a sodium hypochlorite concentration of 5 ppm. Subsequently, the animals are immersed in tanks containing fresh water and ice for quick cooling, preserving their quality. Once immobilized on ice, the shrimp are transferred to boxes, packed with ice, and swiftly transported to the fish processing plant.

For partial harvesting, small nets traverse the tank, selectively collecting a desired number of animals. This method is employed when animal growth rate decreases, indicating that the system has reached its support capacity. After removing a specified number of animals, the remaining shrimp resume growth until total removal is executed (Figure 88).

Figure 88. Marine shrimp production cycle consisting of a ca. 1 month hatchery phase followed by a 1 month nursery phase and 3 months grow-out phase.

6.1.2 Tilapia - *Oreochromis niloticus*

6.1.2.1 Daily/Routine Operations

The daily operations in fish tanks closely parallel those for shrimp. This routine involves measuring temperature, pH, and oxygen levels in the early morning at 7 a.m. Following these measurements, water samples are collected for the daily analysis of ammonia and nitrite. The first feeding for the fish is scheduled only after the water samples have been collected, contingent upon oxygen levels falling within pre-established limits.

Upon completing this step, the ammonia and nitrite samples are analysed, and appropriate actions are determined in the case of values that could compromise the cultivation. These actions may include adding a carbon source to reduce ammonia or, in cases of elevated nitrite values, potentially renewing the water.

A second feeding is scheduled for the early afternoon at 2 p.m. However, there is no need to check oxygen and temperature parameters at this time if the morning values are within acceptable levels. By late afternoon at 5 p.m., new temperature and oxygen measurements are taken to assess the overall temperature variation in the cultivation tanks throughout the day. The final feeding for the fish is provided in the evening at 7 p.m., concluding the daily feeding routine.

6.1.2.2 Feed & Nutrition

Daily feedings for fish occur in three periods. For fish weighing between 30 to 60 g, the rations have reduced protein content, ranging from 40 % to 36 %, with a pellet size of 3 to 4 mm. Juveniles weighing 1 to 5 g are provided with powdered starter feeds containing 40 % to 45 % crude protein. Fish weighing between 5 and 30 g receive rations with 40 % to 45 % crude protein, but with larger particle sizes, in the range of 1 to 3 mm pellet size. From 60 g to 250 g, the feed maintains an average of 32 % crude protein with a pellet size between 4 and 6 mm. Beyond 250 g, the feed contains 32 % to 26 % crude protein, with a pellet size of 6 to 8 mm. This feed is utilized until reaching the desired size for commercialization. In the BFT system, tilapia utilize biofloc as a supplementary food source, enhancing food conversion rates. The presence of biofloc allows tilapia to be fed with a maximum of 2 % of its biomass, whereas in a conventional system it would be 6%.

6.1.2.3 Stocking Density

The IMTA system based on bioflocs can support stocking densities of up to 35 fishes per cubic meter, reaching a maximum system-supported density of 15 kg/m³.

Table 18. Optimal environmental ranges, oxygen, salinity, temperature etc. for Tilapia.

 Nutrients				
25-33 C	0-20	>4,0 mg/L	7,6-8,0	NH₄⁺ < 1,0 mg/L NO₂⁻ < 12,0 mg/L

As the water recirculates more than 100 % daily (300 L/h is the water pump flux), the parameters for fish are similar to those for shrimp (Table 18). Maintaining dissolved oxygen levels above 4 mg/L is crucial. It is advised to avoid extreme temperatures, ideally maintaining them in the range of 25 to 33 °C. Deviations from this range can impact feed consumption and dissolved oxygen levels. pH values should be kept between 7.6 and 8.0, with alkalinity above 150 mg/L of CaCO₃ to enhance biofloc action in nitrification processes. Total Suspended Solids levels must be maintained within the range of 300 to 450 mg/L, as an increase in solids can lead to oxygen problems and the accumulation of organic matter at the tank's bottom.

Nitrogenous compounds must be kept at low levels, ammonia must be kept below 1 mg/L, nitrite below 12 mg/L. Nitrate values will only become a problem if the cultivation water is reused for several cycles, as the accumulation of this compound is slower in the system. Phosphate values in the biofloc system are typically maintained at or below 2 mg/L.

6.1.2.4 Record Keeping

Cultivation data are documented through both manual and automatic methods. Manual recording involves paper spreadsheets, later digitized for long-term storage, serving as a comprehensive record for troubleshooting. These spreadsheets capture daily issues and document the measures taken to address them, providing a valuable reference for future problem-solving as work teams evolve over time. Automatic systems, measuring parameters such as temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen, and total suspended solids, are also employed. Beyond recording variable values, these systems generate alarms in case of critical drops in vital cultivation parameters, such as dissolved oxygen levels.

6.1.2.5 Handling

Minimizing animal handling is prioritized to mitigate stress associated with removal from and return to the water. In fish farming tanks, animals are handled every two weeks for biometric measurements only.

6.1.2.6 Growth monitoring

Fish growth is monitored every 15 days through biometric assessments. Randomly selected groups of 20 to 30 animals are anesthetized and individually weighed to determine the average fish weight (Figure 89). From this average weight, the total biomass of each tank is calculated. Using this biomass and considering environmental parameters, feeding rates for the upcoming weeks are meticulously calculated.

Figure 89. Tilapia juvenile (left) and adult after harvest (right).

6.1.2.7 Predator Control

Predator control measures are deemed unnecessary as the cultivation takes place inside a greenhouse, effectively preventing the presence of predators for these fish.

6.1.2.8 Treatments

Due to constant recirculation, tilapia receive preventive treatment through the application of probiotics in the water. However, when they reach 30 g, the fish are vaccinated to minimize the risk of contamination by bacteria of the genus *Streptococcus*, known to cause significant mortality in unvaccinated fish farms.

6.1.2.9 Mortality Removal & Disposal

Dead animals recovered in the tank are frozen, and a specialized biological waste management company collects them at predetermined intervals or, in the case of substantial mortalities, on-demand.

6.1.2.10 Harvesting

As with shrimp, tilapia harvests can be total or partial. During total harvesting, water from the fish farming tank is drained, either by pumping or gravity, into a reservoir tank for subsequent reuse. The drained tanks retain the tilapia in mesh nets suitable for their size, facilitating accurate weighing. Following weighing, the tilapia undergo a rapid chlorination process with a sodium hypochlorite

concentration of 5 ppm. Subsequently, the animals are immersed in tanks containing fresh water and ice for quick cooling, preserving their quality. Once immobilized on ice, the fish are transferred to boxes, packed with ice, and swiftly transported to the fish processing plant.

For partial harvesting, small nets traverse the tank, selectively collecting a desired number of animals. This method is employed when animal growth decreases, indicating that the system has reached its carrying capacity (15 kg/m³). After removing a specified number of animals, the remaining fish resume growth until total removal is executed, following the aforementioned procedure (Figure 90).

Figure 90. Tilapia production cycle consisting of a ca. 1-2 month hatchery phase followed by a 1-2 month nursery phase and 4-5 months grow-out phase.

6.1.3 Sea lettuce - *Ulva lactuca*

6.1.3.1 Daily/Routine Operations

The routine for tanks containing macroalgae differs from shrimp and fish tanks. As their role in the system is to absorb nitrogen and phosphate nutrients, feeding is unnecessary as these nutrients are dissolved in the cultivation water. The only daily activity involves gently moving the macroalgal biomass by hand to remove excess suspended solids deposited on them, enhancing light absorption throughout the day.

6.1.3.2 Feed & Nutrition

As photoautotrophic organisms, macroalgae extract all necessary elements for growth directly from the cultivation water. Daily analyses of nitrogen and phosphate compounds assess nutrient availability for optimal growth. The system receives daily inputs of nitrogen and phosphorous from feed and animal excreta. The bacteria in the bioflocs transform these compounds into products easily absorbed by the macroalgae, ensuring constant growth in the system.

6.1.3.3 Stocking Density

The recommended initial stocking density for macroalgal biomass in the IMTA system with bioflocs is 1 g/L. This calculation should consider the entire volume of the production system, not just the tank where the macroalgae are placed.

Table 19. Optimal environmental ranges, oxygen, salinity, temperature etc. for sea lettuce (species name).

|
Nutrients |
|---|--|--|---|--|
| <p>23-28 C</p> | <p>20-35</p> | <p>>5,0 mg/L</p> | <p>7,5-8,2</p> | <p>NH₄⁺ > 1,0 mg/L
 NO₃⁻ > 10,0 mg/L
 PO₄⁻³ > 8,0 mg/L</p> |

Due to continuous water recirculation, macroalgae adapt to the physicochemical parameters specific to shrimp and fish (Tables 19). However, for proper development, the presence of nitrogenous compounds and phosphate is crucial, and the suspended solids should not exceed 350 mg/L to prevent significant shading and reduce growth rates.

6.1.3.4 Record Keeping

Cultivation data are recorded manually using paper spreadsheets, later digitized for long-term storage. These records, capturing daily issues and measures taken to address them, serve as a valuable reference for future problem-solving, given changing work teams. Automatic systems measuring parameters such as temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen, and total suspended solids are also used. In addition to recording variable values, these systems generate alarms in the event of a drop in vital cultivation parameters, such as dissolved oxygen levels.

6.1.3.5 Handling

Daily handling of macroalgae involves gently shaking the biomass by hand during the morning routine to remove deposited material on the leaves. This process is conducted once a day, preferably in the morning, to maximize light incidence on the macroalgae's photosynthetic structures during periods of increased sunlight.

6.1.3.6 Growth monitoring

Every 15 days, the growth of macroalgae is assessed (Figure 91). Cultivation structures containing the macroalgal biomass, initially weighed before the production period, are removed from the water. After a 15 to 20-minute period in the shade to drain excess water, these structures are weighed again. The difference between the current weight and the weight from 15 days ago provides the biomass growth during this period.

Figure 91. Seaweed in the system and after harvest.

6.1.3.7 Predator Control

Predator control measures are unnecessary, as the cultivation takes place within a greenhouse, effectively preventing the presence of predators for these organisms.

6.1.3.8 Treatments

No specific treatments are required for macroalgae. However, as they are integrated into the system, the same probiotic used for fish and shrimp is also present in the water and tank structures where the macroalgae are placed.

6.1.3.9 Mortality Removal & Disposal

Macroalgae that present morphological abnormality or ghost tissues during cultivation are frozen, and a specialized biological waste management company collects them at predetermined intervals or, for significant mortalities, on-demand.

6.1.3.10 Harvesting

Harvesting of macroalgae occurs throughout the production cycle. At each biometry assessment, biomass is removed to maintain it at 1 g/L, ensuring a consistent production of macroalgae biomass. This biomass can be stored fresh or dried and crushed for use in feed and food product formulations. At the end of the production cycle, all biomass is harvested and utilized for various purposes as outlined above.

6.1.4 Sea Asparagus – *Salicornia neei*

6.1.4.1 Daily/Routine Operations

The routine of halophyte production in PVC NFT hydroponic benches is divided into two stages: 1st water quality analysis and 2nd maintenance of the structures. In the first stage, water samples are collected daily from each aquaponic bench at two specific points: the inlet and outlet water of each IMTA system, respectively, in the shrimp tank and in the return pipe of the bench. As for the second stage of structure maintenance (aquaponic bench), the flow and water flow (average flow rate 455.3 L/h) passing through the benches are checked daily, as well as identifying possible leaks and water passage obstructions. The plants are constantly irrigated with water from the shrimp culture biofloc, resulting in biofloc accumulation in the channels of the aquaponic benches. Weekly washings of the structures are necessary with the aid of a hose to remove excess solids and prevent both channel obstruction and water overflow. The drained solids were returned to the shrimp raceways (Figure 92).

Figure 92. Accumulation of solids on the benches, and on the roots of the plants, being removed with the assistance of a hose.

6.1.4.2 Stocking Density

The IMTA systems are connected with a aquaponics system arranged with PVC nutrient film technique (NFT) growing *S. neei* halophytes, positioned on the exterior side of the greenhouse (Figure 93). Each aquaponic bench has 6 tubes measuring 85 mm X 45 mm and 3 m in length (area = 4.8 m²), containing 19 plants in each tube and a total of 114 plants per bench (6 benches = 684 plants).

Figure 93. Layout of the PVC aquaponic benches, installed outside of the greenhouse.

The water quality parameters for *Salicornia neei* are the same as those for shrimp farming, with the parameters of greatest interest for plant growth being phosphate and, especially, nitrate concentrations, which should be above 10 mg/L (Table 20). Low nitrate concentrations can be a limiting factor for plant development, as well as low solar radiation. Air temperature in this region varied between 9.0 and 32.5 °C (average = 22.0 ± 0.4 °C) in summer, and the maximum solar radiation is 3.9 J/m²/s (3900 W/m²; average daily radiation = 17.87 ± 0.76 MJ/m²/d).

Table 20. Optimal environmental ranges for sea asparagus.

|
Nutrients |
|--|---|---|--|--|
| 25-32 C | 4-37 | >5,0 mg/L | 7,6-8,2 | NH ₄ ⁺ < 1,0 mg/L
NO ₂ ⁻ < 15,0 mg/L |

6.1.4.3 Record Keeping

The collected data, both on water quality and biometrics, are recorded on printed spreadsheets and later digitized for analysis and monitoring of the system's development. This proves crucial for identifying potential irregularities and applying necessary corrections to maintain the proper functioning of the experimental units. The printed spreadsheets are archived and accessed when needed for any record-related queries.

6.1.4.4 Handling

Daily handling of the plants is minimal, except when pruning is necessary for biometric analysis.

6.1.4.5 Growth monitoring

The plant growth is assessed through pruning, carried out every 30 days of cultivation. During each pruning, all *S. neei* plants on the benches are identified and cut 4 cm above the upper edge of each cup (Figure 94A and B).

Following pruning, the fresh above ground biomass of each plant (stems with branches) is measured using a precision scale (Figure 94C). The fresh root biomass of each plant, which grows outside the cups, is quantified only at the end of the experiment, also through weighing on a scale. In each experiment, the stem and root biomasses of 10 plants from each bench are dried in an oven (60 °C for 48 h) and weighed on a precision scale, allowing for the calculation of dry biomass (Figure 95A-D). Stem succulence is estimated by the percentage difference between fresh and dry biomasses. The percentage of biomass allocated to stems (aboveground biomass) is estimated by dividing the stem biomass values by the total biomass formed (stems + roots) and multiplying by 100. Biomass production per bench area is also estimated by summing the individual biomasses of all plants on the bench and then dividing this value by the bench area (4.8 m²). Additionally, the stem height (in cm) and the number of branches exceeding 10 cm in length for each plant are quantified (Figure 94D).

Figure 94. Harvesting of *S. neei* plants. (A) Pruning of plants, keeping the stem at cup height. (B) Collection and storage in bags for analysis of plant samples in the laboratory. (C) Weighing of fresh biomass. (D) Stem biometrics of the plants.

Figure 95. Assessment of dry biomass produced by *S. neei* plants. (A) Detail of stems and roots of plants on drying trays. (B) Drying of biomass samples in the oven. (C) Weighing and (D) storage of the dried material.

6.1.4.6 *Mortality Removal & Disposal*

In the current cultivation, the average survival rate ranged from 91 to 85 %. Plants considered dead are discarded as organic waste.

6.1.4.7 *Harvesting*

Harvests are carried out based on biometrics, with all plants being harvested every 30 days. *Salicornia neei* is a perennial plant capable of regrowth from its stem after pruning. All plants are weighed and measured to assess growth and productivity indices, and then distributed for consumption among the academic community at the Marine Aquaculture Center (Figure 95).

6.1.5 Brazilian native oyster – *Crassostrea gasar*

6.1.5.1 *Daily/Routine Operations*

The routine for the tanks where the oysters, which are sessile filter-feeding organisms, are housed consists mainly of daily visual inspections of the structures containing these animals. This is done to assess the presence of dead animals, which need to be removed, as well as any potential damage to the cultivation structures.

6.1.5.2 *Feed & Nutrition*

As oysters, being filter-feeding organisms and being part of a cultivation environment with bioflocs, utilize these bioflocs, which are abundantly present throughout the entire cultivation period, as food no limitation of the growth of these organisms has been observed. By removing the bioflocs for feeding, the oysters fulfill their role as biological control of total suspended solids levels (Figure 96).

6.1.5.3 *Stocking Density*

The recommended stocking density for oysters in the IMTA system with bioflocs is 10 individuals/m³. This may vary depending on the volume of the system being used. For proper development, temperatures higher than 28°C should be avoided, and the suspended solids should not exceed 250 mg/L, considering the production in BFT system (Table 21).

Table 21. Optimum environmental ranges for the Brazilian native oyster (species name).

|
Nutrients |
|--|---|---|--|--|
| 20-28 C | 18-37 | >5,0 mg/L | 7,4-8,2 | TSS <250 mg/L |

6.1.5.4 Record Keeping

Cultivation data are initially recorded manually using paper spreadsheets and later digitized for long-term storage. These records document daily observations and actions taken to address any issues, serving as valuable references for future problem-solving, especially considering changes in work teams. Additionally, automatic systems measuring parameters such as temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen, and total suspended solids are employed. Apart from recording variable values, these systems also generate alarms in case of any significant deviations in vital cultivation parameters, such as dissolved oxygen levels.

6.1.5.5 Handling

The daily management involves removing the cultivation structures from the water and analyzing the integrity of the structures as well as the presence of dead oysters, which need to be removed to prevent degradation of water quality.

6.1.5.6 Growth monitoring

Every 30 days, shell length measurements are taken to assess oyster growth. The average value is then subtracted from the previous average value to establish the average growth over the period.

Figure 96. Production of Brazilian native oyster – *Crassostrea gasar*.

6.1.5.7 Predator Control

Predator control measures are unnecessary, as the cultivation takes place within a greenhouse, effectively preventing the presence of predators for these organisms.

6.1.5.8 Treatments

No specific treatments are required for oysters. However, as they are integrated into the system, the same probiotic used for fish and shrimp is also present in the water and tank structures where the oysters are placed.

6.1.5.9 Mortality Removal & Disposal

The oysters that die during cultivation are frozen, and a specialized biological waste management company collects them at predetermined intervals or, in the case of significant mortalities, upon request.

6.1.5.10 Harvesting

The harvesting of oysters occurs at the end of the cultivation cycle (Figure 97), and the oysters can be sold while still fresh.

Figure 97. Oyster production cycle consisting of a ca. 1 month hatchery phase followed by a 2-3 weeks settling phase and 8-10 months grow-out phase.

6.2 Health

Health assessments are conducted during the handling of animals, seaweeds and plants integrated into the system, following the guidelines drawn up by the Brazilian Ministry of Agriculture and Livestock. For shrimps, observations include checking for necrosis in appendages and the animal's body, greening of the uropod (indicative of possible vibriosis – Figure 98), and examining the filling of the digestive tract and hepatopancreas to gauge proper feeding. In fish, assessments focus on the presence of white dots on the body, the normal appearance of eyes, absence of abdominal dilation, cleanliness of gills, and the absence of materials or parasites. For macroalgae, whitish blades may indicate light issues or nutrient deficiencies. Any reported problems prompt the collection of animals, seaweeds or plants for more detailed histology and biochemistry analyses to accurately identify and address underlying issues.

Figure 98. Problems that can be observed in the IMTA tanks. Shrimp with necrosis (black spot - left), shrimp with *Vibrio* (blue-green animal - centre), seaweed with ghost tissues (right).

The Ministry of Aquaculture and Fisheries is the main authority for the management and development of fisheries and aquaculture in Brazil. Alongside the Federal District, the States and Municipal Authorities, and the Ministry of Aquaculture and Fisheries are responsible for the granting of licences and permits for aquaculture. The Institute of the Environment and Renewable Natural Resources (IBAMA) is concerned with the environment and deals with conservation of natural resources (including aquatic resources), environmental licences and water quality control¹⁷⁴. Regarding the seaweed and halophytes health, no regulations were established in the country.

¹⁷⁴https://firms.fao.org/fi/website/FIRetrieveAction.do?dom=legalframework&xml=nalo_brazil.xml#tcNB0076

6.3 Biosecurity

Biosecurity measures within the system are highly effective due to its closed greenhouse environment. All circulation openings are equipped with screens to prevent the entry of birds, known carriers of pathogens. The closed doors also prevent access by other land animals. For water, in the case of initiating cultivation without water reuse, all pumped water undergoes chlorination. After chlorine removal, probiotics are applied to stimulate the colonization of known and fast-growing bacteria, excluding potential pathogens through competition. Upon arrival, all animals and plants undergo a quarantine period to assess the presence of diseases or parasites that could pose problems during cultivation. Subsequently, animals are transferred to production units. Regular visits by the responsible veterinarian are conducted to evaluate animal health and ensure adherence to animal welfare protocols.

6.4 Welfare

The recirculation system's inherent characteristics may lead to occasional imbalances in variables for the species involved. Continuous analyses over time have demonstrated that, despite the high densities and potential turbidity, no stress factors were observed in the cultivated animals. This indicates that the system provides an environment where animal welfare is maintained in equilibrium, fostering significant growth rates and high survival rates compared to other farming systems.

7 The Benefits and Challenges of IMTA

7.1 Benefits

IMTA benefits are environmental sustainability through bio-mitigation, economic stability through product diversification and, risk reduction and social acceptability through better management practices. IMTA may lead to increased biomass production, waste reduction, and new opportunities with regard to spatial use and species diversification.

The following are the benefits IMTA can potentially bring to a predominantly monoculture activity:

- Reduction in ecological impacts.
- From a linear to a more circular model, allowing for a whole ecosystem approach.
- “Waste” reduction service to the industry through bioremediation. The “wastes” become “co-products”, using the vocabulary of circular economy.
- Additional crops produced in IMTA (e.g., seaweeds) can be used as feed or feed ingredients for fed species, enhancing circularity and reducing feed costs.
- Inclusion of seaweeds in IMTA allows for increased recirculation and a reduction in pumping (electrical) costs.
- Full recirculation in IMTA can provide protection to farms during harmful algal bloom (HAB) events (by not pumping seawater from the adjacent ocean during HAB events).
- Seaweeds in IMTA systems or as a feed/aquafeed ingredients have a beneficial impact on the microbiome.
- Improving the societal perception of aquaculture.
- IMTA grown products may have a market advantage.
- Different IMTA models can bring different community benefits – such as with the re-stocking initiatives.
- Optimization of the space available, numerous products to be produced within the same space, utilising the resource effectively and efficiently.
- Commercial benefit from growing other products in their site.
- Diversity provides alternative incomes and cash-flows, increasing the resilience of the business.

- Beyond biomass – true value in added ecosystem services and nutrient trading credits that some low trophic species provide before being valued at the farm gate¹⁷⁵.

7.2 Challenges

The challenges faced by IMTA production are largely economic and regulatory. Generally, there is an imbalance in income between the trophic layers and this can discourage the adaptation of the concept. Adding other trophic levels to monoculture set-ups increases the complexity of farm husbandry and infrastructure, and increases costs and efforts. Farmers are familiar with current systems and change is unattractive and can be risky.

Further research needs to be carried out to demonstrate that profits can increase compared to those of conventional production systems. Issues of awareness and education about these innovative production systems need to be addressed. Concerns around biosecurity when additional species are introduced, or when water is recirculated or co-products are returned to the systems as feed, need to be researched and assurance given to allow for increased societal acceptance of IMTA products.

Competition for space when low-trophic, lower value, species are introduced into systems can cause problems; however, the economic, biological and societal benefits of integration need to be demonstrated. The whole value of the IMTA production systems and the ecosystem services they provide have to first be recognized. This is the phase we are presently in. Next will be the valuation/monetization of these services and their uses for regulatory and financial incentives to make aquaculturists, regulators, aquaculture practices and society evolve.

¹⁷⁵ Chopin, T., Costa-Pierce, B.A., Troell, M., Hurd, C.L., Costello, M.J., Backman, S., Buschmann, A., Cuhel, R., Duarte, C.M., Gröndahl, F., Heasman, K., Haroun, R.J., Johansen, J., Jueterbock, A., Lench, M., Lindell, S., Pavia, H., Ricart, A.M., Sundell, K.S., and Yarish, C., 2024. Deep-ocean seaweed dumping for carbon sequestration: questionable, risky and not the best use of valuable biomass. *One Earth* 7(3): 359-364.